

Proposal

For renewed funding of NFDI4ING in the National
Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)

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Abbreviations

NFDI4ING task areas

A	Alex
B	Betty
C	Caden
CPT	Copilot – Assistance Systems & Artificial Intelligence
D	Doris
E	Ellen
F	Fiona
FIS	Federated Interactive Data Space
J	Journal ing.grid
M&O	Management & Outreach
SKG	Semantic Metadata & Knowledge Graphs
TES	Training, Education & Standardisation

Other abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AAI	Authentication and authorization infrastructure
AARC2	Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration
CESAER	Conference of European Schools for Advanced Engineering Education and Research
CIM	Common Information Model
CRC	Collaborative Research Center
DALIA	Data Literacy Alliance
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DCE	Data Collections Explorer
DMP	Data Management Plan
DT	Digital Twin
ELN	Electronic Lab Notebook
ELSA	Ethical, Legal, Social Aspects
EMMO	Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESG	Environmental Social Governance
EUDAT CDI	EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure
EXC	Excellenzcluster (Cluster of Excellence)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-Usable
FDM	Forschungsdatenmanagement (Research Data Management)
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
FDP	Field Database Platform
FID	Fachinformationsdienst (Special Information Service)
GCS	Gauss Centre for Supercomputing
genAI	Generative Artificial Intelligence
GWK	Gemeinsame Wissenschaftskonferenz (Joint Science Conference)
HeFDI	Hessische Forschungsdateninfrastrukturen (Hessian Research Data Infrastructures)

HLRS	Höchstleistungsrechenzentrum Stuttgart (High Performance High-Performance Computing Center Stuttgart)
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IG RDM4Eng	Interest Group Research Data Management for Engineering
IRL	Integration Readiness Level
JKG	Journal Knowledge Graph
JSC	Jülich Supercomputing Center
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLM	Large Language Model
LO	Liaison Officer
LRZ	Leibniz-Rechenzentrum der Bayerischen Akademie der Wissenschaften (Leibniz Supercomputing Center)
LSDF	Large Scale Data Facility
MaRDA	Materials Research Data Alliance
ML	Machine Learning
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NHR	Nationales Hochleistungsrechnen (German National High Performance Computing)
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies
OD-Rex	NFDI Consortium Open Database for Real World Robot Experiments
OER	Open Educational Resources
OWL	W3C Web Ontology Language
PID	Persistent Identifier
PRACE	Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe
RADAR	Research Data Repository
RAG	Retrieval Augmented Generation
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RDMO	Research Data Management Organiser
Rfil	Rat für Informationsinfrastrukturen (German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures)
RSE	Research Software Engineering
RSEA	Research Software Engineering Assistant
SIG	Special Interest Group
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
TA	Task Area
TKNFDM	Thüringer Kompetenznetzwerk Forschungsdatenmanagement
TRR	Transregio Collaborative Research Center
TS	Terminology Service
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
XAIR	Explainable AI ready

Figures

Figure 1: Overview of NFDI4ING task areas in a second funding period. Abbreviations: Training, Education, and Standardisation (TES); Semantic Metadata and Knowledge Graphs (KGS), Federated Interactive Data Space (FIS), Copilot - Assistance Systems and AI (CPT)	26
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B-1 Proposal Template Part 1

1 General Information

Name of the consortium in English and German

German National Research Data Infrastructure for Engineering Sciences (NFDI4ING)

Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur für die Ingenieurwissenschaften (NFDI4ING)

Summary of the proposal in English and German

NFDI4ING will consolidate and scale its ongoing efforts of transforming the engineering sciences towards being more open, more efficient, and better connected. As new methods begin to revolutionize science, NFDI4ING extends its support portfolio for data-driven workflows. Its target audience remains unchanged and encompasses engineers in all domains of research. The successful concept of orthogonal archetypes will be adapted to gained insights and anticipated trends.

Compared to the first period of NFDI4ING, the overlap and resulting synergies between two former archetypes and respective task areas (TAs) is acknowledged and the two will be consolidated into one new archetype and task area. The formerly monolithic Base Services are transformed into four new task areas devoted to overarching solutions. Centralised outreach tasks are assigned to the management and the NFDI4ING diamond open access journal ing.grid will be promoted into its own task area. While the first period of NFDI4ING has been dominated by the development of services according to the needs of the community, the second period will shift focus to the perpetuation of services, their scaling, and their connectivity with other services of NFDI and beyond. To ensure services work effectively for the community while shifting focus, NFDI4ING will assign a liaison officer (LO) to each task area, thereby establishing a direct personal link between the task area and the community.

NFDI4ING will hone further in on the closing of data cycles, minimising both friction loss and redundant work by eliminating dead ends in the scientific information flow. As a foundation, NFDI4ING will leverage self-contained data entities embedded in knowledge graphs. Furthermore, NFDI4ING will be implementing FAIR digital objects (FDOs) and established vocabularies, thus ensuring that research data is FAIR and AI-ready. The following ten guiding principles summarise NFDI4ING's main approach:

- 1) We are deeply embedded in the engineering research community.
- 2) All our offers serve all engineering scientists at German research institutions.

- 3) We standardise and automate the research data management (RDM) processes wherever possible and support the scientists represented by the archetypes with an NFDI4ING RDM Copilot.
- 4) We close data cycles.
- 5) All research data managed by NFDI4ING's concepts and services will be FAIR and AI-ready in 2030.
- 6) We empower engineering research institutions and universities to include RDM and NFDI4ING's solutions in their curricula as well as their examination and doctoral regulations.
- 7) The usage of our concepts and services increases the scientific reputation of our researchers and the academic credit of our students and doctoral candidates.
- 8) We deepen our collaboration with industry stakeholders and ISO/DIN.
- 9) We contribute significantly to the vision of OneNFDI¹.
- 10) We feel responsible for the long-term sustainability of RDM in engineering.

German:

NFDI4ING wird seine laufenden Bemühungen um eine Umgestaltung der Ingenieurwissenschaften in Richtung mehr Offenheit, Effizienz und bessere Vernetzung konsolidieren und ausbauen. Während neue Methoden die Wissenschaft revolutionieren, erweitert NFDI4ING sein Portfolio für datengetriebene Workflows. Das Zielpublikum bleibt unverändert und umfasst Ingenieur*innen in allen Bereichen der Forschung. Das erfolgreiche Konzept der orthogonalen Archetypen wird an die gewonnenen Erkenntnisse und zu erwartende Trends angepasst.

Im Vergleich zur ersten Förderperiode werden die Überschneidungen und die sich daraus ergebenden Synergien zwischen zwei früheren Archetypen anerkannt und beide zu einem neuen Archetyp zusammengefasst. Die ehemals monolithischen Basisdienste werden in vier neue Task Areas überführt, die sich mit übergreifenden Lösungen befassen. Während in der ersten Periode die Entwicklung von Services entsprechend den Bedürfnissen der Community im Vordergrund stand, wird sich der Fokus in der zweiten Periode auf die Aufrechterhaltung der Services, ihre Skalierung und ihre Konnektivität mit der NFDI und darüber hinaus verlagern. Um sicherzustellen, dass die Services effektiv für die Community arbeiten, wird NFDI4ING jeder Task Area (TA) einen Liaison Officer (LO) zuweisen.

Generell wird sich NFDI4ING weiter auf die Schließung von Datenkreisläufen konzentrieren und sowohl Reibungsverluste als auch redundante Arbeit durch die Beseitigung von Sackgassen im

¹ OneNFDI describes a desired convergence of multiple infrastructures for RDM across domains into one. It is a concept that emerged from the preparation of a 2019 paper on Cross-Cutting-Topics.

wissenschaftlichen Informationsfluss minimieren. Als Grundlage dafür wird NFDI4ING in sich geschlossene Datenentitäten nutzen, die in Wissensgraphen eingebettet sind. Darüber hinaus wird NFDI4ING FAIR Digital Objects und etablierte Vokabulare implementieren und damit sicherstellen, dass Forschungsdaten FAIR und KI-fähig sind. Die folgenden zehn Leitprinzipien fassen den Hauptansatz von NFDI4ING zusammen:

- 1) Wir sind tief in der ingenieurwissenschaftlichen Forschungsgemeinschaft verankert.
- 2) Unsere Angebote dienen allen Ingenieur*innen an deutschen Forschungseinrichtungen.
- 3) Wir standardisieren und automatisieren die Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM)-Prozesse wo immer möglich und unterstützen die durch die Archetypen repräsentierten Forschenden mit einem NFDI4ING RDM Copilot.
- 4) Wir schließen Datenkreisläufe.
- 5) Alle Forschungsdaten, die durch die Konzepte und Dienste von NFDI4ING verwaltet werden, sind im Jahr 2030 FAIR und KI-fähig.
- 6) Wir befähigen ingenieurwissenschaftliche Forschungseinrichtungen und Universitäten, FDM und die Lösungen von NFDI4ING in ihre Curricula sowie Prüfungs- und Promotionsordnungen aufzunehmen.
- 7) Die Nutzung unserer Konzepte und Dienstleistungen erhöht die wissenschaftliche Reputation unserer Forschenden und lässt sich für unsere Studierenden und Promovierenden als erbrachte Leistung anerkennen.
- 8) Wir vertiefen unsere Zusammenarbeit mit der Industrie und ISO/DIN.
- 9) Wir tragen maßgeblich zur Vision von OneNFDI² bei.
- 10) Wir fühlen uns für die langfristige Nachhaltigkeit von FDM in den Ingenieurwissenschaften verantwortlich.

Applicant institution

Applicant institution	Location
Technische Universität Darmstadt (TUDa)	Darmstadt

Spokesperson

Spokesperson	Institution, location
Pelz, Peter F.	TUDa, Darmstadt

Co-applicant institutions

Co-applicant institutions	Location
Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM)	Berlin
Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR)	Köln

² OneNFDI beschreibt die angestrebte Konvergenz paralleler Forschungsdateninfrastrukturen verschiedener Disziplinen und Forschungsbereiche zu einer einzigen. Das Konzept entstand bei der Ausarbeitung eines Papiers zu Querschnittsthemen 2019.

Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ)	Jülich
Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT)	Karlsruhe
Leibniz-Universität Hannover (LUH)	Hannover
Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen (RWTH)	Aachen
TIB - Leibniz-Informationszentrum Technik und Naturwissenschaften und Universitätsbibliothek	Hannover
Technische Universität Braunschweig (TUBS)	Braunschweig
Technische Universität Clausthal (TUC)	Clausthal-Zellerfeld
Technische Universität München (TUM)	München
Universität Stuttgart (US)	Stuttgart

Co-spokespersons

Co-spokespersons	Institution, location	Task area(s)
Auer, Sören	TIB, Hannover	Semantic Metadata & Knowledge Graphs (SKG)
Beetz, Jakob	RWTH, Aachen	Ellen (E)
Bronger, Torsten	FZJ, Jülich	Caden (C)
Dreizler, Andreas	TUDa, Darmstadt	Alex (A)
Flemisch, Bernd	US, Stuttgart	Betty (B)
Iglezakis, Dorothea	US, Stuttgart	Copilot - Assistance Systems and AI (CPT)
Jagus, Gerald	TUDa, Darmstadt	Management & Outreach (M)
Kuckertz, Patrick	FZJ, Jülich	Ellen (E)
Lachmayer, Roland	LUH, Hannover	Fiona (E)
Langenbach, Christian	DLR, Köln	Training, Education & Standardisation (TES)
Linxweiler, Jan	TUBS, Braunschweig	Betty (B)
Müller, Matthias	RWTH, Aachen	Federated Interactive Data Space (FIS)
Nestler, Britta	KIT, Karlsruhe	Doris (D)
Pelz, Peter	TUDa, Darmstadt	Alex (A), Journal ing.grid (J)
Politze, Marius	RWTH, Aachen	Semantic Metadata & Knowledge Graphs (SKG)
Schmitt, Robert H.	RWTH, Aachen	Training, Education & Standardisation (TES), Fiona (F)
Schwarz, Annett	RWTH, Aachen	Management & Outreach (M)
Selzer, Michael	KIT, Karlsruhe	Caden (C)
Sens, Irina	TIB, Hannover	Semantic Metadata & Knowledge Graphs (SKG)
Stäcker, Thomas	TUDa, Darmstadt	Copilot - Assistance Systems and AI (CPT)
Stemmer, Christian	TUM, München	Doris (D)
Streit, Achim	KIT, Karlsruhe	Federated Interactive Data Space (FIS)
Unger, Jörg F.	BAM, Berlin	Betty (B)
Wittek, Stefan	TUC, Clausthal	Copilot - Assistance Systems and AI (CPT)

Participants

Participating institutions	Location
Access e.V.	Aachen
Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften (Leibniz-Rechenzentrum)	Garching
DataCite e.V.	Hannover

Dekane- und Abteilungsleiterkonferenz für Architektur, Raumplanung und Landschaftsarchitektur in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland e.V. (DARL)	Weimar
Verein zur Förderung eines Deutschen Forschungsnetzes (DFN)	Berlin
Fraunhofer Institut für Produktionstechnologie (IPT)	Aachen
Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH (GWDG)	Göttingen
Helmholtz-Zentrum hereon	Geesthacht
Hochschule Darmstadt (h_da)	Darmstadt
Hochschule Fulda (HF)	Fulda
Hochschule für Technik Stuttgart (HFT)	Stuttgart
Hochschule Karlsruhe (HK)	Karlsruhe
Hochschule RheinMain (HSRM)	Wiesbaden
Leibniz-Institut für Plasmaforschung und Technologie (INP)	Greifswald
Physikalisch-technische Bundesanstalt (PTB)	Braunschweig
Ruhr-Universität Bochum (RUB)	Bochum
Sächsische Landesbibliothek - Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden (SLUB)	Dresden
Technische Hochschule Köln (TH K)	Köln
Technische Hochschule Mittelhessen (THM)	Gießen
Technische Hochschule Wildau	Wildau
Technische Universität Berlin	Berlin
Technische Universität Chemnitz	Chemnitz
Technische Universität Hamburg	Hamburg
Universität Freiburg	Freiburg
Universität Paderborn	Paderborn

Contributions of participant institutions:

Access e.V.: Contributing to standards, ontologies and data formats for FAIR data handling of simulation data (c.f. Betty).

Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften (Leibniz Rechenzentrum): Will contribute to task area Doris on topics like data accessibility, storage/archiving of large datasets, reproducibility, the metadata4ing ontology (m4i), as well as other FAIR data and interoperability approaches in supercomputing.

DataCite e.V.: DataCite provides expertise in Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and collaborates in the task areas SKG and Ellen.

DARL e.V.: Will help carry out the development of use cases for the domains architecture, urban and regional planning. Will also collaborate on the definition of metadata standards, and on the definition of user requirements for research data environments, in particular user interfaces.

Deutsches Forschungsnetz e.V. (DFN): Closely collaborates with task area FIS in the management of digital identities and federated access to resources within and across the NFDI consortia.

Fraunhofer Institut für Produktionstechnologie (IPT): Is an integral part of task Area Fiona and collaborates in the measures F-1, F-2 and F-5.

Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH (GWDG): Contributes to the to the sustainable development and operation of federated service infrastructures.

Helmholtz-Zentrum hereon: Will help carry out the development of integrated digital workflows to automate scale bridging computer simulations of materials properties, examining the potential of Large Language Models (LLMs) as knowledge graphs, address integrating information from diverse disciplines, building a data repository compiling and cataloguing of corrosion and microstructural data.

Hochschule Darmstadt: Supplies access to industry networks, mainly SMEs in the Rhine-Main region and several internationally operating companies to allow for technology transfer and the generation of use cases.

Hochschule für Technik Stuttgart: Provides measurement data from their 3D scanning vibrometer via REST API and acts as pilot user/use case for metadata structure recommendations to store the measurement data in a suitable form in a component library and make it usable according to FAIR principles.

Hochschule Fulda: Will disseminate results and services of NFDI4ING to interested engineers at industry partners (including small and medium-sized enterprises), public authorities and private sector organisations and provide feedback and insights.

Hochschule Karlsruhe: Will contribute to the task areas TES, CPT, Doris, and Ellen by adding expertise on topics like digital twins (DTs), metadata models, and AI

Hochschule RheinMain: Contributes implementation and dissemination of the standards and services developed by NFDI4ING in research and teaching at the HRM and in HeFDI, provides good practice examples for the use of electronic lab books (eLabFTW) in the training of engineers, especially in application-orientated practical courses.

Leibniz-Institut für Plasmaforschung und Technologie (INP): Provides support and interdisciplinary connections in the task areas CPT, Alex, Betty and Caden.

Physikalisch-technische Bundesanstalt: Supports the further development and practical application of the metadata4ing ontology.

Ruhr-Universität Bochum: Offers to coordinate activities on structured data storage and generation of FAIR digital objects between NFDI4ING and NFDI-MatWerk. Provides support and expertise in the quality testing, management and provision of heterogeneous data in the construction industry. Collaborates in offering courses and trainings on applications of machine learning for mechanical systems to students and professionals.

Sächsische Landesbibliothek - Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Dresden (SLUB): SLUB supports activities regarding standards, data quality and curation as well as data

publication and long-term archiving. SLUB is also involved in strengthening open publication infrastructures and collaborating with ing.grid (task area J).

Technische Hochschule Köln: Contributes implementation and dissemination of the standards and services developed by NFDI4ING in research and teaching.

Technische Hochschule Mittelhessen: Provides feedback to and community engagement with NFDI4ING products and services, as well as local training for those services.

Technische Hochschule Wildau: Collaborates in the task areas TES and Alex and provides connections to the state initiative (“Landesinitiative”) FDM-Brandenburg

Technische Universität Berlin: Participates in task area Fiona, particularly in measures F-2, F-4, and F-5. Supplies research insights in the field of Digital Twins to enhance data management approaches, ensuring interoperability and scalability. Supports development and refinement of processes for managing distributed and heterogeneous development data, such as CAD, within PDM/PLM systems by leveraging Data Mesh and Fairness principles and provides feedback as pilot user.

Technische Universität Chemnitz: Will contribute by applying ontologies and data norms developed in the NFDI4ING and provide feedback, experience, and suggestions. Will also share models and tools with NFDI4ING, e.g., in the context of Trustworthy AI or related to data integration.

Technische Universität Hamburg: Contributes to task areas CPT and Ellen, primarily in the fields of LLMs as knowledge graphs, and interdisciplinary large multimodal AI models. Also offers active participation in NFDI4ING outreach and knowledge transfer activities, e.g., the SIG Metadata and Ontologies, Community Meetings etc.

Universität Freiburg: Is active in task areas TES, FIS, Betty and Caden. Supports data management with RO-Crates and dtool, provides best practices for engineering of research software, particularly on software packaging (conda) and containerization, and offers the integration of *Galaxy* and *contact.engineering* into a federated data space.

Universität Paderborn: Collaborates in task areas TES, SKG, J, Caden, and Doris. Provides connections and prospective use cases related to high-performance computing via the national high performance computing alliance. Is also active in several NFDI consortia (incl. and offers multidisciplinary and trans-consortial use cases.

Participating individuals	Institution, location
Atakan, Burak	Universität Duisburg-Essen, Institute for Energy and Materials Processes, Duisburg
Begoin, Mathias	TIB, FID Move, FID Materials Science, Hannover
Brand, Ortrun	Philipps-Universität Marburg, Hessische Forschungsdateninfrastrukturen (HeFDI), Marburg
Brümmer, Andreas	Technische Universität Dortmund, Chair of Fluidics, Dortmund
Cyra, Magdalene	Universität Duisburg-Essen, FDM.NRW, Essen

Fasoulas, Stefanos	Universität Stuttgart, CRC 1667 ATLAS, Stuttgart
Fimmers, Christian	RWTH Aachen, EXC Internet of Production, Aachen
Garcke, Harald	Universität Regensburg, Chair of Mathematics VIII, Regensburg
Gerlach, Roman	Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Thüringian Competence Network Research Data Management, Jena
Hartmaier, Alexander	Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Interdisciplinary Centre for Advanced Materials Simulation (ICAMS), Bochum
Hezel, Dominik	Goethe-Universität Frankfurt a. M., Frankfurt a. M.
Johannsen, Jochen	RWTH Aachen, University Library, Aachen
Jung, Anne	Helmut-Schmidt-Universität, Professorship for Protective Systems, Hamburg
Kirchner, Frank	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz (DFKI), Bremen
Kleinert, Sven	Leibniz-Universität Hannover, EXC PhoenixD, Hannover
König, Markus	Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Chair for Computing in Engineering, Bochum
Köstler, Harald	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Erlangen National High Performance Computing Center, Erlangen
Kübel, Christian	KIT, Institute of Nanotechnology (INT), Karlsruhe
Langer, Sabine C.	Universität Braunschweig, SFB/TRR 364 SynTrac
Lanza, Gisela	KIT, Institute of Nanotechnology (INT), Karlsruhe
Maric, Tomislav	TUDa, Mathematical Modelling and Analysis, Darmstadt
Marx, Steffen	Technische Universität Dresden, Institute of Concrete Structures, Dresden
Rehwald, Stephanie	Universität Duisburg-Essen, University Library & SFB/TRR 196 MARIE, Essen
Schaaf, Peter	Technische Universität Ilmenau, Materials for Electrical Engineering and Electronics, Ilmenau
Schlenz, Hartmut	Forschungszentrum Jülich, Jülich
Schmidt, Michael	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Erlangen National High Performance Computing Center, Erlangen
Weiskopf, Daniel	Universität Stuttgart, EXC IntCDC
Wortmann, Thomas	Universität Stuttgart, EXC IntCDC
Xu, Bai-Xang	TUDa, Mechanics of Functional Materials, Darmstadt

Contribution of participating persons:

Atakan, Burak: Contributes practical experience and workflows for RDM in coordinated projects, both large and small. Supports development of established data bases or repositories for the field of thermodynamics, kinetics, and combustion.

Begoin, Mathias: Supports task areas TES and SKG as representative of the “specialised information services” (Fachinformationsdienste, FID) for mobility and transportation (FID move), and for materials science (FID Materials Science).

Brand, Ortrun: Represents the federal state RDM initiative “Hessische Forschungsdateninfrastrukturen” (HeFDI), which contributes their network for knowledge exchange and dissemination.

Brümmer, Andreas: Contributes to task area Alex by collaborating in the dissemination of the FAIR principle for research data in the engineering sciences.

Cyra, Magdalene: Represents the federal state RDM initiative FDM.NRW. Supports the information exchange between NFDI4ING and the universities in North Rhine-Westphalia and collaborates in offering workshops on FDM tools.

Fasoulas, Stefanos: Spokesperson of the CRC 1667 “Advancing Technologies of Very Low Altitude Satellites” (ATLAS). Collaborates with task area Betty, focusing on verification, validation, and benchmarking.

Fimmers, Christian: Represents the “Cluster of Excellence” (EXC) Internet of Production. Contributes numerous use cases and community requirements to task area Fiona.

Garcke, Harald: Collaborates in task area Doris in standardising and automating RDM in the context of mathematical modelling and numerical simulation.

Gerlach, Roman: Represents the federal state initiative Competence Network Research Data Management (TKFDM). The TKFDM contributes to task area TES and supports NFDI4ING in promoting its services to local communities and universities in Thuringia.

Hartmaier, Alexander: Supports the generation of open-software and data repositories for microstructure and mechanical properties of materials in task areas TES and Betty. Also helps coordinate activities on structured data storage and generation of FAIR digital objects between NFDI4ING and NFDI-MatWerk.

Hezel, Dominik: Supports task area Caden as use case and pilot user for further development of the Karlsruhe Data Infrastructure (KaDI), including the Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN) KaDI4Mat.

Johannsen, Jochen: Represents the RWTH Aachen University Library. Supports the curation and maintenance of the NFDI4ING training platform and the development and dissemination of training material as open educational resources (OER).

Jung, Anne: Collaborates in task area Doris with use cases and training data for machine learning optimization and supports the development of workflows and methods for the analysis of that data.

Kirchner, Frank: Contributes to task area Fiona, namely by providing ideas on the further development of the Field Database Platform (FDP), serving as a pilot user of the FDP, and providing feedback for possible improvements. Adds expertise on the recording and storage of robotic field data for discussions within NFDI4ING.

Kleinert, Sven: Represents the EXC “Photonics, Optics and Engineering - Innovation Across Disciplines (PhoenixD). Contributes to task areas SKG, Alex, Doris, and Fiona by providing expertise and use cases for RDM in research on novel optical systems, including their production and application.

König, Markus: Collaborates in task areas SKG, FIS, and CPT. In particular, supports the development of concepts for quality testing of image-based training data for AI processes,

the development of ontologies for the description and use of digital twins of buildings, and the management and provision of heterogeneous data in the construction industry.

Köstler, Harald: Supports task area Betty in improving the sustainability of high-performance computing (HPC) research software by developing data-aware and efficient workflows, and provides user feedback and collaboration on tools like KaDI4Mat

Kübel, Christian: Contributes to task areas SKG, Alex, and Doris, particularly by supporting definition of descriptions, workflows, and data representation possibilities for complex multimodal and highly varying experiments.

Langer, Sabine C.: Represents the CRC/TRR 364 SynTrac. Supports cross-institutional cooperation in the field of sustainable research software development and research data management with a focus on applications in the field of aeronautical research, primarily in collaboration with task area Betty.

Lanza, Gisela: Collaborates with task areas SKG and FIS by linking NFDI4ING to the remanufacturing and Circular Economy community, as well the general production engineering landscape in Germany.

Maric, Tomislav: Integral part of task area Betty, particularly in the measures B-1 and B-2, which focus on verification, validation, and benchmarking. Also contributes to task area Doris by providing findings on Distributed Singular Value Decomposition (DSVD) and Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) to the approximate compression of primary data sets in the field of large Computational Fluid Dynamics.

Marx, Steffen: Provides measurement data from the field of concrete structures to task areas SKG and Doris.

Rehwald, Stephanie: Represents CRC/TRR 196 “Mobile Material Characterization and Localization by electromagnetic sensing” (MARIE) and the University of Duisburg-Essen university library. Will contribute to the development of metadata schemes and an ontology for material characterization in the Terahertz regime in conjunction with corresponding measuring and simulation procedures.

Schaaf, Peter: Provides experimental measurement data and metadata for the validation of large-scale high-performance simulations to task area Doris.

Schlenz, Hartmut: Integral part of task area Caden since 2018 and active in all its measures.

Schmidt, Michael: Contributes to task area Fiona by providing expertise and experience on handling experimental data.

Weiskopf, Daniel, and Wortmann, Thomas: Represent EXC “Integrative Computational Design and Construction for Architecture” (IntCDC). Contribute to task area Betty, particularly to measures B-1 and B-2.

Xu, Bai-Xang: Acts as pilot user for the data- and workflow-management infrastructure and training and consulting products of NFD4ING. Provides feedback and user experience to the consortium and its communities.

Names and numbers of the DFG review boards (DFG-Fachkollegien) that reflect the subject orientation of the proposed consortium

DFG RB-Nr.	Review Board / Subject Area
4.11	Production Technology
4.12	Mechanics and Constructive Mechanical Engineering
4.21	Process Engineering, Technical Chemistry
4.22	Fluid Mechanics, Technical Thermodynamics and Thermal Energy Engineering
4.31	Materials Engineering
4.32	Materials Science
4.41	Systems Engineering
4.42	Electrical Engineering and Information Technology
4.43	Computer Science
4.51	Construction Engineering and Architecture

2 Scope and Objectives

2.1 Research domains or research methods addressed by the consortium, specific aim(s)

In its second funding period, NFDI4ING intends to close data cycles and disseminate its (i) standardised, (ii) scaled, and (iii) sustainable solutions and services to the German engineering research community.

The engineering sciences play a key role in developing a manifold of solutions for the technical, environmental, and economic challenges imposed by the demands of our modern society. Engineers analyse technical, environmental, economic, and social systems. Consequently, they have to deal with a large variety of research data and artefacts - from text documents to physical samples and their provenance, to the results of simulations, and many more. This is reflected in the DFG subject area structure, where the engineering sciences cover the review boards 4.11 (Production Technology), 4.12 (Mechanics and Constructive Mechanical Engineering), 4.21 (Process Engineering, Technical Chemistry), 4.22 (Fluid Mechanics, Technical Thermodynamics and Thermal Energy Engineering), 4.31 (Materials Engineering), 4.32 (Materials Science), 4.41 (Systems Engineering), 4.42 (Electrical Engineering and Information Technology), 4.43 (Computer Science), and 4.51 (Construction Engineering and Architecture).

Despite the diversity in research subjects, data, and artefacts, engineers share common needs and approaches on the methodological level. Prior to the first funding period, NFDI4ING developed typical engineering research profiles based on clustering the most commonly recurring

needs, methods, and workflows and classifying the corresponding challenges regarding RDM. We call these research profiles “archetypes” and have applied them with great success since 2019 [1].

Engineering often uses the knowledge gained through analysis to design technical systems according to social needs in an efficient and sustainable way. NFDI4ING has contributed to a rising awareness regarding RDM and data literacy in the engineering research community. Its conferences attract between 250 and 300 attendees each year, its community meetings around 40 attendees each, and RDM and data literacy are now integral part of the engineering curricula at the applicant institution and, increasingly so, at the co-applicant institutions.

In addition to the provision of software tools, infrastructure, and concepts, NFDI4ING is engaged with its communities in national, federal-state level, and local RDM initiatives, through RDM stewards, integration of RDM methodologies into teaching curricula starting at the B.Sc. level onwards, and within CRC/TRR Projects. Ongoing Special Interest Groups (SIGs) and the NFDI4ING seed fund programme foster community collaboration.

NFDI4ING is very active within NFDI. The consortium is leading the section EduTrain and is involved in all other currently active sections. Its members are heavily contributing to Base4NFDI and active in 27 international research data community forums and initiatives, including the RDA, IDSA, CESAER, AARC2, DataCite e.V., EOSC Association, EUDAT CDI, OpenAire, and others.

While the first funding period of NFDI4ING has been dominated by the development of customised services for its communities, in the second period focus is on

1. communication and collaboration,
2. sustainability of services, solutions, and trainings,
3. scaling of services, solutions, and trainings,
4. standardisation of data formats and ontologies,
5. common infrastructures.

This is reflected in our new overarching solutions task areas (TAs) that are coordinating and synchronising efforts of all other TAs (c.f. ch. 3.1). The designated goal is to deeply integrate NFDI4ING’s portfolio within NFDI and beyond.

Given the changes in regulations and general technological and societal developments, we expect an increased importance of RDM and data literacy especially in engineering and engineering research. Developments such as the EU data act and particularly the requirement to report on environmental, social and governance impacts (ESG), the Supply Chain Act (“Lieferkettengesetz”), or the general trend towards Responsible Research and Innovation all require solid, open, and comprehensible data management. The associated research processes

as well as the life cycle of technical solutions themselves can only be sustainable if they are accompanied by a proper research data management that implements the FAIR data principles. NFDI4ING continues to support the professional development of the connected skills and providing the necessary infrastructure, particularly for engineers and engineering researchers.

2.2 Objectives and measuring success

For the second funding round, NFDI4ING has formulated the following ten objectives. They are the result of an intense process of reflection and evaluation within the consortium and represent a (re-)focusing on the sustainability, scalability, and standardisation of the infrastructures we provide for engineering researchers. They build on previous work and are deliberately aligned with the general objectives of the NFDI.

(1) We are deeply embedded in the engineering research community

Our newly introduced liaison officers and the strengthened task area Management & Outreach (c.f. ch. 3.1) centralise communication efforts and guarantee quick and direct communication between the consortium and our community. Based on this, we build up a long-term structure for inter-community communication, training and support. One example is the NFDI4ING helpdesk that is jointly run by the liaison officers and the TA Management & Outreach. It connects the user's requirements with our own expertise, and, when necessary, the expertise of other RDM support structures, in particular local RDM teams, federal state RDM initiatives, related services from other NFDI consortia, and the EOSC. For closer collaboration, our Special Interest Groups are open for everyone and foster inter-community communication and development.

We continue providing an annual conference and regular community meetings and step up our presence at engineering research institutions in Germany, e.g., through roadshows or workshops. We also continue to expand our collaborations with local and federal state RDM structures, including the "Landesinitiativen" (e.g., HeFDI, FDM.NRW, TKNFDM, etc.) and the data competency centres ("Datenkompetenzzentren"). We support DFG funded collaborative research groups (e.g., CRC, EXC) and foster a community network of embedded and central data stewards in those research programs. We collaborate in trainings with these groups and link it to NFDI section EduTrain and the Data Literacy Alliance (DALIA) [2].

To keep improving, we implement tracking and regular reporting of all usages of our offers (trainings, events, Open Educational Resources (OER), web services, and solutions). In line with this, we build and use a NFDI4ING FAIR reporting system based on FAIR digital objects (FDOs). This means that all data to be recorded are semantically linked. As a result, any performance indicators of the consortium can be easily aggregated at any time.

(2) All our offers serve all engineering scientists at German research institutions

We make our developments sustainably available and ensure German- or European-wide scalability. Our newly formed overarching solutions task areas (c.f. ch. 3.1) guarantee the build-up of integrated long-term services that are accessible to all scientists (e.g., via NFDI-IAM) and provide clear points-of-entry. We follow open procedures at all levels of service development. We regularly check for new or changed community needs or requirements through our archetype task areas and surveys.

(3) We standardise and automate the RDM processes wherever possible and support the scientists represented by the archetypes with an NFDI4ING RDM Copilot

We set up common infrastructures and put the concept of FDOs into practice by agreeing on a common information model (CIM) in the consortium. Our liaison officers and the concept of “shared tasks” - work packages with clear responsibilities yet allocated to more than one task area (c.f. ch. 5) - guarantee the success of this central effort. Based on the CIM we implement federated semantic knowledge graphs which connect to our services. We include existing federated storage infrastructures into our portfolio and connect our services to those whenever applicable, incl. setting up a federated dataset search and bundling our training efforts and materials. The NFDI4ING RDM Copilot provides a single point of entry for assisted RDM planning and continuous support for RDM tasks. These efforts standardise and scale our services and form a basis for a long-term integrated infrastructure that will merge into OneNFDI [3].

(4) We close data cycles

We further develop the deliverables of our first funding period into end-to-end solutions to allow engineers to achieve closed data cycles in their day-to-day practice. We keep a keen eye on the results of our efforts and monitor progress according to our concept of Integration Readiness Levels (c.f. ch. 4.1) and FAIR reporting system (see above). We also continue to present an annual NFDI4ING award for efforts on closing data cycles. The award highlights tools or services that achieve FAIR data preparation, supply, and usage in models (AI or other) in a convincing manner, considering economical, ethical and legal aspects.

(5) All research data managed by NFDI4ING’s concepts and services will be FAIR and AI-ready in 2030

Our FAIR digital objects make data sets and software machine-actionable and AI ready. Continuous further development and integration guided by our Integration Readiness Levels (IRLs) foster interoperability and reusability throughout data life cycles. We establish bridges to AI tools in our services on both ends of the data lifecycle, i.e. data supply and data usage. Our NFDI4ING Copilot will be fostered by AI.

(6) We empower engineering research institutions and universities to include RDM and NFDI4ING's solutions in their curricula as well as their examination and doctoral regulations

We offer patterns for curricula as well as their regulations for examinations and doctoral programs and promote examples from NFDI4ING's co-applicant institutions. We deliver best-practice guides and set standards for RDM on all scales from special data handling tasks to entire tool chains.

(7) The usage of our concepts and services increases the scientific reputation of our researchers and the academic credit of our students and doctoral candidates

We actively support the cultural change towards research assessment reform and FAIR scientific data management and stewardship. In collaboration with the NFDI section EduTrain we develop certificates for RDM expertise in engineering and further build on the concept of EduBricks. We develop and implement engineering related EduBricks for the needs of the NFDI4ING community (c.f. measure TES-2, p. 51). For dissemination, we run the journal ing.grid as a well-known publication platform for datasets, software and manuscripts on RDM practice.

(8) We deepen our collaboration with industry stakeholders and ISO/DIN

We continue to integrate industry partners in our archetype task areas and include data custody models and infrastructures into our portfolio. Via our advisory board we regularly receive and implement input and feedback from industry partners. Our connection to the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) will be further expanded. We continue to work on the community-driven development of standards by providing a platform and workflow comparable to the IETF's requests for comments. In this, we connect to national and international regulatory bodies like ISO/DIN and contribute to the NFDI section Industry Engagement.

(9) We contribute significantly to the vision of OneNFDI

We play a key role in several Base4NFDI services (i.e., IAM4NFDI, PID4NFDI, Jupyter4NFDI, DMP4NFDI, KGI4NFDI, TS4NFDI, and nfdi.software). We are active in all sections and bodies of the NFDI e.V. and closely collaborate with the other NFDI consortia on trans-consortial use cases. A focus lies on collaborating with consortia active in at least one of the DFG review boards 4.11 through 4.51 and thus closely related to engineering sciences. These include NFDI4Cat, DAPHNE4NFDI, NFDI-MatWerk, NFDI4DataScience, NFDI4BioImage, NFDI4Energy, NFDIxCS, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Objects. Beyond DFG classifications, we also include NFDI4Chem and MaRDI in the list of consortia closely connected to engineering. Thematically, cultural and social aspects (e.g. on data related to the built environment with NFDI4Objects and NFDI4Culture) and the development of new use cases that result from combining research data from different disciplines are foci. To further support this, we foster the cross-linking of knowledge graphs and the integration of information models.

(10) We feel responsible for the long-term sustainability of RDM in engineering

We actively develop and plan to implement an operational model that supports our activities and services beyond the projected end of funding in 2030. This process is framed by and in accordance with the activities of other actors, i.e. the German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures (Rat für Informationsinfrastrukturen, RfII), the NFDI e.V., and the Joint Science Conference (Gemeinsame Wissenschaftskonferenz, GWK).

3 Consortium

The following co-spokespersons of NFDI4ING participate in multiple NFDI consortia:

Member, institution	_cs=co-spoke, _pp=participating person
Sören Auer, TIB	NFDI4ING_cs, NFDI4Energy_cs, NFDI4DS_cs, FAIRmat_pp
Jan Linxweiler, TUBS	NFDI4ING_cs, NFDIxCS_pp
Matthias S. Müller, RWTH	NFDI4ING_cs, NFDI-MatWerk_cs, NFDIxCS_cs, NFDI4Chem_pp
Thomas Stäcker, TUDa	NFDI4ING_cs, Text+_pp, NFDI4Culture_pp
Achim Streit, KIT	NFDI4ING_cs, NFDI-MatWerk_cs

3.1 Composition of the consortium and its embedding in the community of interest

Since its inception, NFDI4ING has been set up to support different points of access and varying levels of participation. We aim to adequately represent and include the requirements of individual users, methodological communities, institutional partners, and infrastructure providers in the decision-making processes and the future development of the consortium. Going forward, we now proceed to describing adjustments to the structure of our working programme initially proposed in 2019. These adjustments are grounded in learnings of the first funding period and aim at improving decision-making processes and agility of the consortium.

The consortium is growing. A noticeable change with respect to the proposal in 2019 is the increased number of co-spokespersons. In most cases, the co-spokespersons of the first funding period remain on board and nine colleagues, most of which are at an early career stage, will be joining, leading to 24 co-spokespersons for the second funding period. An overview is given in the table below.

Table 3.1-1: Overview of changes in NFDI4ING co-spokespersons

institution	(co-)spokesperson	staying	joining	leaving
RWTH	Jakob Beetz	/	yes	/
RWTH	Matthias Müller	yes	/	/
RWTH	Marius Politze	/	yes	/
RWTH	Robert Schmitt	yes	/	/

RWTH	Annett Schwarz	yes	/	/
BAM	Jörg Unger	/	yes	/
TUBS	Jan Linxweiler	/	yes	/
TUBS	Robert Strötgen	/	/	yes
TUC	Stefan Wittek	/	yes	/
TUDa	Andreas Dreizler	/	yes	/
TUDa	Gerald Jagusch	yes	/	/
TUDa	Peter Pelz	yes	/	/
TUDa	Thomas Stäcker	yes	/	/
TUD	Regine Gerike	/	/	yes
TIB	Sören Auer	yes	/	/
TIB	Irina Sens	yes	/	/
LUH	Roland Lachmayer	yes	/	/
FZJ	Torsten Bronger	yes	/	/
FZJ	Patrick Kuckertz	/	yes	/
FZJ	Detlef Stolten	/	/	yes
KIT	Britta Nestler	yes	/	/
KIT	Michael Selzer	/	yes	/
KIT	Achim Streit	yes	/	/
DLR	Christian Langenbach	yes	/	/
TUM	Christian Stemmer	yes	/	/
US	Bernd Flemisch	yes	/	/
US	Dorothea Iglezakis	/	yes	/

We value the expertise among the younger colleagues, most of which have already been involved with the consortium for years. In line with this, our spokesperson from the first funding period from RWTH Aachen University will swap seats with its younger deputy from TU Darmstadt. This leads to TU Darmstadt being the applicant institution for the second funding period. Another institutional change with respect to the role of co-applicant institution will affect Clausthal University of

Technology (TUC is joining), Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (BAM is joining), and Dresden University of Technology (TUD is leaving). TUD will remain as a participant institution and will, in the future, be involved with archetype Ellen.

While the consortium is growing, we adequately address the consolidation and stabilisation focus of the second funding period by reorganising at the task area level. Our reorganisation is the result of an internal evaluation performed at the beginning of 2024. Task areas for the second funding period are shown in the figure below.

Figure 1: Overview of NFDI4ING task areas in a second funding period. Abbreviations: Training, Education, and Standardisation (TES); Semantic Metadata and Knowledge Graphs (KGS), Federated Interactive Data Space (FIS), Copilot - Assistance Systems and AI (CPT)

The most significant adjustment will happen in the task area formerly known as Base Services. This task area, which contained seven measures, will, in the future, be consolidated into four full-fledged task areas and also incorporate our Diamond Open Access Journal ing.grid. The consolidation will be undertaken with the main goal of a reduction of complexity and a renewed focus on providing overarching solutions in cooperation with Base4NFDI. In analogy for the collective name given to the archetype task areas, we call the new task areas the *overarching solutions* task areas. They break down as follows:

- Training, Education, and Standardisation (TES)
- Semantic Metadata and Knowledge Graphs (SKG)
- Federated Interactive Data Space (FIS)
- Copilot - Assistance Systems and Artificial Intelligence (CPT)
- Journal ing.grid (J)

Another result of the internal evaluation performed at the beginning of 2024 is that the methodological focus of our archetype task areas is being revisited. We have discovered, and subsequently addressed, redundancies in former TAs Caden, Ellen, Frank, and Golo. This will

result in the dissolution of TA Golo, the reorientation of TA Frank – in the future being called TA Fiona – and an increased methodological focus of TAs Alex, Betty, Caden, Doris, and Ellen. Starting with 2024, our archetypes are becoming the beacons of our community meetings which are effectively being rebranded as *archetopical* meetings. At the time of writing, TA Betty (February 27th 2024), TA Ellen (June 6th 2024), and TA Frank (July 25th 2024) have partnered with our task area Community Clusters to hold meetings with a methodological focus. The meetings pave the way for a more uniform community engagement executed by the archetype task areas to allow engineer-to-engineer communication and direct feedback for further development. They broaden our penetration of the respective (sub-)communities and first results are promising. Archetopical meetings will be pursued for the remaining time of the first funding period and then rolled out further in the second funding period (c.f. task M&O-1-1, p. 105).

While we engage with our various communities via our archetopical meetings, we continue to engage with the larger engineering community once per year via the annual NFDI4ING conference. At the conferences, we will continue presenting the NFD4Ing award for the best RDM solution that has not been developed in the context of our consortium. The conference will be hosted by the co-applicant institutions in turn.

Further learnings of the first funding period result in an adjustment to organising and managing our community engagement and overall outreach. We acknowledge that community engagement and outreach only work in close cooperation of all task areas. This learning will become manifest in the dissolution of the task area formerly known as Community Clusters, which we will restructure to an embedded set of liaison officers as outlined below. We also allocate the strategic communication and outreach oversight to the task area formerly known as Management – now being called Management & Outreach. To adapt our structure to better deal with community engagement and outreach, we take four measures:

First, we will establish liaison officers (LOs) in each task area. The LOs will act as contact persons for both internal and external audiences and they will play a key role in all outreach activities of the consortium. Additionally, they will serve as project managers for the day-to-day business of the task areas below the level of the co-spokespersons. Since these tasks are of immense importance and quite challenging, we allocate a full postdoc position to each task area for these purposes. The profile of tasks required of the LOs demand senior personnel that can speak in an informed and knowledgeable manner about the work of their task area and the field of research their task area operates in. LOs are required to have existing professional networks that can be used to reach our target audiences. All LOs meet weekly to share information across task area boundaries and discuss outreach activities.

Second, we already plan for close collaboration between the overarching solutions task areas and all other task areas in so-called “shared tasks” – tasks that belong to more than one task area – and that are essential for the standardisation and further consolidation of the NFDI4ING product portfolio (c.f. ch. 5). The strategic oversight of these shared tasks will be given to the LOs involved in the respective task areas.

Third, we build up the task area Management & Outreach as the single point of contact for all structured external communication. This includes both incoming communication (e.g., requests for support or consulting, first level support) as well as the centralisation of our outgoing public relations and science communication activities. Previously, these tasks were distributed across multiple institutions, locations, and research areas in our former task area Community Clusters. While initial results have been promising, with the continuing growth and reach of the consortium this decentralised approach has proven to be unsustainable.

Fourth, we provide a central helpdesk. Our helpdesk will be aligned with the helpdesk operations of other consortia to leverage synergies. All task areas are committed to supporting our helpdesk and resolve specific incoming requests. In addition to the helpdesk, an online forum has been set up during the first funding period to empower researchers in the engineering sciences with a collaborative space to ask and answer questions about their research data management [38*]. This forum will continue to offer an exchange platform for researchers and is moderated and supported by NFDI4ING.

Finally, we intend to ensure continuous and consistent interaction with our communities in the future with a structure that has been introduced after the project started and that has been continually active: our special interest groups (SIGs). The SIG format is intentionally open in design, and the time-limited nature (with possibility for extension) ensures that SIG meetings are held for benefit. SIGs have proven to be a good and inclusive way to pool information, discuss challenges and provide solutions beyond the confines of the consortium. A total of four SIGs have been established during the first funding round: SIG metadata & ontologies, SIG RDM training & education, SIG quality assurance & metrics for FAIR data, and SIG workflow tools. A new SIG centred on the built environment is currently underway in cooperation with NFDI4Objects and NFDI4Culture.

3.2 The consortium within the NFDI and the national academic research system

Over the course of the first funding period, NFDI4ING has become established in the national ecosystem of RDM initiatives. Our members actively participate in various NFDI entities beyond the engagement in the NFDI Consortia Assembly and the Jour Fixe of the consortia speakers. Most prominently, R. Schmitt was an elected member in the first term of office of the NFDI Scientific Senate, and A. Streit is a member of the Base4NFDI Technical Expert Committee. Many

more NFDI4ING members are active in all sections of NFDI, act as principal investigators in almost all Base4NFDI projects, and engage in direct cross-consortia collaborations. These three pillars for rooting NFDI4ING within NFDI are explained and shown by selected examples in the following paragraphs. They are in line with the expectations of the NFDI expert committee as outlined in [4] - in particular with tasks c) and h). In chapter 5 our planned contributions towards the goal of one single national research data infrastructure are substantiated by tasks tagged with *-OneNFDI*.

In NFDI, the sections are the main place where cross-cutting issues are addressed across the boundaries of the consortia. We are committed to the goals of the sections, which are to create cross-consortia solutions to common challenges that would not be possible through the work of individual consortia. Through the joint work in the sections, NFDI is developing into a sustainable and efficient infrastructure in the sense of OneNFDI [3]. In particular, P. Pelz coordinates the section EduTrain [5] which aims to collect all training materials developed on RDM and distribute them into the community. B. Flemisch jointly operates the Working Group Research Software Engineering [6] of the section Common Infrastructures [7], which is devoted to identifying infrastructure components for common use and to work out proposals on how these can be technically structured and implemented. In the same section, M. Politze jointly leads the Working Group Overall Architecture. R. Schmitt and eight other NFDI4ING members were part of the preparation team for installing the section Industry Engagement [8], which is focused on the overarching design of collaborations between industry and the NFDI consortia, basic services and other sections. In the future, we will continue and intensify our involvement in all sections to contribute to the development of joint solutions for common challenges and to achieve tangible cross-consortia results.

Evolving from the efforts in the NFDI sections and working groups, NFDI4ING members contribute substantially to NFDI-wide basic services in the framework of Base4NFDI [9]. We consider universal access to common services as critical for the underpinning of efficient data sharing activities in engineering sciences and as a complementary activity to the development of our own discipline-relevant tools and services. In this sense, six of the seven currently funded basic services have at least one NFDI4ING-associated principal investigator: IAM4NFDI - Identity and Access Management (M. Politze, W. Pempe) [10], PID4NFDI - Persistent Identifier Services (I.Sens) [11], TS4NFDI - Terminology Services (F. Engel) [12], Jupyter4NFDI - Central JupyterHub (B. Flemisch) [13], DMP4NFDI - Data Management Plans (T. Stäcker) [14], and nfdi.software - Software Marketplace (S. Wittek) [15]. Since these principal investigators are also involved in corresponding measures within NFDI4ING, a continued exchange of information between Base4NFDI and our consortium is already guaranteed and will be further formalised by working closely with the Base4NFDI service stewards and keeping the channels of

communication updated. We will reserve efforts to attend community workshops, calls and training activities for each basic service. As detailed in the work programme in chapter 5, we dedicate resources to actively integrate basic services in our portfolio.

While collaboration with other NFDI consortia is naturally given in form of the joint work as described above, NFDI4ING also successfully interacts with selected consortia by more direct means. In fact, NFDI4ING is the second most active among all consortia when it comes to direct collaborations based on data published July 25th, 2024 [16*]. According to the published data sheet, NFDI4ING has engaged in the organisation of 22 cross-consortial events, the running of ten cross-consortial interest groups, the joint development of five cross-consortial services, and the forging of one cross-consortial alliance. Respective examples are RWTH4NFDI [17], the ELN consortium [18], Kadi4Mat [19*], and NFDI4ING's memorandum of understanding (MoU) with NFDI4Chem regarding RDMO. While we will extend direct collaborations with other consortia in the second funding period, we appreciate that such trans-consortial use cases in a dynamic research environment cannot always be anticipated ahead of time. We therefore commit to collaboratively issuing open calls for use cases with other consortia, incorporating a joint selection process. To support this, we will make use of our flex funds and coordinate with other participating consortia to share costs.

Beyond NFDI, NFDI4ING interacts closely with many other national stakeholders in the field of RDM infrastructures, including the DFN association, RDM networks of federal states and NHR centres. In this respect, an agreement between the NFDI consortia for natural and engineering sciences and the specialised information services (Fachinformationsdienste, FID) has been established, aiming to increase interoperability and improve the findability and visibility of data. The DALIA platform [2] assembles metadata of OERs developed in the NFDI consortia and federal initiatives. Using the underlying semantic knowledge graph (SKG) of DALIA, intelligent search in these OERs is possible. The OERs comprise texts, slides, videos, and tests for different learning levels ranging from discipline-specific to generic material. The SKG is jointly developed in the section EduTrain, i.e. the platform is based on the work of the section EduTrain and forms the basis for the further work in the section. It is offered to all researchers. Three of NFDI4ING's co-applicant institutions are leading partners in DALIA (TUDa, RWTH, TIB). NFDI4ING contributes substantially to the DALIA knowledge base for "FAIR data usage and supply".

3.3 International networking

On a global scale, NFDI4ING currently participates in a total of 27 international communities including RDA, IDSA, CESAER, AARC2, DataCite e.V., EOSC Association, EUDAT CDI, SSHOC, and OpenAire.

Addressed topics include e.g., the consolidation of FAIR data networks and trainings, which is mainly covered within working groups of the RDA, CESAER and the EOSC association. In the second funding period, the consortium will continue these efforts along with increasing its presence within the RDA and the Research Data Management in Engineering Interest Group (IG RDM4Eng), which was initiated by NFDI4ING. Productive services relevant to the international engineering community will be regularly presented at RDA-hosted events and discussed with the communities there, such as, e.g., FAIRsharing.org, which provides feedback that is incorporated into further service development. There will be a focus on the provision of FDOs in the second funding period [20]. The FDO implementation aims to be compatible to both RDA and Gaia-X recommendations, which form the basis for the Catena-X automotive network [21] and will enable a better data exchange with partners from industry. NFDI4ING establishes long-term collaborations with industry stakeholders by integrating relevant stakeholders in suitable archetype TAs, along with data custody models. One example is the archetype Alex, which integrates a cooperation with Merck KGaA in their task A-3-2 (c.f. p. 74). Evolving from the efforts in the NFDI sections and respective working groups, NFDI4ING will continue to contribute substantially to the DALIA Knowledge Base for “FAIR data usage and supply” [22] and to basic service proposals in the framework of Base4NFDI.

NFDI at large (including NFDI4ING) is recognized by the EOSC Association as a blueprint for other member states. Several NFDI4ING co-applicants are participating within the EOSC Association, the EOSC Working Groups [23], and related forums such as EUDAT CDI and the AARC blueprint architecture for federated Identity and Access Management. The latter forms the basis for the NFDI AAI to be developed within the context of Base4NFDI. The importance of PIDs is covered e.g. by cooperation with DataCite e.V. There, NFDI4ING has developed an interactive NFDI instrument dashboard to visualise connections in the PID graph, representing relationships between instruments and associated digital resources [24*].

From the start, NFDI4ING features an advisory board with international members, including representatives from academia, industry, and science policy agencies. NFDI4ING also launched *ing.grid*, an international open access journal that fosters FAIR RDM practices in the engineering sciences. One area of NFDI4ING’s international visibility have been the NFDI4ING conferences (particularly in 2022), which attracted a significant international audience and speakers. Terminologies in engineering were brought forward in 2023 at the CIRP General Assembly in Dublin, where NFDI4ING’s spokesperson R. Schmitt served as chairman of the CIRP’s Terminology Committee. Together with partners from the Polytechnic University of Milan and the University of Nantes, vocabulary modelling according to W3C Standards has been introduced. The ongoing objective aims to use CIRP dictionaries in English, French, Italian and German as a

base for the Terminology Service (TS) (c.f. TA SKG, ch. 5.2), for the design of ontologies in production engineering [25].

In the Czech Republic, an initiative comparable to the NFDI was launched in 2024 and will be actively supported by a NFDI4ING working group centred on TA Caden and the Kadi4Mat team. This features a collaboration between the Czech initiatives "National Repository Platform" [26] with the additional support of Skills4EOSC [27] to share knowledge in the field of RDM and to build a community around the research data infrastructure Kadi4Mat [19*]. In the USA, NFDI4ING actively participates in the Phase Field Schema working group of Materials Research Data Alliance (MaRDA) [28], where we share our competences to build an ontology in the domain of material science.

3.4 Organisational structure and viability

To meet its goals, the NFDI4ING consortium has implemented a governance structure alongside its functional setup. The role of the different organisational entities is detailed in NFDI4ING's by-laws ("Ordnung"). To give a brief overview, the main organisational entities are:

- The **members' meeting**: Top decision-making body previously called steering committee. The members' meeting is responsible for setting project objectives and work programmes and supervises the scientific progress within task areas. The member role is assigned with the aim of achieving a broad representation of our communities. To illustrate, the member role is automatically assigned to all co-spokespersons, to representatives of all TU9 members, to representatives of non-university research institution members, and to representatives of the NFDI initiative OD-Rex, which was integrated in 2019 after not being funded. In sum, the member's meeting consists of about 45 members. To further include the representatives of the member institutions of the consortium according to the articles of the NFDI association, they are permanently invited guests of the members' meeting.
- The **executive committee**: Consists of a sub-group of twelve persons of the members' meeting that convenes frequently and includes both the speaker and its deputy. The executive committee supervises contractual affairs and the disbursement of funds. It responds to short-term decision-making needs of the consortium and reports to the member's meeting. The members' meeting elects the executive committee at the suggestion of the speakers.
- The **speakers' team**: Both the speaker and the deputy speaker convene frequently with the administrative office in order to set administrative goals and review agendas.
- The **advisory board**: Represents national and international research, politics, and industry, offering an external perspective and advice.

Unlike the initially proposed structure, the implemented governance framework excludes a general meeting to align more closely with the organisational structure of the NFDI e.V.. However, there have been regular all-hands meetings organised by the TA Management to gather input from all persons active in the consortium. This format will continue in the second funding period. Apart from these adjustments, the governance framework has remained consistent since the project's inception in 2020.

The funds requested in the original proposal were significantly reduced after the project received approval. NFDI4ING's approach to manage these cuts without drastically altering the project's scope was to cut salary levels and direct project costs rather than decreasing staff numbers. Positions initially intended for postdoctoral researchers were converted to PhD student positions, with promising results, at first. With the continuing growth and reach of the consortium, however, it has become apparent that senior personnel at the postdoc level are desirable for certain tasks. We now adjust for this by planning to embed liaison officers at the postdoctoral level in all task areas (c.f. chapter 3.1).

Overall, the deviations in fund spending were primarily due to budget cuts implemented after the project was approved, along with some minor organisational changes already reported in our interim report. Most noticeably, the seed fund programme of the first funding period has been successfully implemented with growing numbers of applicants each year. Given the success of the programme, we plan to continue it throughout the second round of funding and broaden its scope, explicitly aiming at collaborations with other consortia (c.f. chapter 3.2).

Given that many established infrastructure providers are (co-)applicants of NFDI4ING, the services and products developed can be considered reliable and sustainable within the framework conditions of NFDI during the first funding period. The following chapter goes into more detail and outlines our plans as to how we will overcome the uncertainties connected to running the services in the long-term.

3.5 Operating model

During the first funding period, NFDI4ING has been providing mainly “soft³” services and developments to the entire engineering community free of charge, as they are financed through the provision of funds within NFDI4ING. Everybody within the engineering community (and beyond) is welcome to participate, contribute, and/or benefit from these activities, which feature specific knowledge on data and software handling. Currently, providers do not charge user fees and most of them do not plan to do so in the future. Software is usually made available permanently via long-term platforms funded by institutions (e.g., GitLab from RWTH Aachen).

³ e.g., curation, software, trainings & training materials, concepts, workflows, etc.

However, we notice an increase in demand for the use of hardware resources, such as storage above the size usually covered by institutional repositories or GPU-usage for AI-based services. Financing of such offers must be discussed with the relevant cooperation partners on a national level for all computing centre users. For now, all services that require the use of hardware are financed by special funding programs of the federal states or individual participating institutions, which are usually limited in time.

The overarching strategy for perpetuating services is the creation of needs and awareness on the user side, which are recognised and served by institutional service operators (e.g., computing centres, providers of repositories and libraries). A wide-spread usage would lead to perpetual provision, as these services would be considered necessary and standard for good scientific practice and considered a “normal”, i.e., permanent, service detached from the consortia funding through NFDI.

In NFDI4ING, some services are already established through funding from various sources, enabling service operations beyond the project phase. To give a few examples, the University and State Library Darmstadt provides a permanent machine readable storage and repository for literature for text and data mining, enabling synergies with the DFG funded project Digital Media Workflow [29]. The long-term operation of Coscine at the IT Center of RWTH is guaranteed by permanent funding from the federal government of North Rhine-Westphalia via the DH.NRW project Coscine.nrw. [30*]. The TIB provides SciKGTex as part of the ORKG, an open access service provided on a long-term basis. The KIT Datamanager portfolio [31] will be further developed and operated at least until 2030 (Data Collections Explorer) or 2035 (MetaStore, base-repo, Typed PID Maker). By commitment of TA Caden’s partners, a basal permanent maintenance of SciMesh [32*] and its associated services is ensured.

Most partners and participants have invested in large-scale storage facilities including long-term storage capabilities foreseeing upcoming demands in data-driven research, as they become necessary for the projects currently undertaken. Storage space providers (i.e. computing centres) are responding to an increasing demand for data storage driven by project needs. The publication of (RDM) metadata can be implemented via the existing storage facilities and corresponding repositories, whereas additional infrastructure will be required for the widespread publication of comprehensive raw data and processed data itself. NFDI4ING caters to all potential users within the engineering communities for RDM related services and solutions where the data storage facilities are supplied through their home institution.

There are already a few fee-based services in NFDI4ING, e.g., the full text conversion service of the University and State Library Darmstadt [33], which has so far been offered to members of the TU Darmstadt and interested researchers via the Centre for Digital Editions (CEiD) [34] on a

smaller scale. It is planned to be extended to engineering researchers in the second funding period. The service is financially sustainable, based on user fees per order and per page processed. Users will be charged fees for the full text conversion service during the second funding period and after the end of the project. However, we consider limited usage models across platforms and fee-based financing models to have the potential to compromise the overall success of NFDI.

NFDI4ING will overcome the uncertainties in running the services long-term by developing, implementing and evaluating own operation and business models within the second funding period. This includes evaluating the legal implications and providing support with financial administration, as necessary. The corresponding tasks will be centrally addressed by the administrative office in measure M&O-7 within task area Management & Outreach. A special staff member will be devoted to these tasks only, working in close collaboration with NFDI4ING's other task areas and the co-applicant institutions as the actual providers of services.

NFDI4ING strives for sustainable and non-bureaucratic solutions which do not burden the researchers themselves. Rather, their respective home institutions, the members of the NFDI4ING consortium or more generally the members of the NFDI association, are targeted actors for e.g., booking additional resources and paying for it at a flat rate (subscription model).

Wherever possible, we will rely on or be inspired by existing legal structures, both national and international. For example, the DFN association, the EOSC, or the RDM networks of the German federal states (Landesinitiativen) can be an inspiration for sustainable operation models. We also stay up to date with recommendations regarding the sustainable development of federated data infrastructures for scientific use, e.g., by the German Council for Scientific Information Infrastructures (RfII). Building on the experiences from the first funding round, we will establish our operational models, notably the financial aspects, alongside the NFDI association and in close collaboration with the NFDI directorate and the other consortia. We trust that the NFDI association will adopt a central role as point of contact and matchmaker between service-demanding research institutions and those offering services via the NFDI consortia (including Base4NFDI).

4 Research Data Management Strategy

4.1 Scientific relevance and quality of the measures

The functional structure of NFDI4ING with a focus on research methodology, on scalability and high integration of services, and on community outreach has been successfully implemented in the first funding period. After an internal evaluation performed at the beginning of 2024, the structure will be adjusted to address the consolidation and stabilisation focus of the second funding period (c.f. chapter 3.1). We will re-align our three pillars regarding research methodology

(archetype task areas), service integration (former task area base services), and community outreach (former task area community clusters) as outlined in the figure below.

Figure 2: Mapping of old task area structure to reworked and consolidated structure for the second funding period.

We refer to chapter 3.1 for a more detailed introduction to the adjusted structure on the right-hand side and to our original proposal [35] for a more detailed introduction to the left-hand side of the figure.

The scientific relevance of the implemented measures and their quality assurance have been positively evaluated in NFDI4ING's interim report [245]. To stay scientifically relevant, NFDI4ING will continue to integrate its products according to our Integration Readiness Levels (IRLs) that have originally been developed in our proposal for the first funding round. We use "products" as collective term for the outputs of the consortium, including software tools for local installation, (web-)services and RDM infrastructures, and concepts as a service (CaaS) like guidelines and best practices. IRLs have been continuously applied to all products of NFDI4ING. For each product, criteria are defined for five levels of maturity, ranging from level 0 where the product is only available internally, up to level 4 where the product is broadly available with interfaces for connectivity, provides training materials, and features the NFDI4ING branding. In a second step, more detailed criteria have been defined per product category. Figure 3 details the integration readiness levels and chapter 4.4 gives a representative overview of existing products and their IRLs.

Integration Readiness Level (IRL)

Figure 3: Introducing the Integration Readiness Level (IRL) for products developed by the NFDI4ING consortium. The IRL indicates the level of maturity and usability of the respective product.

One of the most relevant aspects of NFDI4ING's work and a measure for its success is the implementation of the FAIR principles into data life cycles in engineering research. This can be exemplified for each individual FAIR principle:

Findability: The archetype TAs implement rich metadata description and persistent identifiers to all their distinct methods of data collection and processing. Betty's (Re)Search Engine and Data Collections Explorer index and aggregate metadata for search. HOMER, Data Ingest Service and metadata crawler automatically extract metadata from data formats and simulation settings. These approaches will be further developed in the archetypes and integrated in TA SKG. More generally speaking, Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) and the future AI-copilot along with several discipline-specific DMP templates and best practices will guide researchers towards FAIR results.

Accessibility: Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) and Cosine combined with storage solutions for ELNs, large HPC data, and measurement data in time series or graph-based databases make data and metadata accessible. Collaboration between computing centres (LRZ, HLRS, JSC) answers topics concerning data quality metrics, security aspects, and licensing. In the future, TA FIS integrates these efforts and fosters further integration with BASE4NFDI towards OneNFDI.

Interoperability: The Terminology service provides a basis for domain-specific interoperable solutions, newly developed metadata standards like metadata4ing (m4i), DataDesc and SciMesh integrate recurring engineering needs to comprehensive descriptions. They support data exchange between ELNs and integrate with Kadi4Mat or JuliaBase. Machine actionable data sheets allow for automatic processing of data regarding calibration and uncertainty. The CIM will

further integrate these approaches to a strong interoperable basis for future development of FAIR services in TA FIS and SKG and for FDOs in the archetype TA in the second funding period.

Reusability: Standardising metadata for domain specific methods and according to community needs is a core aim in all archetype TA including the collection of rich information on data processing chains and provenance. PlotSerializer and DataDesc are examples for formats especially developed to reuse data and software. The future focus on FDOs and efforts to describe whole data life cycles in knowledge graphs aim to make engineering data more transparent and reusable.

Promoting open licences and FAIR processes in trainings and curricula professionalises data processing in our target communities. NFDI4ING will continue to support the development of RDM competencies as early in the academic career as possible, i.e., for students in Bachelor and Master programmes. One example is the gradual implementation of the concept of FAIR data boxes into teaching in undergraduate engineering courses at TU Darmstadt starting in the winter semester 2022 ([36*],[37]). Another example is a recurring lecture on RDM in the course “Wissenschaftstheorie und Forschungsmethodik” at RWTH Aachen University, where students design and conduct their scientific methodology to answer a given practical research question, including proper research data management.

Overall, leveraging the functional structure of NFDI4ING described above, we will continue to address the needs of the engineering community regarding RDM. Our embedded liaison officers together with the restructured task area Management & Outreach will continue a two-way communication with the engineering community and further build on channels and formats established during the first funding period. As detailed in chapters 3.2 and 3.3, strong ties to national and international networks ensure we focus on relevant scientific topics.

A dedicated position for communication has been created in task area Management & Outreach. This role is complemented by specific outreach tasks assigned to each task area, ensuring comprehensive engagement with the broader community. These tasks are tagged with *-outreach* in chapters 5.1 to 5.12 respectively. In the second funding period, there is a stronger emphasis on providing training with the dedicated task area TES. Additionally, training components have been integrated into each archetype task area, ensuring that all research areas benefit from targeted educational programs and engage in data literacy education. These activities include proposals as to how RDM can be integrated into curricula and a closer alignment with NFDI’s EduTrain section and the DALIA project. Related tasks are tagged with *-training* in chapters 5.1 to 5.12.

Another dedicated position for the development, implementation, and evaluation of service operation and business models has been created in task area Management & Outreach (c.f.

measure M&O-7, p. 105). This will foster the integration and standardisation of our services and establish the business models needed for permanent operation. On the technical side of things, a common information model and infrastructure for FDOs will be utilised by all services. FDOs raise the efficiency of these services and improve the coherent visibility to their users. The FDOs aim at the integration of services and infrastructures into NFDI and ESOC and provide new search- and assistance-centred services, like helpdesk, AI-copilot(s), and knowledge graph(s).

Our newly proposed FAIR reporting system (c.f. chapter 2.2 and measure M&O-5, p. 106) will incorporate the DFG key performance indicators (KPI) schema and will be aligned with the reporting systems of other consortia. It is aimed at transparently measuring the success of the consolidation and stabilisation focus of the second funding period. Furthermore, a helpdesk is being established to address queries from the community (c.f. chapter 3.1 and measure M&O-1, p. 106). In line with this, we have created an online forum similar to the established Stackoverflow platform to support the empowerment of the community [38*]. This forum will continue to serve as an exchange platform for researchers, supported and moderated by NFDI4ING.

4.2 Metadata standards

NFDI4ING uses, further develops and shapes engineering metadata standards which enable engineers to describe research data and software products in a standardised and reproducible way. This includes the consideration of standards for semantic objects from several nationally and internationally recognized projects such as FAIRsFAIR project deliverables, FOOPs evaluator, O'FAIRE as well as the kept compliance to international standards and guidelines such as EngMeta [39], DCAT [40], DataCite Metadata Standard 4.5 [41], RO-Crate Metadata File Descriptor [42], Resource Description Framework (RDF) [43], and OWL [44]. In the first funding period, four central services and two standardisation works exemplify these efforts:

- The Metadata Hub Service [45*] to standardise access to different metadata repositories to allow uniform use of multiple metadata repositories through a single API.
- The Terminology Service [46*] which provides a central entry point for the development and integration of standardised terminologies.
- The SciMesh method [47*], which uses an RDF data model to describe sample-based workflows in engineering as a knowledge graph.
- The m4i Ontology [48*] which integrates and aligns numerous standards used in engineering (e.g. DCAT, EMMO and EngMeta) and is based on established solutions such as the OBO Foundry.
- The Profile Service [49*] that enables the reuse and exchange of metadata profiles by selecting appropriate elements from controlled terminologies, and thus standardises the markup of research data.

- The DataDesc [50*] toolkit for software supports researchers to enrich their software at the time of development with FAIR scientific information including machine-actionable metadata embedded into the respective code. DataDesc converts all metadata into an OpenAPI-compliant YAML file, which various tools can render and process.

These services exemplify how NFDI4ING's development of RDM solutions builds on, integrates, and extends established standards such as DCAT, EMMO and EngMeta to create a reliable and sustainable service portfolio. Moreover, we ensure reliable and easy interaction of the developed services and standards with each other. For example, m4i is available on the Terminology Service for automatic import into the Profile Service, which in turn allows engineers to mark-up their research data through an easy-to-use interface. Afterwards, the Metadata Hub makes it easy to store these profiles on existing storage solutions and to switch between them.

For the second funding period a focus will be on

- a Common Information Model (CIM) which will integrate and consolidate existing terminologies such as m4i, the HPC-Ontology (m4i tailored to describe relevant entities in High Performance Computing; TA Doris), SciMesh to describe experimental workflows (TA Caden) and the ORKG-DataModel to describe and connect publications with software entries (TA Ellen); the CIM is expected to make a significant contribution towards building a common architecture for the NFDI as a whole;
- the provision of an engineering-specific metadata model for FAIR Digital Objects based on a harmonized common information model (CIM). The CIM will form the core of the development of a standardised description of semantic metadata for FDOs, including mappings between various ontologies to allow specific extensions and the support of extensive extraction of metadata from research data provided by the scientific community;
- KG-as-a-Service for subject and archetype specific research data management includes access authorization, SPARQL endpoint, IAM; schema is specified via application profile and links to existing terminologies;
- the provision of a FAIR Digital Objects Knowledge Graph and a query federation solution for knowledge graph integration; and
- generating a single point of entry to search and find research artefacts (and software) from the engineering community including harvesting of decentralized repositories of various kinds and making them browsable. Supporting cross-disciplinary metadata standards by collaboration with other consortia (e.g. NFDI-MatWerk on the Kadi4Mat service), in order to increase connectivity to standards in the national and international context.

These results will be discussed, distributed and further refined in constant exchange with the NFDI4ING stakeholder community (including research and industry partners) as well as in the NFDI e.V. section (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance and the Base4NFDI projects KG4NFDI and TS4NFDI. This will ensure a close alignment and aid in the harmonization of (meta)data and

terminology services for the NFDI as a whole. In summary, NFDI4ING aims to establish a FAIR and semantically enriched metadata management in the engineering sciences (c.f. TA SKG, chapter 5.2).

4.3 Implementation of the FAIR principles and data quality assurance

The engineering research community is known for high demands regarding data processing, metadata management, data storage and compute capacities, amongst others. As such, the archetype concept established in the first funding period showed that the FAIRness of produced research data and software products needs to be addressed with a detailed view on the use-cases given in respective research areas. Most archetypes and overarching solutions (formerly Base Services) focus on the findability of research data and software products across various research groups and disciplines (e.g., Betty's Research Engine, KG from TA Ellen), accessibility (easy-to-use user interfaces developed in TA Alex and TA Ellen), and on inter-operability (e.g., the m4i ontology and the NFDI4ING Terminology Service), with re-use and the closing of data cycles being a key objective of the second funding period.

The NFDI4ING services developed so far are in line with promoting a better FAIRness of engineering research methods and the identification and utilisation of a coordinated understanding of research data management. NFDI4ING's IRL (c.f. chapter 4.1) has been shown to be a central component in the evaluation of quality accompanying the FAIR data principles. Thereby, the IRL is used to evaluate the operation mode, target group and scalability of the developed products and will be continually developed to ensure the provision of high-quality tools, concepts and services by the consortium (c.f. chapter 4.4). Regarding data and metadata availability, NFDI4ING implemented authorised access systems for humans and machines by a networked technical infrastructure based on standardised protocols and open standards that offer a retrieval of high data volumes. These access systems meet the engineering specific challenge that open and accessible (meta)data is not always desired or possible in applied engineering research due to high confidentiality demands.

In the second funding period, a particular focus will be given across all task areas on the creation of engineering-specific FDOs [20] and their availability via a federated discovery service and established knowledge graphs. This will include the provision of an engineering-specific metadata model for FDOs based on a harmonized CIM. Also, the high demands for data storage and compute capacities among engineers will only increase in the future. Recent developments in AI have further shown the importance of bringing FAIR data storage and HPC closer together.

Realistically, only federated offers will be able to satisfy users' needs. Hence, NFDI4ING has already successfully cooperated with NHR centres (NHR4CES, NHR@KIT) and other initiatives (DataStorage.nrw, LSDF) and expects these existing and new comparable cooperations to

intensify in the future. One basis for cooperation will be the creation of FDOs for data exchange and interoperability. As such, the FDO implementation [51] within NFDI4ING will be compatible with established RDA [52][53] and Gaia-X [54] recommendations, which form the basis for Catena-X [21] and should thus leverage data exchange with partners from industry. To enable harmonized processes and regulations for data access along with the protection of personal data, NFDI4ING services will be connected to the Base4NFDI Project IAM4NFDI [10], including an onboarding of NFDI4INGs' services into the Community AAI. In addition, all NFDI4ING outcomes and services adhere to the GDPR regulations.

4.4 Services provided by the consortium

Across our task areas, we develop various outputs (or products), which include stand-alone installable software tools, online (web-based) services and infrastructure, and concepts. A representative selection of NFDI4ING's services is listed and briefly described below. A full list of our products is available in the data sheet in the appendix. The list contains both products newly developed since the start of NFDI4ING ("new products"), as well as products developed by (co)applicants and participants as part of their institutional mission and adapted to engineering needs ("base products"). Furthermore, we introduced the concept of IRLs to continuously track the maturity and usability of the respective products (see chapter 4.1) on their path towards sustainable services within our overarching solutions and OneNFDI. All listed services include their respective IRL.

Software Tools

- Metadata Crawler (IRL 2, new product) extracts parameters from simulation setups. In addition, machine-actionable data sheets supporting hardware documentation with PIDs and QR codes, SOFIRpy, pyKraken and the Personal Information Assistant for Data Analysis (PIA) help reduce the effort required for RDM tasks related to software and file formats. This range of products will be integrated and standardised by TAs Alex and SKG.
- PlotSerializer (IRL 2, new product) enables storing relevant software and data with published plots and will be standardised within TA Alex and TAS and integrated into ing.grid.
- Betty's (Re)Search Engine (IRL 3, base product) links research software it finds on platforms like GitHub to corresponding publications or entries in third-party databases [76*]. It will be integrated and further developed in TA FIS, TA Copilot and Archetype Betty. Moreover it will be integrated in the newly founded Base4NFDI project nfdi.software.
- HOMER (HPMC tool for Ontology-based Metadata Extraction and Re-use, IRL 1, new product) automatically retrieves relevant metadata from script-based workflows on HPC systems and HDF5 files. It will be further developed in TA Doris.

(Web-based) Services and Infrastructure

- SciMesh [32*] (IRL 2, new product), metadata4ing (IRL 2, new product), and DataDesc (IRL 2, new product) allow documenting scientific workflows, provenance, and data-formats in form of a knowledge graph. They will provide the starting point for the development of the Common Information Model (CIM) in TA SKG.
- Open Research Knowledge Graph (IRL 2, base product), a service contributed by TIB, is adopted to engineering sciences within TA Ellen to map semantic descriptions of software and data artefacts in addition to metadata on publications. It will be further developed in TA FIS and integrated with Betty's (Re)Search Engine for harvesting.
- Terminology Service [183*] (IRL 2, new product) provides access to domain-specific terminologies with a graphical user interface and a machine-readable API that enables an automated use of terminologies in external applications. It will be further developed and extensively used within TA SKG. It has been integrated in Base4NFDI as TS4NFDI.
- Data Collections Explorer (IRL 2, new product) provides an overview of domain specific data repositories, archives, databases, and data sets. It will be linked to the NFDI4ING Data Catalog and the NFDI4ING KG in TA FIS.
- RDMO (IRL 4, base product), a data management plan (DMP) service which supports individual needs of the engineering sciences with specific catalogues. It serves as a model for other consortia and will be part of the DMP4NFDI basic service. It will be further developed in TA CPT.
- Jarves (IRL 1, new product), a web framework guiding and assisting engineering scientists over the whole research process including decision support and task automation.
- ing.grid (IRL 2, new product) offers an innovative platform for publishing manuscripts as well as data sets and software tools, that all undergo an open peer review process that fosters the reputation of data and software publications. ing.grid is continuously run and further developed in its respective TA J.
- Kadi4Mat (IRL 2, base product): The workflow system was extended to facilitate the exchange of research data for simulation and sample tracking within TA Caden. It will be further developed in the TA Caden.
- NFDI4ING JupyterHub (IRL 2, new product) offers a platform to develop and reuse scripts and software with a focus on distinct needs of engineering sciences. It will be further developed in TA FIS and TA CPT. It will be integrated in the Jupyter4NFDI basic service.
- Data Transfer Federation (IRL 3, base product) enables remote data access on integrated storage endpoints and facilitates managed data transfers between these endpoints. Further development will happen in TA FIS.

- TUsStorage (IRL 2, base product) provides access to machine-readable open access literature from the engineering sciences to enable text and data mining (TDM) analyses via APIs.
- Prototype for Virtual Environments (IRL 3, new product) is developed in TA Alex as a template for cavitation experiments with large file size and high frequency requirements.
- Coscine (IRL 3, base product) is a data management platform that provides data storage resources as well as permissions and metadata management in a linked data model and will be integrated into TA SKG.
- Data Ingest Service (IRL 2, base product), originating from FID BAUdigital, extracts metadata from an array of 2D/3D file formats and will be adopted in TA SKG.
- NFDI-RFC (IRL 1, new product) is a centralised platform which will be developed for publishing and disseminating requests for comments (RFCs). Integrating the NFDI-RFC process as a new service within the OneNFDI framework will provide user handbooks, support and training for effective implementation and ensure the platform is accessible and user-friendly.

Conceptual products

- Basic-RDM (IRL 2, new product) is an example for a range of trainings developed, giving introduction to various research data management topics.
- “GitLab & getting started with RDM” (IRL 3, base product) is another example, where participants learn the basic use and collaborative work with GitLab in digital workshops. These trainings will be further developed and extended in TA TES and disseminated with TA M&O.
- The Data Quality Metrics website [83*] (IRL 1, new product) enables researchers to exploit different data quality metrics in their experiments and is an example of conceptual products that support engineers in standardising their RDM tasks. It will be further developed in TA TES and connected to the helpdesk.
- The “Knowledge Base for replicable & reproducible software-based experiments” (IRL 2, base product) offers Best Practices and how-to instructions for software development.
- The Guidelines for Text and Data Mining for Research Purposes in Germany (IRL 4, base product), which describe the conditions under which text and data mining (TDM) for scientific purposes may be carried out on scientific publications.

This growing portfolio is the basis of NFDI4ING’s further development towards FAIR, sustainable, and AI-ready solutions. On top of this, NFDI4ING’s extensive competence building efforts are at the forefront of cultural change in engineering sciences.

A straightforward way of addressing all engineering scientists at German research institutions and of contributing to the vision of OneNFDI is to integrate, wherever possible, offerings of

Base4NFDI. For instance, RDMO is already linked to DMP4NFDI and ORKG is already linked to KG4NFDI. Also, our domain-specific Terminology Service is already linked to IAM4NFDI, PID4NFDI, and TS4NFDI. These integration efforts are not limited to the offerings of Base4NFDI but extend to existing RDM infrastructure at co-applicant institutions. Examples are Coscine, RADAR, and Suresoft. These specific services are complemented by base products such as GitLab and Jupyter notebook instances and a PID-Service. The consortium further relies on web-based services such as GitLab-wikis to offer its standalone software tools and material for its conceptual services.

4.5 Impact of changes of external conditions / constraints

The funding of further NFDI consortia and Base4NFDI projects as well as federated and national FDM initiatives have already been addressed in previous chapters. In addition, NFDI4ING has integrated results and community ties of FID BAUdigital, which is no further funded. FID BAUdigital was already strongly connected to NFDI4ING, and its community has since been adopted by TA Ellen.

The current developments and advances in the field of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) in general have led to a greatly increased interest in accessible, machine-actionable scientific data. For example, the use of ELNs in scientific disciplines is increasing significantly to make generated data and their evaluations available in the long term. An important criterion here is to ensure the findability and improving the machine-readability of the data as well as the associated metadata to be able to use them effectively and automatically by means of AI. The value of (training) data and the clarification of rights of use and copyrights, as well as data protection particularly of personal data, are increasingly coming into focus. These aspects are addressed by NFDI4ING in its objective to standardise RDM processes implementing concepts for FDOs and worked on in concrete projects, for example in the enhancement of electronic lab books, e.g., enabling and improving the communication and data exchange between different lab notebooks (i.e. eLabFTW, Kadi4Mat, JuliaBase, SciMesh).

The upcoming Forschungsdatengesetz (FDG) promises better accessibility of data originating from German government entities. This is of particular interest in engineering research related to infrastructure and built environment and will affect TA Ellen. Similar data related legislation on European and national level, such as the EU Digital Product Passport, EU Artificial Intelligence Act, EU Supply Chain Act, EU taxonomy for sustainable activities, or the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) foster the awareness and need for FAIR processes and FDOs in industry and research, especially in systems design. This is even more true for industry initiatives like Catena-X, Industry 4.0 or Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) that need to be adapted as well. These issues will be addressed in TA Alex.

5 Work Programme

In the second funding period, NFDI4ING’s work programme is restructured to address the learnings from the first funding period. Figure 4 depicts the new structure. Most noticeably, the work programme does not encompass community clusters anymore. Instead, the community networking will be continued by embedded liaison officers (LOs) in all task areas (c.f. chapter 3.1). Each task area’s LO will coordinate both internal and external networking activities. Especially tasks that are relevant to other NFDI consortia or that contribute to NFDI-wide cross-cutting activities will be addressed by LOs.

Figure 4: Reworked structure of the NFDI4ING work programme.

Individual task areas are essentially divided into two groups. As the name suggests, the overarching solutions task areas (5.1 - 5.5) provide, maintain and coordinate activities on topics that are relevant to all other task areas in the consortium as well as provide pathways to the greater RDM landscape, e.g., to the Base4NFDI projects. To support this process, they collaborate with the archetype task areas (task areas 5.6 - 5.11), which focus on different method-oriented engineering science approaches. Finally, task area Management & Outreach (5.12) organises the overall management of the consortium and coordinates its outreach activities.

One of the key tasks of the overarching solutions task areas is to broaden and scale products or product ideas beyond applications in a single archetype and thus prevent the generation of silos and parallel developments. Our stated aim is for the archetype task areas to work in tandem on shared tasks wherever possible, always including at least one of the overarching solutions task areas. We provide a list of shared tasks in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden**. Table 4.5-1 below.

Table 4.5-1: Tasks shared between two or more task areas.

Name	Description	Involved TAs	Involved Tasks
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CIM	Customisation and expansion of the CIM, integration of existing terminological resources (DataDesc, SciMesh, HPC-Ontology) into the CIM	SKG, Alex, Caden, Doris, Ellen	SKG-1-1, A-1-1, B-1-1, B-3-4, C-2-1, C-2-2, D-4-1, E-1-1, E-1-2
MPI - Metadata Profiles Instantiation	CIM compliant semantic FDO metadata, definition of Metadata Profiles (Ellen, Caden, Doris, SKG), and its application for KG instantiation (FIS) related to software (Betty) and its interfaces (Ellen), workflows (Caden), experimental setups (Alex) for benchmarks (Betty), HPC based workflows (Doris).	SKG, FIS, Alex, Betty, Caden, Doris, Ellen	SKG-1-3, SKG-2-1, SKG-2-2, FIS-2-4, A-1-2, B-3-4, C-2-3, D-4-1, D-4-3; E-1-2
Connect	Building of connections between the TS (SKG), the DCE (FIS), and data repositories for the connection to the KG of data and software sets.	SKG, FIS, Alex, Betty	SKG-1-2, FIS-1-3, A-1-4, C-3-3, B-3-4
MetaMap	Mapping/crosswalk of non-semantic metadata into the CIM	SKG, Ellen	SKG-1-2, E-1-2
QA	Quality assessment of research data and their metadata	CPT, Alex, Betty, Caden	CPT-1-4, A-2-2, B-1-5, C-4-3, C-4-5
Dash4ING	Integration of services in in the ReSearch Engine and the assisting dashboard	All task areas	CPT-1-1, CPT-1-2, CPT-3-3, FIS-1-1, all tasks tagged with - <i>training</i> and - <i>outreach</i>
LLMInput & Chatbots	Providing and pre-processing content as input for LLMs and extraction of methodological information from them to deliver AI-based assistance for all services	TES, SKG, FIS, CPT, Alex, Betty, Caden, Doris, Ellen, Fiona	TES-1-1, TES-1-2, SKG-3-3, FIS-3-3, CPT 2-1, CPT-2-3, A-4-1, B-3-5, C-1-1, D-4-4, E-1-3, F-5-1
Jup4ING	Integration of NFDI4ING Services in the Jupyter Ecosystem	FIS, CPT, Betty, Caden	FIS-2-3, CPT-3-3, B-1-1, B-2-6, B-3-2, B-3-3, C-3-4
Journal Knowledge Graph (JKG)	Generate a Knowledge Graph representation of the journal ing.grid, compatible with other KGs developed in the consortium, including a user interface for querying	SKG, J, Alex	SKG-1-1, SKG-1-3, SKG-2-1, SKG-2-2, J-5-1, J-5-2, A-1-2
SOB	Develop, implement and evaluate service operation and business models (SOBs)	M&O, CPT, J, Alex, Doris, with further input from all task areas	M&O-7-2, M&O-7-2, CPT-2-2, J-4-3, A-3-3, D-1-2, D-5-1
NFDI-RFC	Providing a repository of standards for RDM specific topics and the sampling of existing NFDI-RFC based on a standardised approval process.	TES, Alex, Caden, Doris	TES-3-1, TES-3-2, TES-3-3, J-3-1, A-1-3, C-1-2, D-4-2, E-1-1

Furthermore, all task areas are committed to a number of overarching goals as described in the NFDI expert committee's key points for the second funding period [4]. All our task areas include activities in training & education, outreach, and activities promoting an open science landscape and furthering the development towards OneNFDI. In the following individual task area chapters, tasks or measures that address these goals are marked with *-training* (training & education), -

outreach (communication, community building, outreach), and/or *-OneNFDI* (collaborations with NFDI consortia or contributions to NFDI-wide cross-cutting activities). Shared tasks are similarly marked by *-shared*.

As is good project management practice, we outlined detailed timelines and a reporting and quality assurance structure along the lines of the DFG KPI (c.f. Appendix chapter 13) for our work programme. The resulting tables (e.g., on specific deliverables and overview of KPIs used to measure progress) and charts (e.g., Gantt-charts breaking down activity and workflows) would go beyond the scope and page limitation of this proposal. However, we will gladly provide them to interested parties on request.

Table 5.0: Overview of task areas

Task Area	Measures	Responsible Co-spokesperson(s)
Training, Education and Standardisation (TES)	TES-1 Continuation of RDM trainings for engineering sciences in standardised and quality-assured manner TES-2 Integration of RDM into student courses TES-3 Standardisation through NFDI-RFCs	R. Schmitt, C. Langenbach
Semantic Metadata and Knowledge Graphs (SKG)	SKG-1 Metadata Harmonization for FAIR Digital Objects SKG-2: Knowledge Graphs Federated Use SKG-3 Onboarding, Outreach and Training	S. Auer, I. Sens, M. Politze
Federated Interactive Data Space (FIS)	FIS-1 Information Services to Search and Find FIS-2 Interactive Federated Services to Store and Share FIS-3 Onboarding, Outreach and Training	M. Müller, A. Streit
Copilot - Assistance Systems and AI (CPT)	CPT-1 Assisting RDM processes and Formal Data Quality Assurance CPT-2 AI Powered Chatbots and Recommender Systems for NFDI4ING CPT-3 Assisting Research Software Engineers using AI	T. Stäcker, S. Wittek, D. Iglezakis
Journal ing.grid (J)	J-1 Efficient, Reliable and Continuous Journal Operation J-2 Community Building and Outreach J-3 Compliance with Standards in Scientific Publishing, Acceptability and Visibility J-4 Achieving Long-Term Sustainability J-5 Developing and Implementing a Journal Knowledge Graph	P. Pelz
Alex – Bespoke Experiments	A-1 FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) and Semantic Metadata Schemas for experimental setups A-2 Semantic Digital Twins (SDT) for experiments and provenance tracking in research processes A-3 Semantic Digital Twins (SDT) for system engineering A-4 Community activation, hands-on-training and standardisation	P. Pelz, A. Dreizler

Betty – Engineering Research Software	<p>B-1 Verification, validation and benchmarking</p> <p>B-2 Concept for the execution of verification, validation, and benchmarking workflows</p> <p>B-3 Use cases for integration of services</p> <p>B-4 Education and outreach</p>	B. Flemisch, J. Unger, J. Linxweiler
Caden – Provenance Tracking of Samples and Data	<p>C-1 Education and outreach</p> <p>C-2 Compilation of a standardised vocabulary for knowledge graphs</p> <p>C-3 Embedding of data science workflows into knowledge graphs</p> <p>C-4 Intrinsic data quality control in research data management using AI</p>	T. Bronger, M. Selzer
Doris – High-Performance Measurement and Computation	<p>D-1 Accessibility and access rights, data security and sovereignty</p> <p>D-2 Provision of a dashboard service (web-based) to support FAIR HPC usage</p> <p>D-3 Support for third-party users & community-based training</p> <p>D-4 Metadata definitions & terminologies, support to data-generating groups</p> <p>D-5 Storage & archive for very large data</p> <p>D-6 Reproducibility on large-scale high-performance systems</p> <p>D-7 'Data to user' concept: Interfaces for Data search, analysis and processing</p> <p>D-8 'Knowledge to user' concept: Protocols, caching, compression</p>	B. Nestler, C. Stemmer
Ellen – Heterogeneous Data Requirements	<p>E-1 Formalising and collecting technical and methodological knowledge</p> <p>E-2 Compiling technical and methodological knowledge to executable software workflows</p> <p>E-3 Utilizing technical and methodological knowledge for research data organisation and exploration</p> <p>E-4 Education and outreach</p>	P. Kuckertz, J. Beetz
Fiona – Many Participants and Simultaneous Devices	<p>F-1 Practical guidelines for data integration</p> <p>F-2 Data Mesh to RDM adaptation concept</p> <p>F-3 Extending the FDP through Data Mesh Integration</p> <p>F-4 Enhancing DT Concepts through Data Mesh Integration</p> <p>F-5 Training, dissemination, and continuation of the results</p>	R. Schmitt, R. Lachmayer
Management & Outreach	<p>M&O-1 Outreach and community engagement</p> <p>M&O-2 Science communication, public relations, and marketing</p> <p>M&O-3 Internal communication, corporate identity and design</p> <p>M&O-4 Interaction with other initiatives and the NFDI bodies</p> <p>M&O-5 FAIR reporting, transparency, and quality management</p> <p>M&O-6 Financial administration and disbursement of funds</p> <p>M&O-7 Development and implementation of successful service operation and business models</p>	G. Jagusch, A. Schwarz

5.1 Task Area Training, Education, and Standardisation (TES)

Introduction

The goal of TA Training, Education and Standardisation (TES) is to manifest the concepts and solutions created in NFDI4ING in the engineering community as common best practices. The TA aims to enable all engineers working in a scientific context to work in complex data-based environments reliably and effortlessly. This is done by providing training and educational materials, as well as driving standardisation. To establish the cultural change NFDI4ING strives to achieve, we also aim at engineering students as the next generation of researchers, with their lecturers as multipliers. A stronger focus is also set on the collaboration with other task areas to enhance the pool of engineering-specific contents available as FAIR OERs.

For the rapid dissemination of guidelines in RDM, the TA will set up a standardisation platform. This platform should make it easy to communicate new guidelines from the results of the NFDI initiatives and further developments in the field of RDM with the scientific community. The development of the NFDI-RFC platform originates from NFDI4ING, which aims to increase the visibility, benefits and acceptance of the platform across the NFDI promoting OneNFDI.

TA TES encompasses the further development and provision of engineering-related RDM trainings for self-paced learning, didactical training modules, train-the-trainer concepts, as well as standardisation procedures and numerous outreach activities.

State of the art in research data management

Compared to the first funding period of NFDI4ING, several services have been developed and experiences have been gained within NFDI4ING and beyond [55]. The current state of the art approaches follows the OER standard [56] and foster interoperability and reusability by using open file formats, open licences and the annotation with metadata, which also allows for the semantic connection between trainings, e. g., as proposed by DALIA [2]. Our Education Portal [57*] established during the first funding period utilises all the mentioned practices and ready-to-use trainings with interactive elements and is available on an open-source training platform. For the second funding period, the focus will shift towards establishing previously developed services, and the integration of the services into university teaching. This will be supported by a SIG, as was the case in the first funding period.

Regarding standards, a broad variety of potentially applicable frameworks can be found. However, analysis shows that RDM is commonly only rudimentarily covered and no dedicated concept for overarching RDM standards is available. Most are either concrete thematical standards or specialised in one topic (e.g., Internet RFCs, [58][59]). This was the starting point

for developing and establishing a request for comments (RFC) workflow based on the concept of the IETF (Internet standards) for the specific RDM requirements of engineers.

Objectives of task area Training, Education, and Standardisation

OTES-1: We provide engineering-specific trainings.

OTES-2: We provide data literacy and RDM education from the beginning, i.e., in university teaching

OTES-3: We establish a NFDI-RFC standardisation service for RDM practices.

OTES-1 to -3 contribute to NFDI4ING's focus points for the second funding period (c.f. 2.1): Trainings and standardisation are communicated to and collaborated on with other task areas as well as our target group (1). The standardisation documents and (self-paced) training materials we provide are a sustainable (2) and scalable (3) way to establish RDM practices and standardise RDM procedures (4). With platforms for trainings as well as for standardisation we provide common infrastructure (5), that potentially can be reused beyond NFDI4ING.

Measures and deliverables

TA TES is divided into three measures on training materials for researchers, didactical training units for students, and standardisation concept.

Measure TES-1 Continuation of RDM trainings for engineering sciences in standardised and quality-assured manner (RWTH, TIB, KIT-Bib, DLR)

Building upon the existing NFDI4ING learning platform, the existing engineering specific RDM is continued, maintained, and extended. This emphasizes collaboration with RDM training and support units, engineers, and researchers at engineering research institutions, leveraging their expertise for training development and evaluation.

Task TES-1-1 Content Review and Update: A continuous review of the existing RDM training materials on the NFDI4ING learning platform is conducted to ensure their alignment with current RDM tools and best practices. This review involves a detailed assessment of the content and structure and is conducted by our interdisciplinary team in collaboration with other experts and the engaged user community. Iterative feedback ensures relevance, usability, and correctness of the training materials.

Task TES-1-2 Content Development -shared: In collaboration with NFDI4ING archetypes and solutions, new training modules on emerging RDM topics relevant to engineering are developed, ensuring that the content remains at the forefront of engineering advancements. Specialised trainings itself must be held by the respective task areas' staff. Additionally, we create targeted learning materials to address specific challenges faced by engineers, e.g., efficient data

management workflows. These materials are delivered in a clear, concise, and engaging format, utilising multimedia elements, e.g., infographics, and are supplemented with engineering-specific case studies and practical exercises.

Task TES-1-3 Training policy and standardisation of FAIR OER trainings *-training -OneNFDI -shared*: A common educational standard for all NFDI4ING trainings with paramount key elements is defined in form of a training policy together with a checklist. The policy covers the full process from creating to sharing didactically valuable trainings, integrating the learning objective matrix [2], and organising to conducting inspiring events including the feedback afterwards. To support standardised (c.f. measure TES-2) and FAIR OER trainings, we build a metadata template based on the FAIR-by-design methodology for generating learning material [27] and community standards (e.g., [6][3][4][60][61][62]). Open formats, the publication in a repository with DOI, and open licences will foster OER and ensure registration in DALIA and other prominent OER platforms (e.g. ORCA [63], Twillo [64]). Open technical formats allow machine-readability, e.g., for TA CPT.

Task TES-1-4 Promotion and dissemination through networking and exchange *-outreach*: Driven by the LOs, the team of TA TES uses networking and events to exchange with the community. The goal is to promote and disseminate the deliverables (e.g., trainings, EduBricks4Ing introduced in measure TES-2) and get input in form of requirements and feedback. The various contact points include stakeholders within NFDI4ING, lecturers, NFDI consortia and sections (esp. section EduTrain), as well as initiatives like the German federal-state RDM initiatives (Landesinitiativen), the RDA, and the DALIA project. We continue working with our long-term community from the SIG RDM Training.

Measure TES-2 Integration of RDM into student courses (RWTH, TIB, KIT-Bib)

For the long-lasting process of integration of RDM into student teaching and curricula, we choose a bottom-up approach to raise awareness of the topic and to demonstrate ways of integration into existing courses or labs. We foster the exchange between lectures and highlight teaching examples.

Task TES-2-1 Good practice teaching examples: Based on the good experience from the first funding period, we continue identifying existing training materials and multipliers to extend our scope and reach in RDM training and education. The NFDI4ING community surveys and focused search in engineering teaching help find further potential courses, or labs and lecturers to contact directly. Regular presentations of teaching examples in collaboration with TA M&O, e.g., via the NFDI4ING newsletter, will promote existing course concepts and motivate others to adapt them to their own use cases.

Task TES-2-2 EduBricks4Ing *-training -OneNFDI*: EduBricks, developed in the NFDI section EduTrain (WP3), are small modular learning/teaching units described by standardised metadata.

Breaking down the contents into small building blocks allows a flexible combination for scalable and targeted RDM training. Our focus is the creation of engineering related EduBricks for the needs of the NFDI4ING community - EduBricks4Ing. The creation of more generic EduBricks is a collaborative effort across the NFDI consortia, where we want to equally contribute and benefit.

Task TES-2-3 Implementation in selected courses or labs: Based on the developed EduBricks4Ing, we support engineering lectures integrating these into their teaching concepts and lessons. Abstraction and publication of the course concept might serve as a template for other teaching staff. For TA TES, this serves as validation, and iterative feedback cycles will enable improving the modular EduBricks4Ing in the sense of quality assurance.

Measure TES-3 Standardisation through NFDI-RFCs (KIT, DLR)

Task TES-3-1 Refinement of concept and structure: Based on the basic concept and the first styleguide version for the NFDI-RFCs, we identify several candidates for community-driven NFDI-RFCs. Each of this shall go through the planned publication and review process. The given results are used to review for assessment and refinement of the concept. Thus, we ensure that the NFDI-RFCs meet the needs and expectations of our communities.

Task TES-3-2 Establishment of development stages of a NFDI-RFC: Referring to the obtained experience with the finalised NFDI-RFC concept, we establish three development stages of NFDI-RFC: (1) Proposed standard. NFDI-RFC is stable, well understood, and generally considered useful within the community. (2) Draft standard. NFDI-RFC reached a level of stability that allows for the implementation of the standard in RDM applications. (3) NFDI standard. NFDI-RFC achieved technical maturity, widespread implementation, and significant benefits for RDM in the scientific community. During the establishment process we reflect regularly by testing the practical application of the three stages. This testing leads to extensions and refinements of the NFDI-RFC approval process where necessary.

Task TES-3-3 Launching NFDI-RFC platform for the NFDI as a whole -OneNFI: Finally, we set up a platform for publishing the NFDI-RFC (quasi-)standards (guidelines) and open it for the NFDI and NFDI4ING communities. The publication pathway and review process within the NFDI-RFC platform are communicated to the NFDI sections and other consortia to foster the acceptance of the NFDI-RFC concept and service. We expect with this support that the NFDI communities build their own NFDI-RFCs to establish new standards for OneNFI.

Possible risks of implementation

The main risk of implementation lies in the integration into curricula and institutional processes as these depend on external factors. We will address this by promoting our materials especially to multipliers and support the usage of our services with best practice examples.

Competence and expertise

In TA TES an interdisciplinary team brings in broad expertise on RDM processes and tools, and RDM teaching and workshops from an engineering as well as an infrastructure perspective. All institutions have been working together since 2019. The LO position is split between DLR (coordination and dissemination), RWTH and KIT (both dissemination), to integrate RDM into the respective communities efficiently and to best achieve dissemination. We continue our efforts to support services of the NFDI4ING, namely the helpdesk and the Q&A-platform [38*]. Here, we provide our knowledge based on the questions asked, and can at the same time gather information on the specific needs and requests by the engineering community.

Participating in TA TES is the Saxon State and University Library Dresden (SLUB) as one of the largest scientific libraries in Germany. Their expertise and collaboration in various RDM initiatives and other NFDIs as well as their strong community network will support the dissemination of TA TES's results.

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other task areas

TA TES supports all NFDI4ING archetypes and overarching solutions to create and publish trainings for their individual services and offerings. In the same way, TA TES will request input from the archetype TAs as well as the other overarching solutions TAs to enrich basic training materials and modular didactical units. Doing so, this results in a 'push and pull' between other task areas and TA TES. The LOs play an important role in bringing the respective groups together in a formalised way, and to inform about new developments in both directions.

With its activities, TA TES contributes to NFDI4ING's key objectives (c.f. chapter 2.2). The dissemination and discussion of our training materials foster our understanding of the community. Since the deliverables are OERs, they serve all engineering scientists in Germany. With best practices and experiences published in trainings, as well as RFCs, RDM processes are (semi-) standardized. The EduBricks4Ing brings RDM in university teaching, education of PhD students, and potentially in curricula. The trainings on reusing data and preparation of data for reuse contributes to the scientific reputation of researchers. Alignment within NFDI4ING, NFDI (i.e., other consortia as well as Base4NFDI), and initiatives beyond contributes to the vision of One NFDI. The provisioning of trainings (here as well as by archetypes) supports the long-term sustainability and cultural change regarding RDM in engineering.

5.2 Task Area Semantic Metadata and Knowledge Graphs (SKG)

Introduction

The aim of TA SKG is the realisation of a federated knowledge graph (KG) and the provision of an associated harmonised set of tools and services for FAIR and semantically enriched metadata

management. The basis for this is a semantic model that forms the core of the development of a standardised description of semantic metadata for FDOs. In TA SKG, the semantic metadata of an FDO is instantiated via a KG and linked with each other so that comprehensive knowledge about the creation and use of FDOs becomes available.

State of the art in research data management

Semantic metadata is essential for the FAIRification of engineering data management, including relevant software, methods, instruments and tools. The ontology metadata4ing (m4i) provides a mid-level data model that plays a key role in this area. This model serves as a bridge that links data with software, methods, instruments and tools. Recent developments in related areas include MatWerkOntology [65] and PMD Core Ontology [66] for materials science and MathModDB and AlgoData [67] for mathematics. These ontologies provide compatible, albeit sometimes overlapping, terms and concepts that facilitate interdisciplinary data integration. The m4i and further ontologies are accessible via the Terminology Service (TS). The TS has been integrated into several NFDI4ING tools and is constantly expanding its terminologies to improve the harmonisation of the software with external developments. Building on this, next the Metadata Profile Service (MPS) enables the creation, shared use and maintenance of subject-specific metadata profiles. These profiles, which are realised as SHACL shapes, can be created using terms from the available ontologies in a modular system [68]. The MPS also validates metadata records against existing profiles. Coscine is a research data management platform that supports different resource types and the creation of custom metadata schemas for domain-specific use cases [69]. Coscine is well integrated with the MetadataHub [45*] that provides access to different metadata repositories through a unified interface [69], although the ability to collect metadata for seamless access to knowledge graphs is still missing. Coscine constructs a knowledge graph in which all files, the relations between different versions of the files, metadata, extracted metadata, resources and projects are described in detail. However, there are further KG besides Coscine, e.g., the ORKG that is being worked on in the archetype TA Ellen. Another important tool is the Data Ingest Service, a platform for research data publications, that enhances data publications by combining domain-specific MPS with microservices for processing and visualizing 2D and 3D data, automated metadata extraction, and geodata visualization [70*].

Objectives of task area Semantic Metadata and Knowledge Graphs

OSKG-1: Providing an engineer-specific FDO semantic metadata model based on a harmonized information model, including ontology mappings.

OSKG-2: Enable creation and reuse of community specific MPs.

OSKG-3: Semantification and validation of metadata from research data as well as preparing it for use in the FDO metadata model.

OSKG-4: Provision of a FDO KG and a query federation solution for KG integration.

OSKG-5: Tools and Service integration into community specific RDM applications.

OSKG-6: Provision of training and learning resources such as guides and worked examples.

Measures and deliverables

Measure SKG-1 Metadata Harmonization for FAIR Digital Objects (TIB, US, TUDa, RWTH)

Measure SKG-1 comprises all work that arises with regard to the design of semantic metadata for FDO. This includes work on the standardisation of metadata, its curation and use in domain-specific requirements.

Task SKG-1-1 Common Information Model *-shared -OneNFDI*: Creation of and establishing a NFDI4ING CIM in strong collaboration with related consortia (MaRDI, NFDI-MatWerk), the NFDI task force Metadata and the working group Ontology Harmonization in the corresponding NFDI section. This CIM works as a backbone of the SKG and its harmonised services via a comprehensive and maintainable ontology. The ontology will serve as the foundation for NFDI4ING's services and interfaces, as well as facilitate mappings to other terminologies within NFDI, EOSC, and beyond. The CIM will encompass all pertinent engineering entities, including datasets, software, actors, methods, tools/instruments and their setups, and mathematical models (together with MaRDI), building upon existing vocabularies and ontologies both within and outside of NFDI4ING.

Task SKG-1-2 Terminology Service *-shared*: The Terminology Service (TS) is providing a centralized platform for harmonizing terminologies across various applications. In the TA SKG-harmonised set of tools and services, it facilitates clear communication within and between diverse engineering research communities and beyond, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration. The TS' success depends on regularly updating ontologies and solving operational issues. This includes improving system stability, addressing automation challenges, managing resources, and ensuring ontology quality. Enhancing performance and security through system updates and fostering community integration, particularly with existing platforms, are also key goals for the TS.

Task SKG-1-3 Semantic Metadata Schemas *-shared*: The Metadata Profile Service (MPS) is essential for creating, sharing, and managing semantic metadata schemata within the TA SKG harmonised set of tools and services. It integrates terms from existing ontologies into profiles tailored for specific subjects and applications. These profiles are crucial for ensuring that metadata adheres to FAIR principles and fits seamlessly into the NFDI4ING KG (c.f. Task SKG-2-2). The commitment to MPS includes maintaining its continuous operation, resolving bugs, providing technical support, and upgrading the service to meet IRL 4 standards for long-term sustainability.

Measure SKG-2 Knowledge Graphs Federated Use (RWTH, TIB, TUDa, KIT,)

Designed for the simple networking of information, the approach of providing a KG is particularly valuable for the standardised integration of other information sources and thus the reduction of

information silos. The CIM agreed on in measure 2-1 forms the core of the KG and is the basis for harmonised, federated queries that enable extensive reuse of research data. In addition, we will also offer tools and services to integrate the creation of FDOs into existing scientific workflows.

Task SKG-2-1 Metadata Collection and Instantiation *-shared*: The TA SKG harmonised set of tools and services provides solutions to integrate existing research data into the NFDI4ING KG as well as to create new FDOs, enabling their seamless creation and registration by tools like the Typed PID Maker. For the integration of existing DOs, we offer methods to harvest and ingest already published metadata from different sources. These metadata-sets need to be mapped to the CIM in order to be ingested into the NFDI4ING KG. These metadata will be accessible through the MetadataHub and made available via the Turntable API. Additional tools feature tools to extract metadata from specific research data, such as texts or selected 3D data formats. While the Data Ingest Service will prepare and process an array of 2D/3D formats (e.g. point-cloud, mesh), Coscine allows searching for already existing metadata profiles (MP). Making use of an NFDI4ING Kernel Information Profile (based on the CIM) allows these existing MP to be seamlessly integrated into new FDOs and registered in the KG.

Task SKG-2-2 Knowledge Graph *-shared -OneNFDI*: NFDI4ING has already worked on KGs during the first funding period. The second funding period will focus on establishing a federation of KGs and the availability of FDOs within it. Semantic metadata based on MP and created in task SKG-2-1 are an essential part of FDOs. Solutions will be developed in this task to transfer the semantic metadata to a KG. This includes providing interfaces to enable programmatic access to and integration of the Data Collections Explorer with the TA SKG set of tools and services in close cooperation with TA FIS. The instantiation of FDOs is planned to be realised in close coordination with the working group Knowledge Graphs in the NFDI section Metadata, Terminologies and Provenance, and the KGI4NFDI base service.

Measure SKG-3 Onboarding, Outreach and Training (TIB, RWTH, KIT, US, TUDa)

The services provided in the task area need to be integrated into the daily work of researchers within the community. It is therefore essential to communicate the results of the tasks within the consortium and to other interested individuals. The Liaison Officer (LO) serves as a contact point to facilitate the communication process and the results of all tasks are communicated via the help desk and trainings.

Task SKG-3-1 Task Area Contact Point & Liaison Officer *-outreach*: Serve as key contact point for other TAs and interested researchers and infrastructure providers from outside of the consortium.

Task SKG-3-2 Helpdesk and outreach *-outreach*: Provide 2nd level support for users for the provided services. Increasing visibility through organisation and presence at online and in person events, besides social media channels.

Task SKG-3-3 Training and Education *-training*: Build up a knowledge base for the provided services. Create and offer trainings on the usage and integration of provided services.

Possible risks of implementation

A risk of implementation regarding the development of a CIM is a lack of agreement within the broader NFDI community that can be mitigated by active participation in the WG Ontology Harmonization and the TF Metadata.

TS relies on software development from an external organisation, EMBL-EBI. To address this, there is direct dialogue regarding discrepancies between NFDI4ING's requirements and EMBL-EBI's approach.

Competence and expertise

TA SKG is formed by the co-applicants TIB, KIT (SCC), US, RWTH (ITC) and TUDa. The TA is led by the TIB. The services offered in the TA are based on production-ready services that were developed during the first NFDI4ING funding phase or are already offered by the partners as part of their institutional missions. The partners are heavily involved in the NFDI sections and will continue and deepen their involvement. The LO at the TIB will serve as a central point of contact within the TA.

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other Task Areas

TA SKG provides tools for creating and querying semantic metadata for FDOs, while TA FIS manages the research data infrastructure described by TA SKG. TA TES standardises and trains users in the SKG tools, and TA CPT supports the curation of metadata. Shared tasks connect archetypes with TA SKG and facilitate the use of the tools and provide pathways for feedback. Training and workshops organised together with TA TES ensure the effective use of TA tools. The TA SKG liaison officer mediates between archetype TA and overarching solutions TAs and integrates further archetypes into TA SKG activities as the project progresses.

5.3 Task Area Federated Interactive Data Space (FIS)

Introduction

TA FIS bundles RDM services that allow researchers to make use of federated storage and compute infrastructures. A great focus is laid on interconnection of services and the ability to serve as sustainable backends for the engineering-specific services offered by the archetype task areas. FIS takes advantage of existing sustainable infrastructures distributed within the community and aims to integrate research data artefacts therein. Multiplicity and heterogeneity of systems shows the need for a federated approach to make information discoverable in the resulting NFDI4ING data space.

State of the art in research data management

Engineering researchers have always had high demands for data storage and compute capacities. Recent developments in AI have further shown the importance of bringing FAIR data storage and HPC closer together. Realistically only federated offers will be able to satisfy users' needs. Hence, NFDI4ING has already successfully cooperated with NHR centres (NHR4CES, NHR@KIT) and other initiatives (DataStorage.nrw, LSDF) and expects these existing and new comparable cooperations to intensify [71*]. Even though access, bounding conditions, and technical realisations vary greatly among these systems, not all use cases can already be covered. Furthermore, none of these services is currently mandated to support NFDI4ING's nationwide community.

While previously FDOs were only a concept, NFDI consortia, including NFDI4ING, have shown implementations that are now integrated into sustainable services [72]. Coscine, for example, allows researchers to access industry-grade storage in the multi PB range, semantically annotate data and utilize FDOs for data exchange and interoperability [30*]. The FDO implementation within NFDI4ING aims to be compatible to both RDA recommendations and IDSA/Gaia-X which form the basis for Catena-X and should thus leverage data exchange with partners from industry.

Next to generic data storage, especially for research software engineering (RSE), GitLab and GitHub became de-facto standards to manage source code and underlying software development processes. NFDI4ING provided a GitLab instance with enterprise features to spread best practices in RSE. Meanwhile many federal states set up central instances; like git.nrw adopting NFDI4ING's principles [73]. Consequently, the discipline specific service as part of NFDI4ING is handed over to statewide infrastructures and driving the cultural change of using GitLab features in RSE is considered a success [74*][75].

So far, the engineering sciences community has neither established a central, trusted, and open repository to publish data nor a central point of entry to search its federated data space. Having no lightweight and discipline specific place to go hinders researchers of the community to find and publish data in the first place. Nevertheless, approaches like ReSoDate, Betty's ReSearch Engine [76*] or the Data Collections Explorer [77*] exist, focussing on individual aspects of making artefacts in the data space discoverable, but are not yet interconnected.

Key objectives of task area Federated Interactive Data Space

OFIS-1: Offer a single point of entry to find research data and software artefacts from the engineering community including harvesting of decentralized repositories of various kinds and make them browsable.

OFIS-2: Allow publishing or privately preserving datasets of potentially 100s of TB, computer-based workflows or source codes and allow managing access to unpublished or internal results.

OFIS-3: Allow interactive execution of software artefacts in federated computing environments.

OFIS-4: Ensure interoperability in a federation of systems through the implementation of the FAIR Digital Object (FDO) concept in storage systems and data exchange formats.

OFIS-5: Ensure interoperability of the provided services with other consortia, Base4NFDI, and international initiatives like FDO Forum, EOSC, IDS or Gaia-X.

Measures and deliverables

Measure FIS-1 Information Services to Search and Find

The purpose of this measure is to provide researchers with a single point of entry to discover research artefacts (datasets and software) in NFDI4ING's federated data space. This is achieved by making them searchable through the ReSearch Engine [76*] that combines information from sources like the OKRG, GitHub, GitLab Instances, KGs in Coscine, or published data from repositories. While a central index will be maintained in NFDI4ING's Data Catalog, non-indexable data collections are ingested into the Data Collections Explorer.

Task FIS-1-1 NFDI4ING ReSearch Engine -OneNFDI (TUC): Transferred from TA Betty to become the central point of entry for engineering researchers to search and discover research artefacts by cross searching for code repositories, corresponding scientific papers and data repositories by (1) integrating into the homepage of NFDI4ING, (2) integrating Data Catalog and Data Collections Explorer as sources, and (3) enhancing to IRL 4 and prepare for sustainable operation. The ReSearch Engine will leverage its position in the newly founded base service nfdi.software [15] to ensure the OneNFDI perspective.

Task FIS-1-2 NFDI4ING Data Catalog (TIB): Creation of an open search index for engineering research data and software that is obtained from harvestable resources in the federated data space by (1) instantiating an index with central GitLab instances, (2) indexing TU9 data repositories, (3) indexing Repository4Ing, (4) harvesting KGs and sources adhering to the common information model defined by TA SKG, (5) enhancing to IRL 4 and preparing for sustainable operation, and (6) continuous involvement in Section Metadata WG Harvesting.

Task FIS-1-3 NFDI4ING Data Collection Explorer -shared (KIT): Provide the DCE to increase accessibility of research data published in not traditionally indexable resources, i.e., on personal or project home pages by (1) extending to act as a knowledge graph in cooperation with TA SKG (2) enabling harvesting by the Data Catalog, (3) enhancing to IRL 4 and preparing for sustainable operation, and (4) continuous involvement in Section Metadata WG Knowledge Graphs.

Measure FIS-2 Interactive Federated Services to Store and Share

Existing storage infrastructures available to researchers are distributed among local, national, and international providers from academia and industry. While this greatly encourages sovereign scientific work, it often requires advanced solutions to use and reuse research data. This measure

aims to provide more standardised interfaces and technically connect existing offers to increase data mobility within the federated data space. For a start North Rhine-Westphalia and Baden-Württemberg offer a share of their systems (DataStorage.nrw and LSDF) to NFDI4ING.

Task FIS-2-1 Federated Identity and Access Management -OneNFDI (RWTH): Connect NFDI4ING with the Base4NFDI Project IAM4NFDI by (1) consulting for onboarding of NFDI4ING's services into the Community AAI, (2) managing VOs within the CAAI, and (3) continuous involvement in NFDI section Common Infrastructures WG IAM (current speaker M. Politze, RWTH).

Task FIS-2-2 Repository4Ing (TIB, KIT): Provide a central place to publish engineering science data by (1) selecting a suitable software/provider with RADAR as desired choice (including federated IAM and publishing multi-TB data sets), (2) integrating suitable long-term storage providers among the consortium members (storage federation), (3) establishing a sustainable operating model, (4) enhancing to IRL 3 as a service for the engineering community, and (5) establishing synchronisation across consortia in a WG Repositories within NFDI section Common Infrastructures.

Task FIS-2-3 NFDI4ING JupyterHub -OneNFDI, -shared (US): Extend the Jupyter service by (1) creating engineering specific environments, (2) interfacing with the ReSearch Engine and Data Catalog to allow interactive execution, (3) connecting Federated Storage, FDO and software marketplaces to load datasets and dependencies, (4) adding notebook meta data into a KG, (5) aligning with Jupyter4NFDI, (6) enhancing to IRL 4 and preparing sustainable operation.

Task FIS-2-4 Formats and Interfaces for Data Interoperability with FAIR Digital Objects -OneNFDI (RWTH): Offer Coscine as a service to add an FDO layer on top of industry-grade cloud storage systems by (1) implementing compatibility to RDA and IDSA recommendations, (2) using RO-Crate as a bundle format to transport data and metadata within the federation, (3) handling to respect other kinds of research artefacts if agreed upon by archetypes, and (4) continuous involvement in NFDI section Common Infrastructures WG Overall Architecture (current speaker M. Politze, RWTH).

Task FIS-2-5 Federated Storage -OneNFDI (RWTH, KIT): Establish federated application and provisioning of research data storage by (1) integrating providers from federal states, (2) leveraging Coscine for provisioning and IAM, (3) using JARDS for science-led reviews for storage grants, similar to computing time in NHR, (4) building a TCO model for long-term data storage, (5) increasing mobility of data with a file transfer service, and (6) continuous involvement in NFDI section Common Infrastructures WG Multi Cloud.

Measure FIS-3 Onboarding, Outreach and Training

The services provided in the task area need to be integrated into the daily work of researchers within the community. It is therefore essential to communicate the results of the tasks within the

consortium and to other interested individuals. The LO serves as a contact point to facilitate the communication process and the results of all tasks are communicated via the help desk and trainings.

Task FIS-3-1 Task Area Contact Point & Liaison Officer *-outreach* (RWTH): Serve as key contact point for other TAs and interested researchers and infrastructure providers from outside of the consortium.

Task FIS-3-2 HelpDesk *-outreach* (all): Provide 2nd level support for users for the provided services.

Task FIS-3-3 Training and Education *-training* (all): Build up a knowledge base for the provided services. Create and offer trainings on the usage and integration of provided services.

Possible risks of implementation

Core of the federated idea is to rely on specified interfaces. This mitigates the risk of a provider- or vendor-lock-in. It also allows each institution to take responsibilities according to their core competencies reducing the risk of task failures. Processes for building federations can be stagnant as they involve a large amount of communication. This is mitigated by building on or adapting existing federation agreements (e.g. federated IAM, allocation process from NHR). Furthermore, all existing services already provide functionality to their existing userbase and remain operational while extending the federation. Federated services are also handled in NFDI's sections and Base4NFDI. To mitigate these risks and to ensure compatibility with the overall NFDI, engagement in these bodies is essential and will require a significant amount of the TAs workforce and at the same time requires flexibility to adapt implemented services accordingly.

Competence and expertise

TA FIS is executed by RWTH (ITC), TUC, KIT (SCC), US (FOKUS), and TIB and coordinated by the RWTH as the representative of these partners. The services provided in the TA build upon production ready services developed within NFDI4ING or offered by the partners as part of their institutional mission. The partners are deeply involved in NFDI's sections and will continue and deepen their involvement. The LO at RWTH will serve as a central contact point within the TA. All institutions aim for long-term support (IRL 4) for their provided services.

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other task areas

TA FIS mostly focuses on the technical interoperability to span the data space. Hence it serves to give input and use the output of other cross cutting TAs, most prominently (1) contribute OER and towards standardisation of data formats with TA TES, (2) adopt the information model and KGs for harvesting from TA SKG and (3) collaborate on JupyterHub, LLM based information extraction, and integration of DMPs with the application and provisioning model with TA CPT.

Consequently, the TA also defines collaborative responsibilities with the archetype TAs, most prominently with (1) TA Alex on adoption of RO-Crates as FDOs, (2) TA Betty on JupyterHub, (3) TA Caden on providing data storage backends for ELNs, (4) TA Doris on connecting with NHR centres, (5) TA Ellen on ReSoDate, and (6) TA Fiona on Data Mesh and data architectures.

5.4 Task Area Copilot – Assistance Systems and Artificial Intelligence (CPT)

Introduction

Copilot is an umbrella term for AI-powered assistance systems for engineering researchers, enhancing all NFDI4ING services. This TA is based on the work in former TA Base Services measures S1 and S7 and partially S2 and enhanced by generative AI methods. It aims for integration and enhancing of existing NFDI4ING and NFDI services by providing a full data life cycle management. The main objective is to make it as easy as possible for researchers to get specific recommendations on existing RDM and RSE services, on how to integrate them into their daily research workflows, and on how to plan and deliver their high-quality and FAIR data products. It supports the dissemination and adoption of NFDI4ING results in our communities. The Copilot is highly connected to all archetype TAs and further overarching solutions TAs, since their best practices, recommendations, workflows, and service offers are mutually integrated with the Copilot.

State of the art in research data management

In the first funding period of NFDI4ING, several services were developed to support users in the data lifecycle: The RDMO service (IRL 4) to plan data management [78], the ReSearch Engine (IRL 3) [76*] to find data, JupyterHub (IRL 2) [79*] to develop research software, and Jarves (IRL 1) [80*] as a guidance and recommendation tool. With TUStorage (IRL 2) [81*], a provision system for machine readable open access literature has been set up in test operation to access literature for TDM analyses via APIs. Metrics were defined to assess the quality of RDM processes [82*] and data quality [83*]. Outside NFDI4ING, approaches to automatically assess the formal quality of semantic metadata [84] exist, but do not solve the problem that metadata does often not meet the information needs of researchers [85], sometimes resulting in a missing correlation between metadata quality of datasets and their use [86]. Further tools for assisting and automating the research process are under development, e.g., Heliport [248][249]. The white paper of the NFDI WG infra-dmp [78] on the use of data management plans as well as the Salzburg Manifesto [87] calls for greater implementation of machine actionable DMPs across the NFDI. The NFDI4ING RDMO service acts as a model for the NFDI-wide basic service DMP4NFDI [14] that can easily be integrated into research workflows (on the example software management plans [88]) and connected to other Base4NFDI services like IAM4NFDI [10].

The next step is to integrate and enhance these services. The rapid progress of generative Artificial Intelligence (genAI) offers the potential to assist humans in a variety of fields. Regarding RDM, AI is a two-fold topic: a) making research data ready for its usage by ML/AI methods beyond the FAIR principles discussed since 2023 [89], and b) using genAI to assist researchers in their daily RDM and RSE efforts. While the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) [90] for programming assistance tools [91][92][93][94][95] advanced Research Software Engineering significantly, using AI for RDM support is far less worked on except in first attempts for DMP assistance [96]. While the method of Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) [97] shows the greatest potential for supporting RDM tasks, lacking input materials and benchmarking sets remain challenges.

Key objectives of Task Area Copilot - Assistance Systems and Artificial Intelligence

OCPT-1: We standardise and automate the RDM processes wherever possible.

OCPT-2: We utilise AI methods for better RDM and FAIR data and support the scientists by chatbots for all NFDI4ING services that enable us to reach every researcher in engineering.

OCPT-3: We enhance metadata quality and FAIRify data by AI-driven recommender systems.

OCPT-4: We help Research Software Engineers to develop and find (better) software using AI-based assistants.

Measures and deliverables

Measure CPT-1 Assisting RDM processes and Formal Data Quality Assurance

This measure supports the dissemination and absorption of NFDI4ING results in our communities by bringing all NFDI4ING guidelines, recommendations, and workflows together to support decision-making, data quality checks, enabling easier planning and implementation of RDM measures across the whole data life cycle.

Task CPT-1-1 Integration of RDM services via RDMO -shared -OneNFDI (ULB): We implement machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs) by providing integrations and plugins for RDMO to NFDI4ING and NFDI services allowing researchers to plan and achieve their FAIR data products more easily.

Task CPT-1-2 Full data life cycle management -shared (ULB): In addition to the planning phase, a full data life cycle management guides researchers through the entire research process. For each phase researchers are provided with tasks and recommendations via a dashboard to improve data quality, FAIR data management and AI-readiness. Recommendations also include research software management based on our implementation of the software management plan in RDMO and further supported by the collection of workflows generated by measure CPT-3. Connecting all phases further enables simple transfer of metadata to the NFDI4ING knowledge graph.

Task CPT-1-3 DMP evaluation and recommendations *-shared* (ULB): We provide an automated DMP Review Service in RDMO with recommendations, guidelines, and results from the NFDI4ING task areas, and include metrics based on maturity models [98*] and FAIR metrics [82*]. In a next step, we develop the service to include a more flexible recommender system based on the AI powered chatbot developed in measure CPT-2. Further LLM integrations may support the DMP writing process, by creating a comprehensible text draft based on structured answers in RDMO.

Task CPT-1-4 Formal data quality assurance *-shared* (FoKUS): We assist researchers and reviewers to assess and improve metadata quality of engineering data and software. In doing this, we focus on completeness regarding engineering-specific information requirements. We deliver a REST based service to be integrated into review processes and assistance tools building on general FAIR checkers like F-UJI [99] and metadata validation via profiles from TA SKG.

Measure CPT-2 AI Powered Chatbots and Recommender Systems for NFDI4ING

The CPT-2 measure aims to enhance NFDI4ING's services through AI-powered chatbots and recommender systems. The initiative encompasses three primary tasks: pre-processing content for LLMs, provisioning LLMs and chatbots, and developing use cases for AI-based assistance. These efforts improve the accessibility, usability, and efficiency of NFDI4ING's resources and tools.

Task CPT-2-1 Providing and pre-processing content as input for LLMs *-shared* (ULB, DBIS):

This task involves curating and transforming both information about NFDI4ING services and open access engineering literature into structured, machine-readable formats. We collaborate with all task areas to identify and harvest high-quality input data from various sources, converting raw data into (semi-)structured formats through data cleaning, normalisation, and transformation, and enhancing the machine-readability of numerical data, tables, and graphs while ensuring data integrity. Additionally, we integrate the approach with NFDI4ING services (starting with (Re)Search Engine [76*], JupyterHub [79*], Kadi4Mat-LLM [19*], [100]) and others (like the DAFDM project [101]) to provide structured content and data via APIs. Building on the first funding period, this task advances the infrastructure and tools (free and fee-based) for effective content provisioning and pre-processing information about NFDI4ING's services.

Task CPT-2-2 Provision of LLMs and chatbots *-shared* (DBIS): This task focuses on securely provisioning at least one LLM, leveraging state-of-the-art open source LLMs, such as Mixtral 8x7B [102]. It involves prototyping and developing a robust system, managing the LLM(s), and providing a user interface for interaction with engineering researchers. Furthermore, the task includes evaluating and potentially integrating the AI4EOSC platform [103] to enhance AI model development and deployment. Prototyping with RAG strengthens tailoring the LLM(s) to the NFDI4ING domain. Initially, this task uses hardware from own contributions by RWTH Aachen for

prototyping, with plans to expand deployment in collaboration with operational model development (c.f. measure M&O-7).

Task CPT-2-3 Use cases for AI-based assistance *-shared* (DBIS): This task focuses on identifying relevant use cases from NFDI4ING and gathering their specific requirements. It also includes providing interfaces, either via API or prompt access, to the LLM(s) supplied by task CPT-2-2. Initially, a selection of key use cases will be focused on RDMO, JupyterHub, ReSearch Engine, Terminology Service and the Metadata Profile Service. Use cases from the TAs Caden, Alex, and Betty may follow. This ensures the availability of AI-based assistance across NFDI4ING services.

Task CPT-2-4 SIG on AI ready data *-outreach -OneNFDI* (DBIS, ULB): We organise a SIG on Explainable AI ready (XAIR) data. Thus, we will collaborate with internal and external partners and are the central hub within NFDI4ING for the urgent issue of making data reusable beyond just FAIR [104][105]. Furthermore, we put forward all objectives of the Copilot in the work of the NFDI sections. These efforts sustain the SIG “Quality assurance & metrics for FAIR data” and an informal ad-hoc group on LLMs from the 1st funding period.

Measure CPT-3 Assisting Research Software Engineers using AI

We want to provide AI based software engineering tools to the engineering RSE community as a ready to use service to support good coding and architectural practices and focus on the key challenges faced by our researchers. Among these challenges is generating non-Python code (rarely supported by established solutions) for simulations or understanding research software repositories to run the code quickly in order to reproduce state of the art results. This initiative focuses on the existing NFDI4ING RSE tools from the first funding period like Betty’s (Re)Search Engine and the NFDI4ING JupyterHub and extends them with these new and promising tools aiming to increase the FAIR-ness of RSE.

Task CPT-3-1 Identifying and evaluation AI tools (TUC): We identify and evaluate existing AI-based assistance tools and best practices, either developed in the first funding period or arisen in the AI and software engineering community within that period.

Task CPT-3-2 AI-based Research Software Engineering Assistant (TUC): We integrate existing AI-based assistance tools and best practices into a single LLM-based Research Software Engineering Assistant (RSEA).

Task CPT-3-3 (AI-based) support in the NFDI4ING JupyterHub *-shared-OneNFDI* (FoKUS): We give support for high quality code by (1) integrating established software quality tools like linters and formatters, (2) providing best practices of coding tasks and RDM tasks including CIM compatible and quality checked software metadata, (3) connecting the LLM-based RSEA (task CPT-3-2) for auto-completion, code & documentation generation, and quality checks. We will leverage our position in Jupyter4NFDI to ensure the OneNFDI perspective within this task.

Task CPT-3-4 Assisting Research Software Engineers finding Research Software -shared (TUC): We integrate existing NFDI4ING solutions and novel AI approaches into the ReSearch Engine. Further, we provide users with enhanced AI based search, sorting and filtering mechanisms to offer best possible search results, extracted from heterogeneous sources. The ReSearch Engine leverages its position in the newly founded base service nfdi.software [15].

Task CPT-3-5 Outreach -training -outreach (TUC, FoKUS): We develop and maintain a series of short tutorials and documentation for the tools and present those at scientific conferences.

Possible risks of implementation

Among the risks for AI-based assistance are missing input data to refine AI-models leading to an inadequate alignment of a bot's answers. Therefore, it is crucial to identify, create and process high-quality training materials. This is planned through close cooperation with TA TES and all archetype TAs. As the hosting of LLM-based services is quite cost-intensive, it is not possible to offer these services for free. The provision of pre-trained models for self-hosting merely shifts the problem of required cost-intensive GPU resources and expertise to the users. The development of sustainable and acceptable cost models is done in close collaboration with TA M&O.

Competence and expertise

ULB Darmstadt has strong expertise in setting up assistance structures for RDM and in the field of DMP and is a leading partner of the RDMO consortium [106] and the DMP4NFDI base service [14]. It also has experience with harvesting and provision of machine readable, structured literature. The Institute for Software Systems Engineering at TU Clausthal led the development of Betty's ReSearch Engine in NFDI4ING's phase one and has a strong background in software engineering. It also researches using LLM and machine learned models in engineering and is involved in the basic service nfdi.software [15]. DBIS at RWTH Aachen develops knowledge management technologies and participates in NFDI, EXC Internet of Production, and Gaia-X. For over 20 years, DBIS has researched semantic web and linked data and focuses also on LLMs for natural language processing, data analytics, and decision support. FoKUS has strong experience in the curation of data and software sets, in operating a JupyterHub for research incl. being part of the projects Jupyter4NFDI and bwJupyter.

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other task areas

TA CPT is deeply interconnected to all other task areas due to its nature of serving the RDM services and archetype TAs with assistant systems and AI expertise. This is documented by the many shared tasks. The liaison officer at ULB Darmstadt is responsible for coordinating the collaborations.

5.5 Task Area Journal *ing.grid* – FAIR Data Management in Engineering Sciences (J)

Introduction

Although the RDM community in engineering sciences has been growing, a recognised venue for RDM as a subject of research was missing before NFDI4ING started. Simultaneously, possibilities to obtain academic credit for RDM were lacking. To address these issues, the journal *ing.grid* - FAIR Data Management in Engineering Sciences was established in the first funding period. *ing.grid* is an innovative, Diamond Open Access journal. Using open-peer-review, it is a platform for sharing and discussing RDM in the field of engineering sciences. The journal runs on the open-source platform Janeway [107]. *ing.grid* accepts manuscript submissions as well as open access datasets and open source software and is dedicated to the principles of open science. The journal is backed by a strong international editorial board consisting of 19 RDM experts, including pioneers from NFDI4ING and beyond. *ing.grid* actively engages with the community to promote the journal and the consortium at various venues in NFDI4ING [108*][109*][110*][111*][112*][113*], the NFDI [114][115*], and beyond [116*][117*][118][119][120][121][122]. The journal has attracted a large number of authors, reviewers and readers. 22 preprints and eight peer reviewed articles have been published, each with the review discussion transparently available for viewing.

State of the art in research data management

ing.grid is part of a growing movement for accessibility and transparency in scientific publishing, gathering momentum since 2019 [123][124]. While there are journals for publishing research software [125], such as JOSS [126], or datasets [127], *ing.grid* accepts all three types of submissions: manuscript, dataset and software, since all of them are relevant for FAIR data management. Compared to other journals [127], *ing.grid* incorporates the FAIR principles directly in its review guidelines [128]. Unlike the journal *Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement* [129], *ing.grid* has an international outlook. Recognising its contribution to the open access movement, *ing.grid* has been shortlisted among the four best infrastructure initiatives in the Enter-Award 2024 [246].

Key objectives of task area *ing.grid*

OJ-1 The overarching goal for *ing.grid* is to become the internationally leading academic journal for FAIR data management in engineering sciences and related disciplines. This will allow uniting the scientific discussion on RDM on a single platform and facilitate access to the latest developments and state of the art for engineers in academia and industry.

OJ-2 *ing.grid*'s priority is good user experience for all user groups – readers, authors, reviewers and editors. This goes hand-in-hand with the ability to secure the efficient, continuous and reliable operation of the journal.

OJ-3 Good visibility of the published research including preprints, achieved by outreach and by indexing in recognised databases for scientific periodicals. It is crucial to track the journal progress by regularly evaluating relevant metrics.

OJ-4 In order to ensure long term success and sustainability of ing.grid, the journal needs to be established as a legal entity and integrate a sustainable financial model.

OJ-5 Finally, ing.grid aspires to be a FAIR journal. For this purpose, a Journal Knowledge Graph (JKG) is to be developed and implemented as a usable and useful tool for all user groups. To achieve this, in the first funding period ing.grid has already incorporated the package SciKGT_EX [130*] from the former TA Base Services [131]. This cooperation will be further intensified in the scope of the JKG development, with close ties to the tasks SKG-1-1, SKG-1-3, SKG-2-1 and SKG-2-2.

Measures and deliverables

Measure J-1 Efficient, Reliable and Continuous Journal Operation

Task J-1-1: Ensure efficient, routine and continuous publication activity by supervising the publication process through all stages in cooperation with the publisher TUJournals.

Task J-1-2: Evaluate the progress regularly with relevant metrics.

Task J-1-3: Effectuate governance and facilitate decision-making on journal progress in the editorial board meetings. Report on journal performance from Task J-1-2 to the editorial board.

Task J-1-4: Improve journal processes and user experience by keeping up to date with requirements regarding RDM in engineering sciences resulting from the work in NFDI4ING and beyond, as well as by regularly gathering and addressing feedback (e.g., by improving the submission and review guidelines based on input from all task areas.

Task J-1-5: Actively shape the Open Access and Open Science publishing landscape by developing ing.grid further conceptually in step with new developments.

Measure J-2 Community Building and Outreach

Task J-2-1: Participate in relevant conferences and events to establish ing.grid as an active and valuable member of the Open Access and Open Science community. Increase the awareness of ing.grid and the NFDI4ING and encourage engagement in the community review.

Task J-2-2: Drive the discussion on FAIR data management and Open Science forward via relevant information channels. Improve the visibility of ing.grid and the published content, including the results of the NFDI4ING, by these means.

Task J-2-3: Establish ing.grid and the NFDI4ING on the international stage by expanding the ing.grid editorial board through strategic involvement of leading scientists active in RDM from all parts of the world, especially those currently underrepresented.

Task J-2-4: Contribute to the success of NFDI4ING by engaging with all task areas and the embedded liaison officers. Coordinate community engagement and dissemination of NFDI4ING results.

Measure J-3 Compliance with Standards in Scientific Publishing, Acceptability and Visibility

Task J-3-1: Ensure compliance of ing.grid with current standards in scientific publishing defined by recognised databases for scientific journals.

Task J-3-2: Improve visibility of published content and acceptability of ing.grid by indexing the journal in relevant databases for scientific journals.

Measure J-4 Achieving Long-Term Sustainability

Task J-4-1: To strengthen identification with and engagement in ing.grid, collectively select a suitable legal entity for the journal with the involvement of the NFDI4ING steering group.

Task J-4-2: Consolidate ing.grid by constituting it in the form of the legal entity from Task J-4-1.

Task J-4-3 -shared: Ensure sustainability and viable long-term operation by developing a financial model.

Task J-4-4: Ensure journal operation beyond the second funding period of NFDI4ING by securing sufficient funding commitments in accordance with the developed financial model.

Measure J-5 Developing and Implementing a Journal Knowledge Graph (JKG)

Task J-5-1 -shared: Extend and refine the JKG developed in the first funding phase and validate the data model using the existing publications and review discussions.

Task J-5-2 -shared: Implement the triple store and user interfaces and enable the population of the knowledge graph with the journal data by implementing an API on the journal platform.

Task J-5-3: Ensure usability of the JKG by user studies, guides and reference use-cases.

Task J-5-4: Provide the JKG as a service to the community and ensure usability through continuous maintenance.

Possible risks of implementation

The main risk for the implementation of the goals formulated for the task area is that ing.grid does not proceed in gaining acceptance in the community of engineering scientists focused on RDM. This may be due to: (1) low quality of publications, (2) lengthy publication times due to inefficient internal processes, lack of engaged reviewers and editors, (3) limited reach into and awareness of the community, (4) journal directories refuse to index ing.grid, (5) ing.grid falls behind on the current developments in scientific publishing in the direction of Open Science. Each of these constitute a risk in themselves and need to be met with appropriate measures, reflected in the tasks above.

Competence and expertise

ing.grid is backed by a strong editorial board with leading RDM experts. The Editor-in-Chief, Peter F. Pelz, is head of the Chair of Fluid Systems and the Vice President for Digitalisation, Sustainability and Infrastructure of TU Darmstadt. As the deputy speaker of the NFDI4NG, the founding deputy speaker of the NFDI section EduTrain and the co-founder of the DALIA initiative, he is strongly connected in the RDM community. Thomas Stäcker is the director of the University and State Library Darmstadt. From the international editors, Gretchen Greene is the Data Science Group Lead at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in the USA and a technical advisory board member of the RDA. Further editorial board members are Stefan Decker, Bernd Flemisch, Petra Gehring, Ina Heine, Martin Thomas Horsch, Christian Langenbach, Christine Legner, Matthias Müller, Andrea Rapp, Robert H. Schmitt, Irina Sens, Christian Stemmer, Achim Streit, Jörg F. Unger, Satoshi Watanabe, and Dazhuan Wu.

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other task areas

The journal is closely linked to all archetype TAs as a venue for publishing research results and getting feedback from the community through the open peer review process. At the same time, the journal ensures a minimum standard of FAIRness through its guidelines derived from the FAIR principles. Services and tools developed in the archetype TAs can be directly used in ing.grid's workflow (such as SciKGTex package [130*]) or inspire further development. ing.grid will work closely with all task areas and the embedded LOs on community building to maximise impact. ing.grid will coordinate development of the JKG with TA SKG measures SKG-2-1 and SKG-2-2.

5.6 Task Area Alex – Bespoke Experiments

Introduction

“Hello, I’m Alex. I conduct bespoke, one-of-a-kind experiments in custom-tailored hardware or software related to technical systems that range from nano and microscale, e.g., investigation of wall slip [132] or cloud cavitation [133]) to macroscale, e.g., algorithmic planning of fluid systems [134]. I work with experimental setups that are not only bespoke, but also reconfigurable, i.e., can change over time and are often operated by multiple (generations) of scientists. On one hand, my interest is the FAIR analysis of physical phenomena; on the other, it is the FAIR synthesis in systems design and operation. My research fields include process engineering, including physio-chemical processes, mechanical engineering, control engineering, thermo- and fluid dynamics, energy systems and systems engineering.

Thanks to the work of TA Alex, I can make the research objects resulting from each step of my bespoke workflow FAIR. Not only datasets and software, but also my reconfigurable virtual and physical experimental setups and their components can be documented and linked to other research objects in the workflow, using, for example, persistent identifiers (PIDs) and QR codes.

Due to the bespoke nature of my work, I profit greatly from best-practice examples and reference implementations that simultaneously validate solutions developed for individual workflow steps.

I am still looking for convenient solutions to model my complex research workflows and systems end-to-end and to track provenance of my data and calculate KPIs within my systems.”

State of the art in research data management

Despite the challenging, bespoke nature of experimental workflows typical for Alex, the community has increasingly recognised the importance of FAIR RDM practices in recent years and showed an interest in implementing them [134][135*]. Especially concepts and tools for documenting experimental hardware on the component and system scale, e.g., metadata4ing [136*] and RO-Crate [137], but also publishing and linking various research objects to one another, have undergone advancements, e.g., using PlotID [138*], not in the least thanks to the work of NFDI4ING. Moreover, interest in FAIR data management practices is noticeable beyond academia, with a focus on value chains, e.g., Catena-X [139], and sustainability, e.g., ENPRO REUNION [140]. More and more attention has also been paid to competence building and training with regard to RDM on various career levels, e.g., HeFDI Code School [141], NFDI Section EduTrain [5], DALIA [2].

Through intense cooperation and exchange with the community, TA Alex contributed substantially with RDM tools, services, and concepts that are easy to use, fast to implement, modular, reusable and applicable to a wide range of bespoke approaches. TA Alex has introduced a variety of guidelines [142][143*][144*][145*][146*], best practices [134][135*][147*], concepts [148] and reference implementations [149] for creating sustainable, FAIR research objects.

TA Alex has carefully validated the practicability and acceptance of its approaches on suitable practical use-cases, e.g. in system optimization studies with FAIR data linked to diagrams [134][150] and experimental study on a uni-axial servo hydraulic test rig with automated end-to-end uncertainty tracking using PIDs and QR codes for connecting physical and digital objects [135*].

Moreover, Alex has contributed to lowering the threshold for RDM practices with several software tools [138*][147*][151][152][153] that can be applied in different steps of the workflow. For example, *Plot Serializer (PloSe)* [153] allows for machine-readable serialisation of scientific diagrams with the possibility of describing each of the diagram elements with additional metadata. Used together with *plotID* [138*], diagrams can be linked to other research objects like code and data.

Recognising the importance of teaching *data literacy right from the start*, TA Alex actively integrated the developed solutions to teaching in the form of introductory courses with practical

examples (Grundlagen der Digitalisierung [154]) but also as tangible, beginner-friendly science experiments (“Küchentisch” experiments in Praktikum Digitalisierung [155]). The TA Alex co-spokesperson is engaged as deputy speaker NFDI’s EduTrain section and pushing data literacy as participant in the DALIA project.

TA Alex’s deliverables are meant and ready to be integrated into sustainable end-to-end solutions. *Plot Serializer (PloSe)* will be recommended in the author guidelines in NFDI4ING’s journal *ing.grid* (J-1-4) as a tool for making manuscript and data submissions FAIR. Others can be merged with NFDI4ING developments (*m4i*, *DataDesk*, *SciMesh*) to form knowledge graphs documenting comprehensive research processes and to build FDOs.

Finally, TA Alex sees FAIR data as an enabler for transparency, sustainability, science and economy. Building upon the concept of the data powerhouse (*Datenkraftwerk*), it recognises the importance of considering the value of data and of studying economic and environmental aspects related to it.

Objectives of task area Alex

In the second funding period TA Alex aims to scale its solutions to a broader user base reached by activating the engineering community and adapting to a wider range of workflows. TA Alex aims to further standardise its solutions and foster their sustainability by integrating with the newly structured overarching solutions task areas and the other archetype task areas. More specifically Alex plans to:

OA-1: Develop standards for FDOs suitable for the purposes of Alex, building upon existing file formats such as HDF5 and RO-Crates. Standardise *AI-ready* metadata for all its modular solutions based on semantic metadata profiles conforming to the CIM. Integrated all solutions into data storage, curation and enrichment tools of TA SKG, TA FIS, and *ing.grid* guidelines, including an out-of-the-box solution for PID and QR-code generation.

OA-2: Integrate its modular solutions for one-of-a-kind experiments in custom-tailored hardware or software into a knowledge graph to model continuous semantic representations (*Semantic Digital Twin*) of volatile experimental setups and related data processing by validating and extending the CIM and overarching solutions with Alex related SOP.

OA-3: Transfer concepts and tools for continuous semantic modelling to design processes in systems engineering and applications for tracking sustainability and regulatory compliance with industry partners.

OA-4: Disseminate sustainable integrated solutions and activate engineering capabilities and hands-on mindset within the Alex community for RDM by fostering data-literacy and RDM training in engineering curricula with training data and “kitchen science” kits (c.f. above), and support

engineer-to-engineer exchange of experience and own developments with knowledge base and developer support infrastructure.

Measures and deliverables

Measure A-1 FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) and Semantic Metadata Schemas for experimental setups (FST)

This measure is aimed to integrate TA Alex existing modular research-centred workflows based on JSON/Python/HDF5 with enrichment and publication (web) services in TA SKG and TA FIS based on Semantic Metadata Schemas (RDF). These TAs provide further integrations with the Terminology Service (SKG-1-2) and Knowledge Graph (SKG-2-2) and storage solutions, and with technologies such as RO-Crate and ongoing development from other archetypes such as *SciMesh*, *M4I* and *DataDesc*. This includes further development of AI-ready FAIR digital objects (FDO) for bespoke data formats as typical within Alex research area.

Task A-1-1 -shared: Contribute to the development of the NFDI4ING CIM (SKG-1-1) by providing metadata requirements for Alex's specific entities related to dynamic experimental setups, sensor data, simulation software and variables of interest. Validate the CIM ontology and terminology with existing use cases [133][134][135*] and with participants from Alex engineering community and students within the *Praktikum Digitalisierung*.

Task A-1-2 -shared: Update metadata models of existing deliverables (*machine actionable data sheets*, *physical object PIDs*, *SOFIRpy*, *PIA*, *pyKraken*, *PlotSerializer*, *Metadata Crawler*) according to CIM and co-develop semantic metadata schemas (SKG-1-3) for these deliverables adapting existing NFDI4ING ontology related developments (*SciMesh/m4i/DataDesc*) and engineering-focused ontologies (e.g. SSN/SOSA).

Task A-1-3: Extend existing metadata models with standards for FDOs for data from bespoke experiments in files and data silos (e.g. CSV, numpy, HDF5, Time Series Database (TSDB)). Extend metadata schemata from A-1-2 with metadata on data structure and typing including semantic lifting of observed properties and features of interest by integrating engineering ontologies and terminologies (e.g. SSN/SOSA, Unit Ontology, Ontology of units of Measure (OM), QUDT). Validate the results with use-cases from A-1-1.

Task A-1-4 -shared: Integrate software tools and define SOP of deliverables of Task A-1-2 and A-1-3 with Metadata Collection and Instantiation (SKG-2-1) and Interactive Federated Services to Store and Share (FIS-2-2, FIS-2-4, FIS-2-5) to form continuous workflows for Alex related tasks. This includes the development of conversion tools for deliverables of Task A-1-3 to common AI (e.g. CSV with metadata) and publication workflows integrating *PlotSerializer* with *ing.grid* (J-5-1). Solutions such as *Metadata Crawler* will be used as microservices within Metadata Collection and Instantiation (SKG-2-1).

Measure A-2 Semantic Digital Twins (SDT) for experiments and provenance tracking in research processes (FST, RSM, STFS)

The machine actionable transparent description of Alex's data collection and processing chains of reconfigurable one-of-a-kind experiments, mirroring physical and computational setups necessitates linking FDOs and semantic metadata of physical entities, e.g. components, substances etc., and methods from individual steps to allow continuous tracking data provenance and uncertainty, minimise errors, and automate updates when new data is available.

Task A-2-1 -shared: Integrate deliverables of the first funding period (e.g., SciMesh, m4i, [135*]) into SDT for experiments with modular, adjustable structure and the possibility of accounting for Alex-specific software and hardware reconfigurability, i.e. dynamics, as knowledge graphs conforming the CIM. Further development, optimization and validation of metadata models by applying them to best practice examples regarding automated tracking and computation of system uncertainty [135*], or in high-fidelity simulation workflows (TUDa STFS) mirroring experimental setups with sophisticated optical diagnostics (TUDa RSM). Extension of the metadata models to semi- or full-automated documentation during experimental data acquisition, post-processing and data transfer.

Task A-2-2: Provide exemplary use cases checking for missing provenance and metadata including the application of knowledge graph embedding and ML solutions for heuristically screening metadata for errors in collaboration with TA CPT (CPT-1-4).

Task A-2-3 -shared: Contribute use-cases of SDT to the development of visual representation for scientific process chains within TA Ellen's measure E-2-1 and to Metadata Collection and Instantiation (SKG-2-1). Document data access by the scientific community, monitor interaction with the data and support requests to inform upstream improvements in (meta-)data curation and processing. The long-term goal is to assess and ensure the mandatory resources for interoperability and sustainable data usage by the scientific community (TUDa RSM, STFS).

Task A-2-4: Further develop software for creating, maintaining and exploring semantic digital experiment twins' knowledge graphs and assemble out-of-the-box solutions providing workflows, software and hardware (QR code generator/scanner) for Alex research workflows. Integrate and test these solutions in data literacy curriculum ("Praktikum Digitalisierung") and running projects.

Measure A-3 Semantic Digital Twins (SDT) for system engineering (TUDa FST)

Each system design is in the first place a bespoke experiment. FAIR SDT of systems make design processes transparent and reproducible. Financial constraints and social cost can be objectified within these models [156]. SDT allow tracking sustainability and regulatory compliance through the design process.

Task A-3-1 -shared: Apply semantic metadata schemas and SDTs to modelling systems for aggregating KPIs (energy, sustainability and social costs) within design processes. Extend

prototype LEGO car exercise from “Praktikum Digitalisierung” to industrial applications, e.g., lifecycle analysis, “Produktpass”, Catena-X. Link with TA Ellen regarding green building KPI and design processes related to the built environment.

Task A-3-2 -OneNFDI: Explore possibilities to exchange concepts and tools between RDM and industry applications, e.g., machine-actionable datasheets to track conformity to regulations and industry norms as boundary conditions throughout design processes. Develop use cases with industry partners e.g. Merck KGaA, KSB or contributors of the REUNION project [140]. Provide prototypes and define interfaces. Integrate research results on linguistic uncertainty in norms from the cooperation with the NFDI consortium Text+ [156][157].

Task A-3-3 -shared: Formalise semantic requirements and develop guidelines regarding privacy of data and data economics, including data trading and scientific reputation. Develop KPI to track value of data through design and research processes, data curation and publication. Integrate with ing.grid.

Measures A-4: Community activation, hands-on-training and standardisation (Postdoc TUDa FST/Liaison Officer)

This measure bundles the communication demands of the Measures A-1 to A-3 and the activities related to Alex’s community to TES and TA management & outreach.

Task A-4-1 -shared: Actively contribute to the development and operation of the Copilot, a NFDI4ING knowledge base and helpdesk by providing SOPs, guidelines etc.

Task A-4-2 -outreach -training -OneNFDI: Develop and organise hands-on early academic career data literacy training programs based on existing deliverables, including from the “Praktikum Digitalisierung”, unit testing workshops etc., and further developments in Measure A-1 to A-3 as a Roadshow for TU9 and other universities in collaboration with TA M&O (M&O-2), TA TES (TES-1). Link with NFDI section EduTrain and DALIA.

Task A-4-3 -outreach: Contribute and organise community meetings and community board meetings for the thermal engineering and process engineering community (DFG review boards 4.21 and 4.22), and NFDI4ING conferences including a “Data-Opportunity-Workshop” in collaboration with the SIG on “AI ready data” (CPT-2-4), where RDM and AI experts meet, discussing FDO (e.g. tables, HDF5) as basis for machine-actable data solutions and AI-readiness, and fitness criteria of domain specific AI applications.

Task A-4-4 -outreach -OneNFDI: Bootstrap advanced user/developer OSS communities, platforms and hackathons for TA Alex’s software tools and workflows deliverables to foster long term development and networking within Alex’s engineering community. Integrate with SureSoft and nfdi.software.

Possible risks of implementation

Proprietary applications, legacy software and path dependency in general can hinder acceptance and interoperability of TA Alex's deliverables. NFDI4ING prefers openly accessible and open-source solutions (e.g. Python/Gitlab/Jupyter services). These are comprehensive, but proprietary software and file formats (e.g. Matlab) are widely used, provide their own advantages and are not in all cases easy to integrate.

TA Alex understands data literacy, research data management and industry collaboration as ongoing issues for which NFDI4ING can provide an organisational framework and important groundwork, but sustainable success in this field necessitates continuous engagement of research communities and funding bodies.

Competence and expertise

All the contributors and participants are experienced in standardisation work closely related to national and international certification that can be leveraged for the challenging task of unifying research data management for bespoke, one-of-a-kind experiments [158][159]. TU Darmstadt is among the leading universities in thermo-fluids (DFG classification 4.22, c.f. [247]) and contributes to this task area via its institutes FST [160], RSM [161], STFS [162]. They have gained broad expertise in the design of bespoke measurements and simulations based on unified interfaces, data models and modular software in various research domains: Pilot users from the field of thermos-fluids are CRC 1194 [163], CRC/TRR 150 [164], and CRC/TRR 129 [165], while the completed CRC 805 has addressed the DFG classification 4.22 [166].

In addition to being the nominated speaker of the NFDI4ING, jointly with Prof. Dr.-Ing. Robert Schmitt, Prof. Dr.-Ing. Peter F. Pelz (TUDa FST) is the deputy speaker of the NFDI Section EduTrain [5] and an initiator of the DALIA project [2]. He has developed the innovative learning course "Praktikum Digitalisierung" in the Bachelor curriculum in sustainable engineering at TU Darmstadt and is active in the university's RDM Network. In 2023, he was elected the Vice President for Digitalisation, Sustainability and Infrastructure of the TU Darmstadt. Prof. Dr. habil. Andreas Dreizler (TUDa RSM) and Prof. Dr.-Ing. Christian Hasse are speakers of the project Clean Circles [167] and Prof. Dreizler is laureate of the Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz Prize.

TUDa FST will provide the LO to support the training and communication with domain-specific expertise. A network of further Participants – Prof. Dr. Burak Atakan, Uni Duisburg-Essen; Prof. Dr. Andreas Brümmer, TU Dortmund; Univ. Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr.-Ing. Christian Bauer, TU Wien – are engaged in the dissemination and validation of TA Alex's results.

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other task areas

Beside contributing to shared tasks (A-1-1, A-1-2, A-1-4, A-2-1, A-2-3), TA Alex will provide semantic metadata profiles (A-1-2, A-2-1) and solutions for FDOs (A-1-3) applicable not only in Alex's communities. Here, it will contribute to and benefit from common work in the SIG “metadata & ontologies” and the SIG “quality assurance & metrics for FAIR data“, as well as from TA Ellen's work on DataDesc, TA Caden's work on SciMesh, TA Doris' work regarding the HDF5 file format.

TA Alex will engage with TA Ellen regarding FAIR solutions for sustainability KPI in system design and industry integration. It will engage with all TAs in training and jointly addressing the engineering community.

5.7 Task Area Betty – Engineering Research Software

Introduction

“Hello, I'm Betty. Being an engineer and self-taught programmer that develops research software has been exciting during the past five years. Writing code for the analysis and conversion of research data has become easier thanks to tools like Betty's (Re)Search Engine, which allows me to find software relevant to my needs, reducing the necessity of writing every piece of code from scratch. My software typically relies heavily on the operating system and various third-party libraries. Advancements in workflow systems have guided me to design my software in a way that ensures others can replicate my computational results. Moreover, I can use services such as the NFDI4ING JupyterHub to inspect and evaluate results of my fellow researchers. However, benchmarking remains a challenge in our community for accurately assessing the state-of-the-art methods, simulations, and models. It is crucial to reproduce these computational models and simulations swiftly and accurately to minimise each researcher's effort and fully leverage current developments. I believe that others could greatly benefit from the insights I have gained throughout my journey.”

State of the art in research data management

During the past few years, the crucial role of research software in the context of RDM has been recognized by the scientific community and all relevant stakeholders, amounting to, for example, the adaptation of the FAIR Guiding Principles to research software [168] and the explicit role of software in the DFG's Code of Conduct [169]. Regarding NFDI, the working groups Research Software Engineering (RSE) in the NFDI section Common Infrastructures [6] and Research Software Metadata in the NFDI Section (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance [170] have been installed with substantial contributions by NFDI4ING members. Nevertheless, according to [171], “software in science is ubiquitous yet overlooked”.

Tools, services and concepts for achieving the FAIRness of research software and its input/output data have undergone tremendous advancements over the past years. Regarding the engineering

sciences, TA Betty contributed substantially with, for example, the services JupyterHub [79*] and Betty's (Re)Search Engine [76*], the tools fieldcompare [172*] and GridFormat [173*], as well as concepts for increasing the FAIRness of software [174*] and selecting workflow engines [175*]. Nevertheless, the adoption within the engineering sciences can still be considered in need of improvement. Regarding metadata, the Citation File Format [176] has evolved as a de-facto minimal standard for describing software projects. While CodeMeta [177] contains a richer set of terms, it is still discipline-agnostic, whereas EngMeta [39] addresses all data relevant for the engineering sciences and not only research software. Even though verification, validation and benchmarking are considered to be important in computational engineering [178], generally accepted platforms with standardised procedures and supportive tooling (e.g. similar to openML [179] in the ML community) do not exist at the moment.

Objectives of Task Area Betty

The objectives for TA Betty are inspired by the objectives defined for the first funding period and refined according to the lessons learned during the first funding period. Initially, we stated that: *(1) Researchers should be equipped with the tools and knowledge that are necessary to develop validated quality-assured engineering research software and (2) be capable to guarantee the reproducibility or at least the transparency of computational results.* However, developing such software doesn't need to happen from scratch. Finding methods, models and simulations that are (remotely) related to one's own research scenario is just as important as creating research software in such a way that others can find and reproduce it. This task goes beyond metadata as it includes engineering specific environments, workflows, and benchmarks. Moreover, equipping researchers with tools and knowledge means reaching out to engineering communities and promoting the value that comes with good RDM practice and solutions regarding research software. Accordingly, the refined objectives for TA Betty are:

OB-1: Researchers are able to find, access, verify and validate engineering research software, models, simulations, workflows and are provided with metrics, tools and knowledge to develop and maintain high-quality software themselves.

OB-2: All advancements are accessible to a larger community by being integrated into services such as the (Re)Search Engine and the JupyterHub.

OB-3: Communication channels as well as training and outreach activities have been well established and contribute to a sustained constructive dialogue with the engineering communities.

Measures and deliverables

We implement four measures to achieve our objectives described above. In particular, measures B-1 and B-2 target mainly OB-1, while measures B-3 and B-4 relate mostly to OB-2 and OB-3, respectively.

Measure B-1 Verification, validation and benchmarking (BAM, TUBS, TUDa)

In engineering practice, numerically solving partial differential equations is a very prominent research task that is very challenging in the context of verification, validation and benchmarking (VVB). VVB – particularly the benchmarking of simulation software - ensures that mathematical models are accurately solved, that the equations model the right physics based on a comparison with real-world experimental data, and that consistent results are achieved across different simulation codes. This is essential for integrating these tools into industrial applications or standards. VVB necessitates interoperable and interpretable data formats, as it requires collaboration with scientists from various disciplines and compatibility with other software.

Task B-1-1 *-shared*: Use the developed data structures in CIM to represent experimental and simulation data exchanged in verification, validation and benchmarking.

Task B-1-2: Develop a tool-independent data structure for the definition of initial and boundary value problems (IBVP) to be simulated in verification, validation and benchmarking.

Task B-1-3: Implement converters for transforming the benchmark problem into specific inputs for a set of software tools, such as e.g. ANSYS/LS-Dyna, FEniCSx and Abaqus.

Task B-1-4: Define and implement a set of benchmarks comprising varying combinations of model setups, constitutive models and experimental or analytical results.

Task B-1-5 *-shared*: Develop guidelines for data curation as a basis for a process to incorporate external data and models into the platform (developed in B-2). Develop a reward system encouraging external contributions, e.g. using granular authorship acknowledgements.

Task B-1-6: Define metrics for verification and validation of numerical results with analytical and experimental data and implement them in a software agnostic framework published on GitHub.

Task B-1-7 *-OneNFDI*: Cooperate on the level of Base4NFDI on a joint metadata scheme for structuring benchmark data, workflows for executing benchmarking applications, foster an exchange between the editorial boards for the curation and organise joint workshops. Direct synergies with the MaRDI benchmarking activities are already identified, with the goal to establish a broader Base4NFDI community.

Measure B-2 Concept for the execution of verification, validation, and benchmarking workflows (TUBS, BAM, TUDa)

Based on the Continuous Integration (CI) and virtualization approaches (Docker) developed in the first project phase, the concept will be applied to workflows for automating verification, validation and benchmarking workflows ensuring reproducibility of VVB results. The approach is extended to incorporate computationally expensive benchmarks with large-scale data resolution by automating the distributed execution of VVB workflows on 3rd party systems as well as HPC environments. The solution will be tailored to specifically facilitate the VVB workflows developed in B-1 and integrated into the JupyterHub infrastructure to be accessible by any researcher.

Task B-2-1: Integrate the toolchain developed in B-1 in a platform with a workflow and the option to integrate new software solutions (B-1-3 for a new tool), new benchmark problems (define a new problem with the tools in B-1-2) or new data (B-1-1).

Task B-2-2: Extend the workflow for use with HPC systems based on, e.g., HPC-Rocket and guix. If necessary, extend these solutions for use with various scheduling systems which are commonly used in HPC environments (Slurm, PBS, etc.).

Task B-2-3: In collaboration with TA Doris, develop a virtualization solution based on Docker or Apptainer to reduce system specific dependencies and allow for generality, c.f. Task D-6-1.

Task B-2-4: Evaluate the possibility of connecting external (third party) systems accessible via SSH to be integrated into specific benchmarking workflows (using, e.g., HPC-Rocket and guix).

Task B-2-5: Document the steps required to upload new data and models into the platform and advertise the framework in the community.

Task B-2-6 -shared: Integrate the postprocessing of the benchmarking results and visualise the relevant metrics within a Jupyter notebook.

Measure B-3 Use cases for integration of services (US, BAM, TUDa)

Betty's (Re)Search Engine and the JupyterHub are two prime examples for services that emerged from the first funding period of archetype Betty. Going forward, these two services are participating in TA FIS to provide a central point of entry for finding research software and creating engineering specific runtime environments. They both will participate in TA CPT for leveraging existing NFDI4ING solutions and novel AI solutions. Moreover, Betty's (Re)Search Engine will play a central role in the newly accepted nfdi.software base service and the NFDI4ING JupyterHub will be connected to the Jupyter4NFDI base service. This development offers potential for collaboration and integration within engineering communities and beyond. Moreover, these two established services, together with the Chatbot/LLM initiative in TA CPT, offer a platform which could host the results of archetype TA Betty in the second funding period, reinforcing the service mindset. In Measure B-3 we plan to:

Task B-3-1 -shared: Collaborate with the (Re)Search Engine to find datasets suited for benchmarking in the sense that they have already been invoked or have the potential to be used in the framework developed in Measure B-2.

Task B-3-2: Collaborate with the JupyterHub to provide computational environments for comparing the performance and results of different solvers and integrate the results from B-3-1 and B-3-2 into a consistent workflow and provide (or reuse) examples for educational and outreach efforts.

Task B-3-3 -OneNFDI: Identify and evaluate use cases for combining the (Re)Search Engine and the JupyterHub with respect to nfdi.software and Jupyter4Nfdi. Collaborate with nfdi.software to implement the identified use cases.

Task B-3-4 -shared: Define relevant information and terminology for engineering research software for the CIM and provide engineering research software as knowledge graph entries in form of FDOs.

Task B-3-5 -shared: Collaborate with TA CPT to identify relevant information from measures B-1 and B-2 to empower an LLM based search for research software models, scenarios, data, workflows and benchmarking. Leverage the educational and outreach materials provided in measure B-4, to create a distinguished prompt access/chatbot ("Prof. Betty") for delivering educational materials on demand and make it widely available.

Measure B-4 Education and outreach (US, BAM, TUBS, TUDa)

During the first period, training materials concerning research software development have been compiled by all partners involved in task area Betty and used at their respective local institutions as well as in overarching events such as workshops offered as part of the NFDI4ING community meetings. Within this measure, we will further optimise these materials and develop new ones related to appropriate aspects of B-1 to B-3. By closely collaborating with TA TES, we will ensure that the materials are accessible from our central point of contact and become machine-readable. Together with the employed tools and services, the developed training materials will be used at various outreach activities, ranging from NFDI4ING roadshows to Betty-specific workshops.

Task B-4-1 -training: Design a course “FAIR verification and validation of engineering research software” based on material developed during the first period and for the new measures B-1 and B-2.

Task B-4-2 -training: Implement the course in different variations such as a block course for doctoral researchers or a semester course for master students at selected NFDI4ING co-applicant and participating institutions.

Task B-4-3 -outreach: Based on the course material and the procedures established in Measures B-1 and B-2, design and offer workshops on “validate your fluid/solid mechanics simulator” to reach out to the simulation science community.

Task B-4-4 -OneNFDI -outreach: Continue and intensify our engagement in NFDI-wide, national and international initiatives such as the WG RSE of the NFDI section Common Infrastructures, de-RSE e.V., the FG RSE of the German Informatics Society (GI), and the Research Software Alliance (ReSA).

Possible risks of implementation

Risk	Mitigation
Developed solutions not easily generalizable to other benchmark problems	Early interaction with the community and other NFDI initiatives for an early interaction with stakeholders

Community not actively participating in developing the platform	Platform design to create granular references to individual contributions for creating incentives
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Competence and expertise

Task area Betty is headed by co-spokespersons B. Flemisch (US), J. Linxweiler (TUBS) and J. F. Unger (BAM); complementary expertise is added by T. Maric (TUDa) and O. Lünsdorf (DLR). This team formed during the first funding period and is the result of a successful integration of Betty's pilot use cases and users as well as the work undertaken in the SIG on workflow tools and its accompanying seed fund project. A. Seeland (US) and V. Seibert (TUC) contributed substantially to Betty's success during the first period via NFDI4ING's JupyterHub and Betty's (Re)search Engine, which will both be continued and expanded in TAs FIS and CPT in the second period. Betty's team has ample experience in all aspects of computational engineering and RSE, particularly on the topic of verification, validation and benchmarking of simulation software. Its members are contributing substantially to several cross-cutting software-related activities within NFDI sections, working groups, basic services and beyond the NFDI.

Several co-spokespersons of research alliances engage as participants to continue and initiate strong collaborations with TA Betty: S. Fasoulas (CRC 1667, US), S. Langer (TRR 364, TUBS), S. Staab (EXC 2075, US), H. Steeb (CRC 1313, US) and D. Weiskopf (EXC 2120, US). Their contributions will nucleate in Measures B-1 and B-2 and ensure that Betty's solutions will be applicable to contemporary complex use cases from many different parts of the engineering sciences.

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other task areas

Through the (Re)Search Engine and the JupyterHub TA Betty is closely connected to the TAs FIS and CPT. By integrating the results from TA Betty into the (Re)Search Engine and the JupyterHub, we contribute to the overarching effort of the consortium. Moreover, by having colleagues sitting on both sides of the table, the archetype task area stays up to date with ongoing efforts and developments. This allows us to adjust our measures and priorities according to the consortium dynamics and, through our outreach activities implemented in Measures B-3 and B-4, we will be able to feed community needs back into the consortium. Further synergies are expected from collaborating with TA Doris, particularly on virtualization solutions in Tasks B-2-3 and D-6-1.

The LO will be responsible for being involved in the (Re)Search Engine and the JupyterHub and the individual measures defined in TA Betty. The LO will act as an oversight instance that identifies collaboration opportunities within and beyond the consortium.

5.8 Task Area Caden – Provenance Tracking of Samples and Data

Introduction

“Hello, I’m Caden. I’m an engineer whose research deals with complex sequences of processing and analysing steps, applied to samples and/or data sets. My professional background is mostly informed by materials science, process engineering, and technical chemistry. For me, the output of one processing step is the input of a subsequent one. For instance, I synthesise an alloy sample, temper, and etch it. After that, I analyse the sample in various measurement setups, creating data sets. My scientific workflows consisting of samples, data sets, and processing steps can be fully represented by knowledge graphs.”

Key objectives of TA Caden

OC-1: Ensure increased competence in sharing and publishing of complete scientific workflows in the engineering community, in particular using TA Caden’s toolset.

OC-2: Build a sustainable community around SciMesh and its various implementations to foster its future dissemination and development.

OC-3: Provide a standard set of re-usable vocabularies for maximum interoperability when sharing knowledge graphs, harmonised within the NFDI.

OC-4: Define a method to publish both knowledge graphs and raw data in one global namespace, i.e. without fragmentation over multiple repositories.

OC-5: Enable automated publishing of quality-controlled, reusable workflow graphs.

State of the art in research data management

During the first funding period of NFDI4ING, we have observed three strong trends that are relevant for TA Caden: (1) Electronic lab notebooks (ELNs) have gained much momentum and have proven to be an effective entry point into RDM for institutes and scientific work groups. (2) Knowledge graphs have become more and more popular, albeit especially for linking aggregating entities like publications [180][181]. Still, some emergent technologies [66][182] address similar use cases as SciMesh (a set of specifications that define the representation of scientific results in the form of a knowledge graph) [47*] and might be combined with it. (3) While metadata has dominated RDM so far, *raw* research data receives strongly increasing attention due to its importance for AI training. However, landing pages and large data transfers often make reuse a cumbersome manual work.

Measures and deliverables

Measure C-1 – Education and outreach

While TA Caden implemented working prototypes of services and protocols in the first funding period, these need to be communicated and refined in collaboration with the community on a

broad basis. We approach the community actively through different channels and in different formats. This is in alignment with NFDI4ING's concept to appoint a LO in each task area to strengthen the positive effect of NFDI4ING's services in the community.

Task C-1-1 Presentation at events -outreach -training (all): Presentation of TA Caden's services at conferences, meetups, and workshops in order to make the services known in the engineering community as a whole. A focus is laid on the best-practice handbook (a user-oriented RDM guide) that is created during the first funding period. Both the handbook per se but also its content should be presented, because the latter will form the basis for instructional hands-on workshops.

Task C-1-2 Feeding the best-practice handbook into TA CPT -shared (FZJ-IMD2): By reviewing the content of our handbook, we convert it into comprehensive context for the assisting tools created in TA Copilot. This way, all RDM best practice and tooling knowledge collected in the first funding period are available not only in book form but also in replies of a chatbot or an LLM-based search engine.

Task C-1-3 Community building for SciMesh [47*] -outreach (FZJ-ZB): By commitment of TA Caden's partners, a basal permanent maintenance of SciMesh and its associated services is ensured. In addition to that, this task aims at establishing a sustainable community for SciMesh by bringing the number of people who actively work on corrections and extensions above the critical mass. By continually advocating development of SciMesh itself at meetings and on social media, volunteers are attracted to the project. This is supported by deploying infrastructure around SciMesh that makes collaborative work a pleasant and effective experience.

Measure C-2 – Compilation of a standardised vocabulary for knowledge graphs

SciMesh at its core is a mid-level ontology. Therefore, practical use for the consumer of SciMesh graphs (ELNs, indexing machines, graph visualisers, etc) is greatly enhanced by including further existing vocabularies.

Task C-2-1 Inclusion of existing vocabularies -OneNFDI (all): Re-use of existing vocabularies for the domains of timestamps, chemical formulae, units of measurement, physical dimensions, people, institutions, grants, methods, experimental setups, and further concepts that are generic enough to make them eligible to become part of SciMesh's core. By using the TIB Terminology Service [183*], candidates for such vocabularies are identified, which then pass a thorough review with respect to their technological soundness and maturity, useful scope, and degree of adoption. This task collaborates with other ontology endeavours within the NFDI and is aligned with existing technologies such as RO-Crate.

Task C-2-2 Addition of domain-specific vocabularies -OneNFDI (all): With focus on scientific engineering, existing vocabularies are added to SciMesh which enable the presentation of scientific workflows as knowledge graphs that represent a specific engineering discipline. Again,

this has to be harmonised with other NFDI consortia because there, such vocabularies have been defined already for at least the material sciences [66].

Task C-2-3 Definition of compliance levels (FZJ-ZB): By acknowledging the difficulty to implement all of SciMesh’s vocabulary, this task prioritises them by significance and generality, and groups them into compliance levels.

Measure C-3 – Embedding of data science workflows into knowledge graphs

This measure is the result of adaptation of TA Caden’s efforts to the increasing need for raw data in the scientific community, not exclusively but to a large part as training material for AI applications. The engineering sciences profit greatly from these novel approaches of data science. Therefore, TA Caden enriches its knowledge graphs with raw data processing as well as the raw data itself. Moreover, TA Caden eases the publication of such data as well as lowers the threshold to re-use it for new science, helping to close the data cycle.

Task C-3-1 Add AiiDA (Automated workflows for computational science) [184] – or a subset thereof – to SciMesh (FZJ-ZB, KIT-INT): In the first funding period, TA Caden has been evaluating ontologies with related goals to SciMesh. For data-only, AiiDA was chosen as the best candidate, given its maturity and widespread adoption. The SciMesh implementations JuliaBase, elabFTW, and Kadi4Mat are updated to be able to visualise AiiDA graph nodes.

Task C-3-2 Define a way to link to raw data (FZJ-ZB): Enable linking to raw data from SciMesh nodes so that consumers of SciMesh (e.g. importing ELNs) are able to visualise the data. This includes a list of allowed schemas in raw data URIs as well as additional graph nodes that give hints how the data can be used as input for calculations, simulations, and visualisations. For the latter, TA Caden will consider techniques like signposting [185] or RDF-star [186].

Task C-3-3 Deploy production grade distributed hubs for exchanging large data (FZJ-ZB, KIT-INT): Deployment of at least two IPFS (InterPlanetary File System) [187] servers, where each of them exposes scientific research data stored in a data repository. The data encompasses only material that is to be published, and both its raw data and metadata, organised in SciMesh graphs. TA Caden will make use of the intrinsic distributed nature of IPFS that allows to download large quantities of data from multiple sites at the same time. Moreover, traversal through the knowledge graphs is possible using the IPFS-related technology IPLD [188], which TA Caden will extend with a so-called “Advanced Data Layout” [189] for RO-Crates.

Task C-3-4 Enable working with data and sample knowledge graphs in Project Jupyter (FZJ-ZB): Offer a bridge between SciMesh graphs available by URLs and Jupyter Notebooks or JupyterLab [190] by providing additions to the Jupyter ecosystem that enable the user to search for graph nodes with certain properties and accessing raw and meta data for further processing in JupyterLab. Thus, this task complements the previous task by closing the data cycle from publishing data to re-using it comfortably.

Measure C-4 – Intrinsic data quality control in research data management using AI

Scientists need quality control in their RDM workflows. If an ELN instance has been filled with sufficient scientific data over time, then this knowledge can serve machine learning algorithms as reference to decide whether newly added data is “plausible”. TA Caden leverages its direct influence on the development of the ELN solutions JuliaBase [191] and Kadi4Mat [19*] as well as its close collaboration with eLabFTW [192] to implement the necessary algorithms and hyperparameters for data quality control.

Task C-4-1 (FZJ-IMD2): Identify at least three different use cases (experiments) suitable for data collection and analysis, and collect a sufficient amount of data within eLabFTW, Kadi4Mat and JuliaBase that can serve as first training data.

Task C-4-2 (FZJ-IMD2): Code and implement ML algorithms in the ELNs Juliabase and eLabFTW using the Python libraries Scikit-learn [193] and Auto-Sklearn [194] (already implemented in Kadi4Mat).

Task C-4-3 (FZJ-IMD2): Define criteria for data evaluation and comparison of different kinds of experimental data, e.g., x-ray diffraction, electron microscopy, Raman spectroscopy, and others.

Task C-4-4 (FZJ-IMD2): Perform the necessary ML processing steps (preprocessing, classification, training, testing, prediction) to carry out an initial assessment of the quality of the available data. Carry out further statistical tests to identify so-called outliers in the initial training data.

Task C-4-5 (FZJ-IMD2): Adding new measurement data in order to be able to assess the precision, accuracy and completeness of new measurement data on the basis of what has been learned. Compare the results of all three ELNs.

Possible risks of implementation

Main risks are due to complexity and external dependencies of the planned measures. This affects first and foremost measure C-3, as an IPFS deployment consists of many components that have to interact seamlessly with each other. Moreover, it needs to be connected with an institutional repository, which is unprecedented so far. Similar risks exist for the connection with Project Jupyter, as new software is necessary.

TA Caden’s work programme contains some standardisation efforts, which are notoriously threatened by difficulties to agree upon a final recommendation. Furthermore, the community building for SciMesh might not reach the critical mass necessary to expect a sustainable maintenance of SciMesh and its associated technologies. While the general interest in RDM topics grows dramatically currently, this might not be sufficient.

Competence and expertise

TA Caden consists of three NFDI4ING members, the Central Library at the Research Centre Jülich (FZJ-ZB), the Institute of Energy Materials & Devices, division “Materials Synthesis and Manufacturing Processes” IMD-2, also at Jülich (FZJ-IMD2), and the Institute of Microstructure Modelling and Simulation at the KIT (KIT-INT). FZJ and KIT share the lead of TA Caden.

FZJ-ZB has been responsible for central RDM services for Jülich since 2016, and has designed, implemented, and operated the institutional repository Jülich DATA and many training and counselling services for the local scientific community. FZJ-ZB employs one core developer of Dataverse as well as the inventor of the sample database framework JuliaBase.

FZJ-IMD2: The Institute of Energy Materials & Devices of Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, division “Materials Synthesis and Manufacturing Processes” (IMD-2) focuses on materials research into energy materials of the future, which includes the necessary process technologies, e.g. for the production of high-performance ceramics. IMD-2 serves as a pilot project to test and further develop RDM procedures in a wide range of areas, particularly in the fields of ELNs, data analysis, and the application of AI in materials research and process engineering.

KIT-INT has a strong background in material science and software engineering over the last 20 years. In recent years RSE and RDM has become a major topic. The combination of workflows, data management, data science and machine learning in the ecosystem of Kadi4Mat has been shown to be a community relevant tool set.

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other task areas

The first focal points for synergies are the compilation of sets of vocabularies. Here, TA Caden works closely together with TA Alex and TA SKG. The latter provides significant competence in the design of ontologies and vocabularies, and it offers services that help managing them. TA Caden contributes criteria for the selected vocabularies.

The second focal point is the connection with the Project Jupyter. TA Caden does not have experience with Jupyter’s APIs. Therefore, the development happens together with TA Betty, TA FIS, and TA CPT.

Measure C-4 complements the content of the new TA CPT. The latter focuses primarily on formal data quality, whereas TA Caden's C-4 is explicitly dedicated to intrinsic data quality (precision, accuracy and completeness of experimental data). Both TAs will offer a shared service as part of the Copilot.

5.9 Task Area Doris – High Performance Measurement and Computation

Introduction

“Hello, I’m Doris, an engineer conducting and post-processing high-resolution and high-performance measurements and simulations on High-Performance Computing systems (HPC). For me, large, immobile data is the main challenge in RDM. I require standardised research-data management principles to enable the reuse of these huge data sets through FDOs. I will adapt these to the high-performance workflows for multi-physics and multi-scale simulations increasingly using ML/AI-methods either during production or post-processing phases of the projects. I am facing the challenge on large tier-1 and tier-2 HPC-facilities that data sizes often exceed the storage capacities of the user’s local storage capabilities, making them non-transferable in their original state. And my measurements in these engineering topics have become time and spatially highly resolved such that measurement data meet the same challenge due to their sheer size in post-processing or applying ML/AI methodologies. The value to my fellow colleagues in engineering can be increased manifold enabling access to the data which have been generated at great expense at the site where the data is generated ('user to data' concept).”

The focus of the proposed activities in TA Doris is the technical implementation of data access on HPC centres taking into account the local security, hardware- and software architecture and access models. Additionally, TA Doris will offer support, guidance, workshops, and community outreach on practical solutions and best-practice guidelines, embedding RDM procedures across various user groups and workflows in the engineering community. This follows the 'knowledge to user' approach.

TA Doris creates the foundation for FAIR data management and publication in HPMC (high-performance measurements and computations) for these resource-intensive data.

State of the art in research data management

RDM on large-scale computing systems is in a stage where individual researchers and groups generate (FAIR) data locally, post-process the data into a condensed form and publish the scientific results partly associating them with persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI), that is, condensed data that was used to generate the graphs in the publications. The huge raw data generally cannot be published and made available for reuse with computing capabilities on the same platform due to their sheer size exceeding common repositories and it would be of no use as most other researchers do not have the resources to locally process the overwhelming amount of data after a lengthy download in the PB range and beyond. This creates a hampering bottleneck in the effective and widespread reuse of HPMC data. The workflow on the individual HPC platforms is largely unique to individual research groups due to the complexity of the simulations and often

conducted using self-developed software [252][253-259]. Software version control is commonly used. Access models, individual libraries, etc. are individual to different centres [276][277][278]. In short, RDM methods are applied but access to the data once found is a bottleneck to make RDM-tools effective for HPMC-data re-use. Within associations of German HPC centres in various functional or geographical scopes (e.g. GCS, NHR, bwHPC), the development of unified methods for RDM in HPC has begun. Through the strong overlap of HPC-centre staff with co-applicants and participants active in TA Doris, the task area will be aligned with these efforts.

Objectives of TA Doris

The first main objective is to establish standardised and transferable approaches that enhance the efficiency of FAIR research data management for our target group enhancing interdisciplinary research and the use of ML/AI on HPMC data [260][261-275]. To achieve the goals of 'user to data', a common user interface for the complex workflows based on the Kadi4Mat framework (open-source dashboard service, mostly web-based) will be provided as a front-end guidance through individual access models, tools and libraries, security measures and usage models differing from one HPC centre to another. This allows for more flexibility and usability on varying platforms. A general and hardware independent dashboard service enables users to remotely control the access and processing of large HPMC data by applying user-specific algorithms and workflows on the HPC systems and to transfer the results to the local workstation systems. The framework will support standardised generation of data on HPC systems with openly accessible format descriptions of the data. This feature is specifically for users who generate data on HPC systems and is therefore developed in close cooperation with the NHR network and the Gauss Alliance and communicated to the user community. Furthermore, showcase routines for reading and searching characteristic features, parameters and properties within the big HPMC data on HPC systems are developed and optimised algorithms enabling a problem- and domain-specific access to the large volumes of data are provided. Access to the data including processing capabilities at the location where the raw data is stored is of central importance to TA Doris. TA Doris contributes to the communication between the different German HPC associations on general methods for RDM in HPC and will help to realise specialised solutions for the field of engineering.

TA Doris contributes to standardised metadata definitions (e.g., metadata4ing) and terminologies as well as the automated collection of structured metadata (e.g., metadata crawler HOMER), improving the findability and interoperability of HPMC data. In order to foster the interoperability and reusability of HPMC data, TA Doris is dedicated to the evaluation of containerization of HPMC workflows. One of the key issues of RDM and quality of data, the 'reproducibility' of large-scale HPMC results, is still an open issue as containerization generally does not reach the performance to reproduce the data on the HPC systems in acceptable time frames. The general harmonisation

of RDM workflows at the German tier-1 computing centres is enhanced via collaboration with initiatives such as GCS or InHPC-DE and hand-in-hand with the NHR tier-2 centres. Together with its partners, TA Doris offers various formats of knowledge transfer with different target groups. To advance the 'user to data' strategy, programming interfaces for comprehensive analysis and further processing of the data on the HPC systems are to be generated enabling the connection of user-specific visualisation methods, advanced data analysis including AI/ML as well as the application of user-specific analysis workflows.

Disseminating the knowledge in the form of methods, processes and solutions to the engineering community will be the second main objective 'knowledge to user' of Doris. Methods such as protocols, compression, interfaces, caching will support the transfer of knowledge gained from data workflows on the HPC systems to the local computer systems of the respective user. In interviews, the aspect of fast adaption of the methodologies to the individual tools and workflows of the individual researchers is stated as the single-most hurdle to apply potential solutions. Regular workshops with hands-on training, dissemination and enhancement of (individual) training materials, the provision of entire courses and RDM for Bachelor and Master curricula will spread the knowledge, tools, and services in the respective HPMC-community. The creation of the LO position will bundle all the information and expertise available to a single point of entry to RDM on HPC centres and TA Doris' procedures and knowledge. The LO will also support the individual engineers in adapting the potential solutions to the needs of the researchers.

Thus, TA Doris contributes to the following key objectives of the 2nd funding period as outlined by the NFDI expert committee in [4] (NFDI objectives a-g):

- Advance the system and integration readiness level of previously designed concepts and tools (a, b, d),
- establish processes and workflows as well as metadata standards in the engineering HPMC community (a, b, d),
- harmonisation of these solutions in between HPC centres (e),
- due to the participation of HPC centres and scientific libraries in European initiatives and networks (e.g. RDA, PRACE), Doris represents potential for Europe-wide outreach and fulfilment (e),
- the re-use of existing large data sets will be enabled through FAIR data management, while sovereignty, integrity and security of data will further be strengthened (f, g)

Measures and deliverables

Measure D-1 Accessibility and access rights, data security and sovereignty (TUM, HLRS, JSC, LRZ)

D-1-1 -OneNFDI: Enabling the publication of (large HPMC) data and metadata in university, NHR and GCS repositories and derive a generic, transferable solution by aligning with the outcomes of TAs SKG and FIS.

D-1-2 -outreach: Establish and disseminate new access and user models at HPC centres to access and reuse very large data sets, maintaining data security and sovereignty.

D-1-3 -OneNFDI -outreach: Front-end operation to publish, access and re-use large HPMC data.

D-1-4: Transfer of showcases and proof of concepts to partners and external institutions (e.g. NHR Alliance, JSC).

Measure D-2 Provision of a dashboard service (web-based) to support FAIR HPC usage (KIT)

D-2-1 -outreach: Concept and technical realisation of a dashboard service taking into account user requirements.

D-2-2 -outreach: Setup and implementation of an operating workflow for remote execution with a common interface.

D-2-3 -outreach: Integration of methods for data generation, data search and data processing.

Measure D-3 Support for third-party users & community-based training (TUM, KIT)

D-3-1 -training -outreach: Community-based training in biannual workshops disseminating the developed tools and services to our peer group.

D-3-2 -training -outreach: Support 3rd-party users to effectively use the developed tools and services and therefore to apply the FAIR principles on very large HPMC data sets.

D-3-3 -training -outreach: Expansion of our target group and outreach to users of international as well as national HPC centres (tier 2 and below).

Measure D-4 Metadata definitions & terminologies, support to data-generating groups (TUM, HLRS, LRZ, KIT)

D-4-1 -shared: Establish and disseminate terminologies for (HPMC) methods and embedding in established schemas, harmonisation with NFDIxCS, MaRDI, NHR centres; contribution to the shared tasks CIM and MPI of TA SKG.

D-4-2 -OneNFDI -outreach -shared: Transfer of developed standards to other user groups / consortia creating large data on HPC systems (e.g. NHR, PUNCH4NFDI, NFDI4Earth).

D-4-3 -shared: Standardised metadata schemas (Metadata4Ing) to enable the publication and search of application-specific HPMC datasets; contribution to the shared task MPI of TA SKG.

D-4-4 -outreach: Establish and disseminate best-practice guidelines among the target group (inside and outside of NFDI4ING).

Measure D-5 Storage & archive for very large data (TUM, HLRS, JSC, LRZ)

D-5-1: Increase the number of institutional showcases and proofs of concept for long-term archiving solutions for non-transferable data (data & metadata) making use of searchable and indexable front ends (in coordination with TA FIS).

Measure D-6 Reproducibility on large-scale high-performance systems (TUM, HLRS, JSC, LRZ)

D-6-1: Establish and disseminate standards and best-practice guidelines, as well as use of containers (in collaboration with TA Betty, Task B-2-3) for increased reproducibility on HPC systems.

D-6-2 -OneNFDI -outreach: Expansion of use cases and best-practice examples to other user groups creating large data on HPC systems (e.g. PUNCH4NFDI, NFDI4Earth).

Measure D-7 ‘Data to user’ concept: Interfaces for Data search, analysis and processing (KIT)

D-7-1 -OneNFDI -outreach: A framework of routines and libraries to support standard-compliant data generation on HPC systems with openly accessible format descriptions, developed in collaboration with the NHR Association and the Gauss Alliance.

D-7-2: Routines for reading and searching characteristic features and properties within large HPC data for engineering research users, providing optimised, domain-specific access.

D-7-3 -outreach: Interfaces for comprehensive evaluation and further processing of data on HPC systems, enabling user-specific visualisation, advanced data analysis, and custom analysis workflows.

Measure D-8 ‘Knowledge to user’ concept: Protocols, caching, compression (KIT)

D-8-1 -OneNFDI: Methods such as protocols, compression, interfaces, and caching will transfer insights and knowledge from HPC system analysis workflows to users' local computers. These applications can be used by data producers and subsequent users within the research community as part of OneNFDI.

Possible risks of implementation

Achieving these goals depends on third-party compatibility, such as infrastructure operators and institutional or political decisions at HPC centres including technical feasibility across HPC centres, institutions, and repositories.

Competence and expertise

The task area Doris is led by co-spokespersons C. Stemmer (TUM) and B. Nestler (KIT), both with a long-standing HPC experience and record. The Gauss Computing Center partners HLRS, LRZ and JSC as well as NHR members form the group of participants in TA Doris. Doris will provide a LO as contact and support person to the engineers in need for RDM-support for HPC applications. The integration of TA Doris' and NFDI4ING's outcomes into curricula and graduate

school qualification programs as well as into HPC user workshops is an ongoing process in which several outcomes have already been achieved.

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other task areas

TA Doris collaborates continuously with task areas Betty and Alex as well as all overarching solutions task areas, TA M&O and the Base4NFDI consortium on fulfilling its tasks and measures. As software and experiments are the base for HPC data generation, TA Doris contributes to addressing related NFDI objectives. One particular example is the common focus on virtualization solutions, c.f. tasks B-2-3 and D-6-1.

We will publish our new methods, services and datasets in the journal *ing.grid*. Our training & teaching activities will be embedded in the structure of TA TES. Our metadata definitions and terminologies are developed in cooperation with the TA SKG. Together with the TA FIS, we will harmonize the technical infrastructure of the participants and improve storage, transfer systems and access models. As our target group uses AI and ML methods regularly, we are interacting intensively with TA CPT.

The LO aims at deepening collaboration with industry stakeholders (software producers like ANSYS, or large-scale users like AIRBUS) and other consortia to enhance the development and integration of RDM tools and systems. The outreach efforts will focus on increasing visibility and mutual recognition within our target community, ensuring that we are both known by and familiar with the community. The LO will provide guidance and support for users at HPC centres, helping them utilize adequate RDM tools and systems effectively. It is essential for the LO to understand the differences in RDM conditions and tools at associated HPC centres to better address diverse needs and challenges to facilitate consistency and interoperability across the centres.

5.10 Task Area Ellen – Heterogeneous Data Requirements

Introduction

"Hello, I'm Ellen. I'm an engineer who analyses complex systems comprising a large set of multidisciplinary interdependencies. Working within the computational and building sciences, I conduct research by performing model-based simulations and optimisation calculations, whereby I often utilise algorithms coming from statistics and computer science. Inputs to my analyses are the scenarios I investigate or the vast spectrum of heterogenous data from the built environment, covering all aspects of the built and virtual infrastructure. This data often stems from fragmented and heterogenous sources of a wide spectrum of engineering disciplines. They typically are very data-intensive, requiring information from many different disciplines and also include field data from public institutions. My professional background is typically based in civil, electrical, chemical or energy systems engineering and is often complemented by several aspects of computer science, physics, social science and economics."

TA Ellen supports the reuse of research software and data by focusing on its interoperability and integration in addition to its findability. We assist scientists in meeting their data requirements. In doing so, we go beyond simply finding existing datasets by providing methodological knowledge and research software implementations that yield the desired data.

State of the art in research data management

Finding research software that helps researchers to meet their heterogeneous data requirements and integrates seamlessly into existing software workflows remains a major challenge [195]. Currently widespread software metadata schemas, such as CodeMeta [177], only capture the purpose or intended use of software very superficially in the form of non-standardized categories and keywords, which makes it difficult to search for software tools that can be used for specific research tasks. At the same time, they neglect the detailed technical descriptions of interfaces that are important for the integration and subsequent use of the software [196]. In response to these problems, modifications of the FAIR guiding principles [197] were recently adopted [168][198]. However, the question of how these guidelines can be practically implemented in day-to-day research has not yet been conclusively clarified [199].

As part of the first funding period, TA Ellen developed DataDesc [200*], a metadata standard that can describe data models in software interfaces and data sets, and SciKGTEx [130*] to enrich text documents with structured and machine-actionable information, which can be transferred to the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) [180] via semantic templates. The new ORKG Ask Service [201] provides the engineering community with a powerful tool for extracting this information from huge volumes of literature in a structured way using Question Answering.

A field of research that typically necessitates the analysis of complex systems in multidisciplinary teams is the built environment. TA Ellen's community in this field has been addressed by NFDI4ING's Community Cluster 45 during the first funding period, but also by the FID BAUdigital and in close trans-consortial collaboration with NFDI4Objects and NFDI4Culture, DFG SPP Hundert plus [202], CRC/TRR 339 [203] and supported by the large body of work in Construction [204] and Architecture [205] Informatics communities fostering necessary digitalization in the built environment. To foster RDM regarding the built environment as a cross-cutting issue in TA Ellen's community, the team of the archetype is joined by Prof. Jakob Beetz (RWTH).

Objectives of task area Ellen

OE-1: Formalize knowledge about research tasks and methods as independent research data artifacts to make it more accessible and reusable to cover heterogeneous data requirements.

OE-2: Utilize knowledge of research tasks and methods to organize research software and data according to their possible uses and make them findable according to individual objectives.

OE-3: Mapping technical information via data model metadata within software interfaces and datasets in a machine-actionable way to visually and automatically integrate software and data artefacts into customized executable research workflows.

OE-4: Introduction of research software workflows as FDOs for sustainable reuse in the engineering sciences.

OE-5: Provision of training and learning resources on the reuse and integration of software and data resources to cover heterogeneous information and data requirements.

OE-6: Extend outreach to TA Ellen's communities in architecture, civil engineering, urban and regional planning and foster trans-consortial topics regarding RDM related to the built environment and coordinate community outreach with other NFDI consortia.

Measures and deliverables

Measure E-1 Formalising and collecting technical and methodological knowledge (FZJ, TIB, RWTH)

In this first measure, the metadata standards developed in TA Ellen for describing technical and methodological information will be standardised and made usable by existing metadata and annotation services. In addition to the manual collection of metadata, the automated collection of methodological knowledge is focused.

Task E-1-1 Standardising and providing technical and methodological metadata schemas

-shared -OneNFDI: Contributing DataDesc and SciKGTEx semantics to the development of the NFDI4ING Common Information Model (task SKG-1-1). Implementing DataDesc terminology as a permanently referenceable web resource within the Terminology Service (task SKG-1-2) and providing a semantic metadata schema within the Metadata Profile Service (SKG-1-3, shared task *MPI*). Integration of DataDesc semantics in the NFDI Metadata Section.

Task E-1-2 Integrating technical and methodological metadata into metadata collection and instantiation services

-shared: Integrating DataDesc's and SciKGTEx's annotation and parsing functionalities with metadata collection and instantiation services and NFDI4ING's knowledge graph and the sustainable creation of FDOs (task SKG-2-1).

Task E-1-3 Extracting methodological knowledge from engineering literature:

Providing a service for extracting mentions of software, datasets and research tasks from scientific articles and linking them to automatically capture conceptual methodological processes. The service will be based on LLMs and be applied to a large collection of machine-processable engineering literature (task CPT-2-1).

Measure E-2 Compiling technical and methodological knowledge to executable software workflows (RWTH, FZJ)

The second measure aims to integrate software and data into executable research workflows that researchers can use to cover their individual information and data requirements. A graphical

service is offered in which the individual components are linked by means of modular and reusable data transformation steps.

Task E-2-1 Advancing DataDesc to a graphical software workflow design service: Merging DataDesc's metadata schema and functionality for software and data integration with a flow-based programming platform (e.g. Apache NIFI) to provide a community driven repository of reusable and extendable data transformation workflows with a graphical web service for the design and automation of modular research software and data workflows.

Task E-2-2 Designing workflows as FAIR digital objects *-shared -OneNFDI*: In order to close the knowledge cycle, metadata on new methods and software process chains are organized as a separate research data artifact type in accordance with the CIM and transferred to NFDI4ING's knowledge graph for sustainable reuse (task SKG-1-1, task SKG-1-3, task SKG-2-2).

Measure E-3 Utilizing technical and methodological knowledge for research data organisation and exploration (FZJ, TIB)

The methodological knowledge, formalized in the form of conceptual task and process descriptions, is used in this measure to support organization and search and discovery services. Research data are linked by semantic metadata to the research tasks for which they can be used, enabling its task- and problem-oriented discovery.

Task E-3-1 Organising research data within the federated data space based on technical and methodological metadata *-shared -OneNFDI*: Transferring the semantic metadata collected in measure E-1 to the NFDI4ING knowledge graph and relate them to each other in the context of technical and methodological information forming an organisational structure for concept-related research data categorisation (SKG-2-2). Indexing software workflows from measure E-2 as FDOs within the NFDI4ING Data Catalog (FIS-1-2).

Task E-3-2 Extending the NFDI4ING ReSearch Engine with exploration functions based on technical and methodological metadata *-shared -OneNFDI*: Utilising the links between research software and data and the conceptual tasks and methods they support or implement for task-related search methods and integrating these into the ReSearch Engine (FIS-1-1).

Measure E-4 Education and outreach (RWTH, FZJ, TIB):

The focus of this fourth measure is communication with the engineering community. By building new and expanding existing networks, a dialog is maintained that aims to support scientists in their research data-related challenges and to overcome these through the services and best practices provided by TA Ellen and NFDI4ING.

Task E-4-1 Community building and networking *-outreach*: Outreach to public stakeholder actors in the built environment for reusable, secure low/no-code research data provision workflows. NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Objects and NFDI4ING are involved in a trans-consortial working

group on research data relating to the built environment. The aim is the coordinated development of data and metadata standards, authority control and standard procedures, as well as the networking of infrastructures and community work. This includes multidisciplinary and trans-consortial use cases.

Task E-4-2 Community support including onboarding, training and best practice dissemination *-training*: Enhance outreach and training to TA Ellen's community in built environment research in collaboration with AdvanceAEC network, GACCE, Städtetag, BAST, Bahn AG, stakeholders from research, industry and public sector. Adopt Datatalks and Open Structures conference series, promote INGEST as part of Metadata Collection and Instantiation (SKG-2-1). Continuously disseminating best practices and services in community events and implementing webinars and training materials, including a roadshow for TU9 and other universities. Further establishing SciKGT_eX functionality in journals and conferences.

Possible risks of implementation

The embedding of technical and methodological knowledge as well-defined scientific concepts into the research data infrastructure will fully exploit its potential, if the schemas, best practices and services of TA Ellen have been harmonised with those of the overarching solutions and archetype TAs. Until this is achieved, the services, schemas and other resources can be published and provided with the resources of FZJ, RWTH and TIB.

Competence and expertise

The Jülich Systems Analysis Institute (ICE-2, formerly IEK-3) of the Jülich Research Center (FZJ) develops models and strategies for sustainable energy supply, utilizing large sets of heterogeneous data. The ICE-2 cooperates nationally and internationally [206][207][208][209] and publishes research data largely as open-source [210][211]. RDM is advanced in research projects like LOD-GEOSS [212], H2Atlas-Africa [213] and the Open Energy Ontology [214].

For two decades, RWTH has been working in the field of knowledge engineering and interoperability in the built environment and the digital long term archival (EU FP 7 DURAARK) spanning civil engineering, architecture and urban planning. RDM expertise was built up during pioneering work on linked data integrations (EU FP 6 Intelligrid), collaborative engineering model versioning (bimserver.org), infrastructure data model interoperability (okstraOWL), legacy data integration or brown field building stock (EU H2020 Bim4Ren), and digital twins of vulnerable critical infrastructure (BMVI TwinGen, DFG SPP HundertPlus). A long history on standardization for domain-specific data models and protocols on DIN, CEN, ISO, VDI and buildingSMART levels in the field further contribute to the expertise. Long-standing active (board-)memberships in important scientific bodies (CIB W78, ECPPM, EG-ICE, GACCE, AK:AI, EC3, FID BauDigital) allows a significant extension of the NFDI4ING user community.

The TIB represents and operates a national research infrastructure facility for the provision of scientific information. TIB organises information, data and knowledge and provides digital services like ORKG [180], AV-Portal [215], Leibniz Data Manager [216] or ORKG Ask [201]. TIB has outstanding expertise in managing and preserving knowledge, with a focus on the development of vocabularies and ontologies. As such, TIB performs research aiming to advance information, data and knowledge sharing and to facilitate the digitalisation of science and industry [217].

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other task areas

TA Ellen has developed semantic metadata schemas and structures both in the area of describing software interfaces and data models and in the formalization of scientific tasks and workflows. In the second funding phase, these will be incorporated into the work of TA SKG, which will play a coordinating role in the further development of the Common Information Model, the Terminology Service and the Metadata Profile Service across all Archetypes of the consortium. While TA Ellen's tools for the manual collection of metadata will be integrated with TA SKG's services, the use of large language models for the extraction of engineering knowledge will be carried out in cooperation with TA CPT. The integration and use of the semantic metadata provided by TA Ellen can complement TA FIS in the organization and retrieval of research data by making the possible uses of data and software formally tangible and interpretable by machines. Finally, TA Ellen's LO will work closely with TA M&O and TA TES regarding educational and outreach activities.

5.11 Task Area Fiona – Many Participants and Simultaneous Devices

Introduction:

“Hello, I’m Fiona. I’m an engineer who is leveraging existing data. When reusing an existing dataset, I have to check for content-wise, quality, technical, and legal aspects. Beyond this, I enrich data by combining datasets from multiple sources, which introduces new challenges at the same time. Next to my knowledge about data re-use and data combination, my tool is a web-based platform where I can get this done. I provide this enriched data to other users as well as machines. My mission summarized in one sentence: Provisioning, reusing, and combining data from distributed sources and heterogeneous types by and for different stakeholders.”

The archetype Fiona addresses data sharers and re-users alike by enabling them to share their FAIR and quality-assured data, combine it with existing data, and enrich it for analysis with methods of statistics as well as artificial intelligence. The focus of Fiona is the sharing and re-use phase of the data life cycle, utilizing the increasing amounts of available FAIR data to close data cycles and make data not only re-usable, but actually re-used, thus improving sustainability.

During first funding period, the TAs Frank and Golo both worked on concepts and solutions for RDM on distributed and field data respectively. TA Frank collected requirements of researchers towards RDM and their daily work [218*][219*]. Golo's Field Database Platform (FDP) [222*], developed on the concept of a Digital Twin (DT) model, provides a foundational legacy for the work of TA Fiona and the implementation of a data mesh approach in the second round of NFDI4ING. RDM processes as a concept will be utilised to tailor TA Fiona's results further to its community's demands [220*][221*]. The infrastructure and rich metadata established in TA Golo, along with the developed DT framework, will be used in the RDM process in TA Fiona. Its extensive experience across the entire data lifecycle – specifically in field data collection and analysis, quality assurance, and data reusability – will help address future challenges for TA Fiona.

Going beyond the FAIRification of engineering data in NFDI4ING's first funding period, TA Fiona now emphasizes the FAIR sharing and re-use of data. Specific examples from engineering include the enrichment and provisioning of distributed data in a manufacturing context, the combination of material and process data, or field data with related weather data.

State of the art in research data management

The idea of combining data from multiple sources has been used for several decades in industry, starting with central (business) data warehouses. With the emergence of Industry 4.0, Internet of Things (IoT) and DT concepts [223][224][225], this idea is gaining more and more traction. However, the current practice in RDM in engineering is mainly characterized by researchers planning their own experiments with individual data collection instead of reusing existing data. In this context, DTs have gained considerable attention in recent years due to their pivotal role in modelling complex engineering systems and their capability to enhance RDM and data FAIRness [226*][227*][228*][197][229][230]. Moreover, the actual implementation of such frameworks enables the utilization of the state-of-the-art ML/AI approaches (e.g., [231][232][233][234][235]). Nonetheless, analysis and processing of the wide spectrum of the obtained heterogeneous data poses considerable challenges that still need to be addressed.

The “Data Mesh” concept has been introduced in 2019 in two blog posts [236][237] and a book [238] for the analysis of heterogeneous data. The basic idea is to decentralize data management in order to adapt to heterogeneous data sources and data characteristics while enabling standardisation and interoperability. Microservice architecture is applied to data management. Four principles have been defined: (1) Data remain in their decentralised domains (domain-driven ownership, DDO), are treated as quality-assured data products (2), provided under computational federated governance (FG) (3), on (4) a self-serve platform (SSP). The approach is practically motivated, and experiences are mainly gained in industry as well as in scientific contributions.

Stored datasets are categorized using advanced tools and techniques, and rich metadata [239*][240*] for proper accessibility.

Objectives of TA Fiona

Aligned with NFDI4ING's overarching goals, TA Fiona focuses on supporting both data providers and (re)users of heterogeneous and field data. TA Fiona's objectives are:

OF-1 Streamline data provisioning and data reuse: Adapting data mesh as operational concept for RDM in the engineering sciences. Achieving interoperability this way is key enabler for the next objective.

OF-2 Support data integration (combination) from multiple datasets: Combining data from multiple sources provides the benefit of enriching data. The focus is on heterogeneous and distributed data and data sources in the engineering sciences. A guideline will help researchers on how to proceed and how to avoid common mistakes.

OF-3 Platform provisioning: To make the objectives OF-1 and OF-2 practically applicable, we will enhance and provide a respective platform.

Beyond these subject-specific objectives, training and dissemination is another focus. TA Fiona contributes to NFDI4ING's key objectives through sustainable and scalable solutions, standardisation, provisioning common infrastructure, and communicating and collaborating with researchers and RDM initiatives. All objectives will be addressed by the measures and the tasks below.

Measures and deliverables

To achieve the intended objectives of TA Fiona, the work program is structured into five measures.

Measure F-1 Practical guidelines for data integration (WZL, IPT, IoP, DLR)

Based on previous work, we have hands-on knowledge on the sharing and reuse of data, especially in the context of combining existing data sets with each other to enhance their value. On this basis, we create a guideline for data integration focussed on applicability.

Task F-1-1 Requirement analysis: Analysing the requirements for data integration in the various engineering sciences will include status quo and information on the usage of data types and formats, data characteristics as well as policies need further investigation.

Task F-1-2 Conceptualisation -OneNFDI: Collected requirements for data integration can be combined with RDM concepts and best practices. The result is a guideline for data integration. This guideline encompasses a process, and challenges like missing data, inconsistent granularity of data or data privacy are addressed. Alongside, the leveraging of metadata is promoted to facilitate the FAIR connectivity of data sources.

Task F-1-3 Validation: The created guideline will then be validated in collaboration with researchers and their use cases. The EXC IoP's position is especially relevant in this context, as they not only are experts on large scale data management with heterogenous data sources, but also provide a vast amount of different use cases for TA Fiona.

Measure F-2 Data Mesh to RDM adaption concept (WZL, IPT, TUB, DLR)

While measure F-1 is focused on the conceptional introduction of data integration, measure F-2 is leveraging and adapting the (industrial) concept of “Data Mesh” for RDM along the principles.

Task F-2-1 Domain definition: Domains and their boundaries within the engineering sciences need to be defined more granularly. This might be according to research institutes, engineering subject areas, type of data, or other criteria, and may encompass source-aligned data (e.g., raw data), aggregated data (e.g., analysed research data), and/or consumer-aligned data (e.g., data publications).

Task F-2-2 Data product definition: Datasets will be provided as so-called data products, with data reusers as ‘customers’ in mind. For such a data product, criteria and key elements must be defined. This can include documentation, quality indicators, and technical access (input/output ports), among others. For this, we will leverage FDOs.

Task F-2-3 Federated Governance definition: Although data is provided decentralised in data meshes, the governance is federated. This enables standards and interoperability top-down, while leaving domains local autonomy to decide. Core elements of FG will be defined, including licensing and metadata schemata. In contrast to the industrial data mesh, data sharing is not only inter-, but also intra-organisational within RDM. A close collaboration with NFDI section ELSA will be established for data ownership and trading.

Task F-2-4 Self-Serve Platform conceptualisation: To enable data access and data democratisation, the industrial data mesh concept suggests a self-serve platform, that allows access to data as well as other data management processes. This includes the creation of ‘combined data products’, which are data products made of data from multiple sources (F-1).

Measure F-3 Extending the Field Database Platform (FDP) through Data Mesh Integration (LUH, WZL)

In F-3 the capabilities of the FDP will be extended by integrating data mesh principles developed in F-2, aiming to deliver a sustainable operational model for heterogeneous data management.

Task F-3-1 Designing the Infrastructure for Data Mesh Integration within the FDP: This task will focus on refining the existing concepts of digital master, digital shadow, and DT and developing an infrastructure for extending the FDP capabilities to integrate the data mesh principles, resulting in the Data Mesh FDP (DM-FDP, *working title*).

Task F-3-2 Integrating the Data Mesh Concepts into the FDP Operations: (R)DM processes (onboarding of new datasets, updating existing datasets, and archiving outdated data) will be established. Additionally, mechanisms for DDO (role-based access controls) and FG (each domain can configure its governance policies) will be set up. A form of data catalog is established as entry point for users.

Task F-3-3 Validating the FDP and Integrating User Feedback: The upgraded platform will be deployed among selected users from NFDI4ING and the broader engineering sciences community. This deployment aims at collecting practical insights and validating the new features. Feedback channels, such as chatbots, contact forms, and surveys, will be established to gather user experiences and suggestions for ongoing refinements.

Measure F-4 Enhancing DT Concepts through Data Mesh Integration (LUH, TUB)

Task F-4-1 Refining and FAIRifying DT Frameworks through Data Mesh: Building upon F-3, this task focuses on introducing stakeholders to the enhanced DT concepts that now integrate data mesh principles. The primary goal is to adapt the digital shadows of distributed systems in such a manner that they can leverage data mesh capabilities. We aim to showcase how traditional digital shadows can be transformed to support data interoperability, scalability, and management. This will ensure that the DM-FDP does more than just meet the existing requirements of RDM; it will set a new benchmark for the use of DT technologies in research.

Measure F-5 Training, dissemination, and continuation of the results (WZL, LUH, IPT, TUB)

Task F-5-1 Dissemination -outreach: We will present and disseminate the developed concepts (F-1, F-2) within NFDI4ING formats (e.g. conference, community meetings, talks, roadshows, webinars), NFDI, and beyond. For the DM-FDP (F-3) we will provide respective training materials, including practical use cases specifically for the engineering sciences. While the concepts will be stabilised in the form of publications, the DM-FDP will require continued governance; therefore, we aim to establish it in a wider scope of community or NFDI respectively.

Task F-5-2: University teaching -training -shared: We will integrate RDM practices – particularly on data provisioning, reuse, and combination – into educational curricula through courses (LUH: “Lecture: Data Management and Analytics”, RWTH: “Research methodology and research data management”).

Possible risks of implementation

The data mesh approach leveraged in F-2 and F-3 is a relatively new approach, which introduces a degree of uncertainty to design and implementation. However, this gets mitigated by industry experience with data mesh, as well as by the individual well-known foundational components like microservice architecture. Integrating data mesh principles into the FDP in F-3 introduces complexities due to diverse data structures and metadata. Adopting a microservices architecture

will be utilised to address this issue with independent and modular components. To ensure relevance and long-term sustainability of the results, our LO will closely collaborate with Fiona's community, collect their feedback, and enhance our work. Onboarding (F-4) and combination (F-1) of datasets can touch on legal issues, e.g., regarding personal data. These aspects will be covered by explicitly focusing on ELSA aspects in F-1-1 (data integration concept) and F-2-3 (federated governance).

Competence and expertise

With WZL of RWTH Aachen University, IPeG of LUH Hannover, IIT of TU Berlin, the Fraunhofer IPT, the EXC IoP, and the DLR, we form an interdisciplinary team from the engineering sciences. All partners have been working on NFDI4ING since 2019. The WZL will provide the LO for the task area. Since Fiona's vision is to leverage the re-use of existing datasets, the connection to other data producers in engineering is crucial. The LO will hence manage and foster connections to other TAs as well as external partners and user groups. As TA Fiona supports researchers in combining and reusing data, the LO will also answer related questions, e. g., via the NFDI4ING helpdesk. Simultaneously, this will help us get deeper insights into researchers' challenges.

We consider the skill of re-using as well as combining data as central for data-driven research. The guidelines developed in measure F-1 are transformed into a training module. In contrast to a guideline, the training module will include additional exercises and checks on the learning progress. Combined with a didactic concept, this can be provided as a university lecture as well.

Additionally, the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence (dfki) will participate in Fiona by continuing their support in the development of the FDP by providing their expertise and practical experience with mobile robots and robotic subsystems in several different robotics domains (i.a., terrestrial, underwater, health), containing the interdisciplinary and decentralised management of data and metadata.

Synergies and demarcations with regard to other task areas

As all other NFDI4ING archetypes, Fiona represents a distinct research and data-generation methodology. However, 'real' researchers usually are less focussed and connect with multiple of our archetypes. The closest content-wise connection of TA Fiona is TA Ellen, because of heterogeneous data requirements and data sources. The data product definition from F-2-1 can be aligned with the work in TA SKG as well as the standardisation aspect in TA TES. Fiona's 'tool', the DM-FDP from F-3, is a form of infrastructure and covers aspects of (federated) data spaces, so a connection will be made to TA FIS. Beyond NFDI4ING, NFDI4DS, NFDIxCS, NFDI4Earth and NFDI FAIRagro work with data of similar characteristics (esp. field data), and common practices apply independently from the topic of the data considered. For data provisioning and reuse, we will also take into consideration data trusteeship, on which a strong

collaboration with the NFDI section ELSA (Ethical, Social and Legal Aspects) will be formed. For trainings on the guidelines and on the data platform (F-5) we will get in close contact with TA TES.

TA Fiona's LO will establish and conduct the systematic exchange with the partners mentioned above as well as new partners identified in future. Goals are to leverage synergies by avoiding redundant work; to promote solutions and harmonise them with partners; and to identify potential use cases from sciences as well as industry for collecting impulses, exchange of experiences, and validation. This covers NFDI4ING, NFDI, and beyond.

The upcoming NFDI4ING funding period will focus on 10 key objectives (c.f. chapter 2.2), which TA Fiona will contribute to. With the requirement analysis in F-1-1 we will foster the understanding of our community (1). The DM-FDP (F-2, F-3) with data products and automated governance execution will contribute to the standardization of RDM processes (3). Data product definitions (F-2-1) support adherence to the FAIR principles (5). Provisioning, re-use and combination of datasets (data products) will close data cycles of research data (4). Making data lineage comprehensive (F-1, F-2-1) in data reuse supports the scientific reputation of the dataset creator (7). We contribute to long-term RDM (10) not only with the developed guidelines (F-1), but with the DM-FDP (F-3) as well. Insights from our work will be transferred to NFDI as well (9).

5.12 Task Area Management & Outreach

Introduction

As outlined in chapter 3.4, our internal evaluation at the beginning of 2024 has led to a number of adjustments for the second funding period. They include an adjustment to organising and managing our community engagement and overall outreach, resulting in an increased number of measures for the management team as compared to the first funding period. The increased number of measures will require more resources, which will be allocated to the task area.

In continuation of the first funding period, the management team will be based at two locations: TU Darmstadt (applicant institution) and RWTH Aachen (co-applicant institution). This arrangement leverages the unique perspectives of both institutions and accommodates diverse working structures. Embracing diverse working structures is crucial to account for the consortium's multi-institutional composition. The team of TA M&O (the "administrative office") emphasises and fosters a sense of shared responsibility for NFDI4ING as a whole.

Objectives of TA Management & Outreach

OM&O-1: NFDI4ING is perceived as a hub for services and advice for RDM in engineering sciences. The mindset "we are a service provider for the community" is widespread in the consortium, reaching all engineering communities. We actively advertise our counselling service in the engineering research community. We have a central contact point for support and advice

(i.e. helpdesk) where we provide 1st level support. We have established processes for the transfer and continuous support of clients to 2nd and 3rd level support providers (i.e. in the archetypes or local/regional initiatives).

OM&O-2: NFDI4ING is increasingly visible as a consortium. A majority of all people affiliated with and adjacent to engineering research are aware of NFDI4ING. We actively support the cultural change towards awareness and professionalisation of RDM in engineering research. We have strong ties to local and regional initiatives outside the NFDI (i.e. data stewards at our partner/participant institutions, “Landesinitiativen” like HeFDI, FDM.NRW). We are connected to and in dialogue with new or additional target audiences (industry, politics, prof. associations, citizen science projects).

OM&O-3: The consortium constitutes an entity with a coherent design and identity. All members of the consortium actively support and identify with the consortium by using branded materials whenever appropriate. We have a guideline for publishing results generated in the consortium as outcomes of the consortium (i.e. acknowledgement and branding). We have templates for presentations, posters, information materials, banners, VC backgrounds, etc.

OM&O-4: NFDI4ING supports the community in developing innovative solutions to new or unexpected problems. We continue the NFDI4ING Seed Fund programme and actively disseminate their results. We promote community solutions by continuing and improving the visibility and impact of the NFDI4ING award for the best RDM solution that has not been developed in the context of our consortium (c.f. chapter 3.1). We connect to other actors in the field of innovation promotion (e.g., incubators at our participant institutions) and make them aware of our efforts.

OM&O-5: NFDI4ING provides a reliable financial administration and disbursement of funds, including the disbursement of funds for Base4NFDI.

OM&O-6: NFDI4ING develops and implements successful service operation and business models. These will allow the consortium to scale up all its services and to serve all researchers in engineering in Germany. The models will be designed to sustain the well-used services regardless of the NFDI funding in the future (c.f. chapter 3.5).

Measures and deliverables

Measure M&O-1 Outreach and community engagement

Task M&O-1-1 -outreach: The administrative office provides support and coordination for event planning and management, e.g. for the archetypical community events (c.f. chapter 3.1) and the NFDI4ING conference.

Task M&O-1-2 -outreach: The administrative office coordinates the NFDI4ING helpdesk/ticketing system and Q2A-platform.

Task M&O-1-3 -outreach: The administrative office prepares, disseminates and analyses surveys of the community.

Task M&O-1-4 -outreach: The administrative office supervises NFDI4ING's seed fund programme and the NFDI4ING award (c.f. chapter 3.1).

Measure M&O-2 Science communication, public relations, and marketing

Task M&O-2-1 -outreach: The administrative office supervises the content plan and strategy for primarily one-way formats such as the website, social media, and newsletter.

Task M&O-2-2 -outreach: The administrative office supervises the design, production, and dissemination of marketing materials such as flyers and leaflets.

Task M-&O2-3 -outreach: The administrative office connects with multipliers on the local (i.e., data stewards), regional (i.e., Landesinitiativen), national (i.e., Rfll) and international level (i.e., RDA, EOSC) with the goal of making the work of NFDI4ING visible.

Task M&O-2-4 -outreach: The administrative office keeps track of the scientific disciplines represented in the consortium and connects with the members of the various community boards established in the first funding round.

Measure M&O-3 Internal communication, corporate identity and design

Task M&O-3-1: The administrative office oversees guidelines and workflows for publications, presentations, social media campaigns, roadshows, and more.

Task M&O-3-2: The administrative office maintains and disseminates templates for presentations, posters, information materials, banners, video call (VC) backgrounds, and more.

Task M&O-3-3: The administrative office runs and maintains centralised communication resources, such as a SharePoint, mailing lists, and chats.

Task M&O-3-4: The administrative office coordinates on- and offboarding events.

Task M&O-3-5: The administrative office coordinates regular meetings of the LOs.

Task M&O-3-6: The administrative office coordinates the annual all-hands meetings ("Gesamtteamtreffen").

Task M&O-3-7: The administrative office oversees NFDI4ING's internal meeting structure and escalation and conflict resolution processes.

Task M&O-3-8 The administrative office coordinates all major board meetings (c.f. chapter 3.4), sets up the agendas, and ensures that the minutes are kept.

Measure M&O-4 Interaction with other initiatives and the NFDI bodies

Task M&O-4-1 -OneNFDI: The administrative office supports, reviews, and keeps track of NFDI4ING's collaborations with other consortia, the NFDI bodies, and Base4NFDI.

Task M&O-4-2: The administrative office supports, reviews, and keeps track of NFDI4ING's collaborations with actors outside the NFDI, including actors outside of Germany.

Measure M&O-5 FAIR reporting, transparency, and quality management

Task M&O-5-1: The administrative office implements a KPI database that adheres to FAIR principles and supports reporting via the DFG datasheet.

Task M&O-5-2: The administrative office maintains a publicly available service portfolio for NFDI4ING.

Task M&O-5-3: The administrative office continues to track and review work results. The administrative office continues to make the metadata of publications publicly available as a collection.

Task M&O-5-4: The administrative office continues to implement feedback loops from collected findings, such as surveys and event evaluations.

Measure M&O-6 Financial administration and disbursement of funds

Task M&O-6-1: The administrative office continues to perform an overall monitoring and control of finances. It reports the financial figures to the executive committee, on the one hand, and to the DFG, on the other hand.

Task M&O-6-2: The administrative office continues to coordinate the conclusion of funding agreements. Decisions regarding the disbursement of seed funds follow agreed-upon procedure that is detailed in NFDI4ING's by-laws ("Ordnung"). Both the seed fund proposals and the decisions leading to disbursement or non-disbursement are documented and made available for external review.

Task M&O-6-3: NFDI4ING's management continues to ensure the correct handling and administration of all material expenses. This includes expenses related to traveling, purchasing, and organising events. Decisions regarding the disbursement follow agreed-upon procedure that is detailed in NFDI4ING's by-laws ("Ordnung").

Measure M&O-7: Development and implementation of successful service operation and business models

Task M&O-7-1 -shared -OneNFDI: The administrative office develops service operation and business models in close collaboration with NFDI4ING's task areas and the co-applicant institutions as the actual providers of the services as well as with the NFDI directorate (c.f. chapter 3.5). Sustainable and non-bureaucratic solutions which do not burden the researchers themselves, but their respective home institutions are in focus.

Task M&O-7-2 -shared -OneNFDI: The administrative office coordinates the implementation and evaluation of the developed service operation and business models (c.f. chapter 3.5). This includes the assessment of legal implications and the assistance with financial administration, if needed. Wherever possible, we will rely on or be inspired by existing legal structures, e.g. the DFN association or the RDM networks of the German federal states.

6 Additional Aspects

6.1 Equal opportunity and diversity

Gender and diversity management is independently handled by institutions within NFDI4ING, and each institution is committed to promoting diversity through specific guidelines, resources, and initiatives. Some of the NFDI4ING co-applicant institutions such as RWTH and FZJ have received the 2023 Total E-Quality Award [241], and even more NFDI4ING co-applicant institutions have received this prestigious award in previous years [242]. NFDI4ING sees a unique opportunity at hand to explore innovative strategies and leverage the collective expertise of its diverse partners. We strongly encourage our personnel to take part in the respective measures and programs offered by the institutions.

NFDI4ING's executive committee (c.f. chapter 3.4) regularly addresses the state of gender and diversity management and supports a yearly collection of internal data on gender, citizenship, and career stage. The consortium has maintained a stable representation of female employees, with women comprising approximately one quarter of the NFDI4ING workforce. Additionally, in-kind contributions by female employees were higher, totalling 30.6% in 2022 and 33.9% in 2021. Comparatively, the proportion of women who completed final examinations in engineering sciences in Germany in 2022 was 25.9% [243], and the proportion of female engineering scientists at German universities in 2022 was 23.1% [244]. This indicates that the NFDI4ING workforce reflects, if not slightly surpasses, the national level of female representation in engineering.

In 2022, 26,9 % of the NFDI4ING workforce did not hold German citizenship, indicating a diverse international presence. It is because of this international presence that events within NFDI4ING are regularly conducted in English. To address age hierarchy and encourage the open exchange of ideas and experiences, NFDI4ING has actively implemented innovative, accessible formats such as fishbowl talks and online after-lunch meetings (NFDI4ING Collaboration Coffee - CoCo). At the time of writing, a formal code of conduct to be observed at our events is being developed and will be implemented in the remaining time of the first funding period. Moving forward, we will further leverage diverse practices to create an inclusive environment where all members feel valued and empowered to contribute to our research data management community.

Appendix

The appendix may only include the following information and documents:

9 Bibliography and list of references

Sources marked with * are results of the consortium and contain an acknowledgement complete with project number 442146713.

- [1] G.W. Jagusch, N. Preuß, Umfragedaten zu “NFDI4Ing - Rückmeldung aus den Forschungscommunities,” (2019). <https://doi.org/10.25534/TUDATALIB-104>.
- [2] Akademie der Wissenschaften und der Literatur Mainz, DALIA Datenkompetenz von Anfang an, (n.d.). <https://dalia.education/> (accessed September 27, 2023).
- [3] Konsortialversammlung Des Vereins Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) E.V., Stellungnahme der NFDI-Konsortien zu Basisdiensten, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6091656>.
- [4] NFDI Expert Committee, Key points for the second funding period of the NFDI consortia, (2023). <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/204398/dfab28aa8bb3f2864cec55fb49370e93/eckpunkte-zweite-foerderphase-en-data.pdf>.
- [5] S. Herres-Pawlis, P. Pelz, N. Kockmann, R. Gläser, M. Richter, J. Liermann, J. Ortmeyer, I. Heine, A. Metzmacher, A.-C. Andres, A. Münzmay, J.-O. Heuer, M. Hagener, J. Dierkes, C. Wiljes, B. Lindstädt, R. Danabalan, J.D. Jolliffe, Sektionskonzept Training & Education zur Einrichtung einer Sektion im Verein Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V., (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6475541>.
- [6] M. Hammitzsch, C. Busse, B. Flemisch, K. Förstner, T. Kalman, F. Löffler, M. Politze, D. Riehle, Concept for Setting up a Working Group Research Software Engineering in the NFDI Section Common Infrastructures, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6483449>.
- [7] M. Diepenbroek, S. Schimmler, B. Ebert, Sektionskonzept Common Infrastructures zur Einrichtung einer Sektion im Verein Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V., (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5607489>.
- [8] F. Stahl, A. Hamann, Sektionskonzept Industry Engagement zur Einrichtung einer Sektion im Verein Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V., (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7900079>.

- [9] L. Bernard, R. Altenhöner, F. Böhm, M. Diepenbroek, B. Ebert, J. Fluck, S. Herres-Pawlis, A. Klinger, O. Koepler, S. Lorenz, B. Mathiak, B. Miller, P. Pelz, N. Reißler-Pipka, R. Ritz, U. Sax, S. Schimmler, T. Schörner, T. Schrade, M. Schubotz, A. Sczyrba, R. Stein, D. von Suchodoletz, Base4NFDI - Basic Services for NFDI, (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245518>.
- [10] A. Manske, IAM4NFDI, Base4NFDI (n.d.). <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/iam4nfdi> (accessed July 26, 2024).
- [11] A. Manske, PID4NFDI, Base4NFDI (n.d.). <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi?rCH=-2> (accessed August 1, 2024).
- [12] O. Koepler, J. Sasse, N. Karam, R. Baum, Terminology Services 4 NFDI (TS4NFDI), (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12188787>.
- [13] B. Hagemeier, A. Bleier, B. Flemisch, M. Lieber, K. Reuter, G. Dogaru, Jupyter4NFDI, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12699382>.
- [14] X. Ritter, DMP4NFDI, Base4NFDI (n.d.). <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/dmp4nfdi> (accessed July 26, 2024).
- [15] X. Ritter, nfdi.software, Base4NFDI (n.d.). <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/nfdi-software?rCH=-2> (accessed August 1, 2024).
- [16*] F. Eberl, C. Schneide, L. Jansen, B. Miller, L. Amelung, V. Coors, R. Danabalan, É. Demandt, B. Ebert, J. Engel, J. Eufinger, S. Espinoza, S. Ferenz, F. Fritzsche, M. Goedicke, B. Götz, C. Hege, C. Hennig, A. Hofmann, C. Hofmann, S. Jünemann, R. Jutz, U. Krieger, C. Lauke, C.M. Rodrigues, M. Meister, S. Pittroff, N. Schatlowski, A. Schleuß, C. Schmidt, A. Schwarz, T. Schwetje, J. Seegert, F. Steinhart, T. Trippel, W. Zinke, Collaborative work in NFDI, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12819087>.
- [17] D. Hausen, A. Ujkani, J. Baur, Nachbericht des RWTH4NFDI-Workshops 2021 – Tag 1, Forschungsdaten – Aktuelles Wissenswertes (2021). <https://blog.rwth-aachen.de/forschungsdaten/2021/04/29/nachbericht-des-rwth4nfdi-workshops-2021-tag-1/> (accessed September 23, 2023).
- [18] N. Carpi, The ELN Consortium, GitHub (2022). <https://github.com/TheELNConsortium> (accessed September 23, 2023).
- [19*] N. Brandt, L. Griem, C. Herrmann, E. Schoof, G. Tosato, Y. Zhao, P. Zschumme, M. Selzer, Kadi4Mat: A Research Data Infrastructure for Materials Science, Data Sci. J. (2021). <https://kadi.iam.kit.edu/> (accessed October 30, 2023).

- [20] K. De Smedt, D. Koureas, P. Wittenburg, FAIR Digital Objects for Science: From Data Pieces to Actionable Knowledge Units, *Publications* 8 (2020) 21.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/publications8020021>.
- [21] J. Mügge, J. Grosse Erdmann, T. Riedelsheimer, M.M. Manoury, S.-O. Smolka, S. Wichmann, K. Lindow, Empowering End-of-Life Vehicle Decision Making with Cross-Company Data Exchange and Data Sovereignty via Catena-X, *Sustainability* 15 (2023) 7187.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097187>.
- [22] C. Hastik, G. Kismihok, F. Lange, P. Steiner, DALIA FAIR Open Educational Federation: Aggregation, Harmonisation, Curation, and Quality Assurance With DALIA, *Proc. Conf. Res. Data Infrastruct.* 1 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.373>.
- [23] EOSC, EOSC Working Groups, EOSC Secretariat (n.d.).
<https://eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-working-groups>.
- [24*] M. Buys, K. Garza, P. Vierkant, B. Dreyer, C. Ross, K. Stathis, B. Laing, FAIR Workflows: Connecting Engineering Research Outputs using PID Infrastructure, (2023).
<https://nfdi4ing.de/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Final-report-FAIR-Workflows-Connecting-Engineering-Research-Outputs-using-PID-Infrastructure.pdf>.
- [25] CIRP, CIRP Unified Terminology, CIRP Unified Terminol. (2024).
<https://www.cirp.net/cirp-unified-terminology.html>.
- [26] M. Antol, J. Marek, M. Capandova, J. Juracek, L. Matyska, EOSC CZ: Towards the development of Czech national ecosystem for FAIR research data, (2024).
<https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2402.13343>.
- [27] Skills4EOSC, (2022). <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/about>.
- [28] MaRDA, Materials Research Data Alliance, MaRDA (2024). <https://www.marda-alliance.org/>.
- [29] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, DFG - GEPRIS - Digital Media Workflow – An innovative concept for building digital collections to implement text and data mining methods, (n.d.). <https://gepris.dfg.de/gepris/projekt/505256794?language=en> (accessed August 1, 2024).
- [30*] M. Politze, I. Lang, K. Jansen, Coscine.nrw Landesweite Basisversorgung zur Verwaltung von Forschungsdaten im Open Source Modell, *Proc. Conf. Res. Data Infrastruct.* 1 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.235>.
- [31] KIT Data Manager, FAIR Data Commons - Service Portfolio, FAIR Data Commons - Serv. Portf. (n.d.). <https://kit-data-manager.github.io/webpage/> (accessed August 1, 2024).

[32*] T. Bronger, H. Schlenz, M. Flemming, M. Selzer, Manideep Jayavarapu, SciMesh – Knowledge graphs for scientific experiments and insight, (2022).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5878990>.

[33] Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Darmstadt, ULB´s full-text service, Univ.- Landesbibl. – TU Darmstadt (n.d.). https://www.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/die_bibliothek/einrichtungen/zeid/volltextservice.en.jsp (accessed August 1, 2024).

[34] Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Darmstadt, Centre for Digital Editions in Darmstadt (CEiD), Univ.- Landesbibl. – TU Darmstadt (n.d.). https://www.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/die_bibliothek/einrichtungen/zeid/index.en.jsp (accessed August 1, 2024).

[35] R.H. Schmitt, V. Anthofer, S. Auer, S. Başkaya, C. Bischof, T. Bronger, F. Claus, F. Cordes, É. Demandt, T. Eifert, B. Flemisch, M. Fuchs, M. Fuhrmans, R. Gerike, E.-M. Gerstner, V. Hanke, I. Heine, L. Huebser, D. Iglezakis, G. Jagusch, A. Klinger, M. Krafczyk, A. Kraft, P. Kuckertz, U. Küsters, R. Lachmayer, C. Langenbach, I. Mozgova, M.S. Müller, B. Nestler, P. Pelz, M. Politze, N. Preuß, M.-D. Przybylski-Freund, N. Reißler-Pipka, M. Robinius, J. Schachtner, H. Schlenz, A. Schwarz, J. Schwibs, M. Selzer, I. Sens, T. Stäcker, C. Stemmer, W. Stille, D. Stolten, R. Stotzka, A. Streit, R. Strötgen, W.M. Wang, NFDI4Ing - the National Research Data Infrastructure for Engineering Sciences, (2020). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4015200>.

[36*] P.F. Pelz, M. Richter, Datenkompetenz von Anfang an! Maschinenbau, Sustainable Engineering, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5669216>.

[37] N. Preuß, FAIR data box demonstrator, (2022). <https://tudatalib.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/handle/tudatalib/3610.2> (accessed August 12, 2023).

[38*] Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Darmstadt, NFDI4Ing Q&A, (2024). <https://questions.nfdi4ing.de/> (accessed August 1, 2024).

[39] B. Schembera, D. Iglezakis, EngMeta: metadata for computational engineering, Int. J. Metadata Semant. Ontol. 14 (2020) 26. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMSO.2020.107792>.

[40] R. Albertoni, D. Browning, S. Cox, A.G.B. Beltran, A. Perego, P. Winstanley, DataCatalog Vocabulary (DCAT) - Version 2, (2020). <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>.

[41] DataCite Metadata Working Group, DataCite Metadata Schema for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs v4.4, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.14454/FXWS-0523>.

- [42] P. Sefton, E. Ó Carragáin, S. Soiland-Reyes, O. Corcho, D. Garijo, R. Palma, F. Coppens, C. Goble, J.M. Fernández, K. Chard, J.M. Gomez-Perez, M.R. Crusoe, I. Eguinoa, N. Juty, K. Holmes, J.A. Clark, S. Capella-Gutierrez, A.J.G. Gray, S. Owen, A.R. Williams, G. Tartari, F. Bacall, T. Thelen, H. Ménager, L. Rodríguez-Navas, P. Walk, brandon whitehead, M. Wilkinson, P. Groth, E. Bremer, L.J. Castro, K. Sebbby, A. Kanitz, A. Trisovic, G. Kennedy, M. Graves, J. Koehorst, S. Leo, M. Portier, P. Brack, M. Ojsteršek, B. Droesbeke, C. Niu, K. Tanabe, T. Miksa, M. La Rosa, C. Decruw, A. Czerniak, J. Jay, S. Serra, R. Siebes, S. de Witt, S. El Damaty, D. Lowe, X. Li, S. Gundersen, M. Radifar, RO-Crate Metadata Specification 1.1.3, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3406497>.
- [43] RDF Working Group, RDF - Semantic Web Standards, (2014). <https://www.w3.org/RDF/> (accessed November 26, 2023).
- [44] OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Conformance (Second Edition), (2012). <https://www.w3.org/TR/2012/REC-owl2-conformance-20121211/> (accessed June 24, 2024).
- [45*] V. Hartmann, B. Heinrichs, Metadata Hub - One for All, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000151732>.
- [46*] F. Engel, G. Tuncay, A. Kraft, NFDI4Ing Terminology Service, (2021). <https://terminology.nfdi4ing.de/ts/> (accessed September 7, 2023).
- [47*] T. Bronger, H. Schlenz, M. Flemming, M. Selzer, M. Jayavarapu, SciMesh: RDF graphs for scientific knowledge, 2022. <https://juser.fz-juelich.de/record/911876>.
- [48*] D. Iglezakis, M. Fuhrmans, G. Lanza, D. Terzijska, S. Arndt, S. Leimer, J. Hickmann, Modelling Scientific Processes with the m4i Ontology, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8348784>.
- [49*] N. Preuß, M. Bodenbenner, B. Heinrichs, J. Windeck, M. Moser, M. Fuhrmans, Creating application-specific metadata profiles while improving interoperability and consistency of research data for the engineering sciences, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.26083/TUPRINTS-00024573>.
- [50*] P. Kuckertz, J. Göpfert, O. Karras, D. Neuroth, J. Schönau, R. Pueblias, S. Ferenz, F. Engel, N. Pflugradt, J.M. Weinand, A. Nieße, S. Auer, D. Stolten, A Metadata-Based Ecosystem to Improve the FAIRness of Research Software, (2023). <http://arxiv.org/abs/2306.10620> (accessed January 26, 2024).
- [51] FAIR Digital Objects Forum, FDO Specifications, (n.d.). <https://fairdo.org/specifications/> (accessed July 9, 2024).

- [52] RD Alliance, Research Data Management Engineering, (n.d.). <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/research-data-managementengineering-ig/case-statement/research-data-management-engineering-ig> (accessed February 11, 2024).
- [53] Research Data Alliance, FAIR Digital Object Fabric IG Home, (n.d.). <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/group-fair-digital-object-fabric-ig-1942598258/> (accessed July 9, 2024).
- [54] A. Braud, G. Fromentoux, B. Radier, O. Le Grand, The Road to European Digital Sovereignty with Gaia-X and IDSA, *IEEE Netw.* 35 (2021) 4–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MNET.2021.9387709>.
- [55] A. Lehmann, S. Day, W. Zinke, Workshopbericht zum Community Workshop: Kartierung der Datenkompetenzlandschaft, Zenodo, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7920834>.
- [56] B. Petersen, C. Engelhardt, T. Hörner, J. Jacob, T. Kvetnaya, A. Mühlichen, H. Schranzhofer, S. Schulz, B. Slowig, U. Trautwein-Bruns, A. Voigt, C. Wiljes, Lernzielmatrix zum Themenbereich Forschungsdatenmanagement (FDM) für die Zielgruppen Studierende, PhDs und Data Stewards, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7034477>.
- [57*] M. Galdino, T. Hamann, C. Hastik, D. Hecker, C. Langenbach, M. Moser, J. Neumann, U. Trautwein-Bruns, K. Wedlich-Zachodin, Schulungsplattform der NFDI4Ing, (2023). <https://education.nfdi4ing.de/#/> (accessed September 13, 2023).
- [58] IETF, About RFCs, IETF RFCs (n.d.). <https://www.ietf.org/process/rfc/> (accessed July 9, 2024).
- [59] Research Data Alliance, RDA Standards, Standards (n.d.). <https://www.rd-alliance.org/standards/>.
- [60] J. Geiger, P. Steiner, A.A. Desouki, F. Lange, DALIA Interchange Format, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11521028>.
- [61] K. Biernacka, S.A. Danker, C. Engelhardt, K. Helbig, S. Hendriks, J. Jacob, G. Jagusch, G. Lanza, C. Leone, K. Meier, J. Neumann, C. Odebrecht, K. Peters, S. Rehwald, J. Rex, M. Senft, A. Strauch, K. Thiemann, U. Trautwein-Bruns, C. Wiljes, U. Wuttke, F. Ziedorn, Metadatenchema für Schulungsmaterialien zum Thema Forschungsdatenmanagement, (2020). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3760397>.
- [62] N.J. Hoebelheinrich, K. Biernacka, M. Brazas, L.J. Castro, N. Fiore, M. Hellström, E. Lazzeri, E. Leenarts, P.M. Martinez Lavanchy, E. Newbold, A. Nurnberger, E. Plomp, L. Vaira, C.W.G. van Gelder, A. Whyte, Recommendations for a minimal metadata set to aid harmonised discovery of learning resources, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00073>.

- [63] Open Resources Campus NRW, ORCA.nrw, (n.d.). <https://www.orca.nrw/>.
- [64] twillo, twillo, Offene Bild. Finden Auf Twillo Teilen (n.d.). <https://www.twillo.de/oer/web/>.
- [65] A.A. Guzmán, A.Z. Ihsan, S. Fathalla, The MatWerk ontology, (2024). <https://nfdi-matwerk.pages.rwth-aachen.de/ta-oms/mwo/docs/index.html> (accessed July 17, 2024).
- [66] B. Bayerlein, M. Schilling, H. Birkholz, M. Jung, J. Waitelonis, L. Mädler, H. Sack, PMD Core Ontology: Achieving semantic interoperability in materials science, Mater. Des. 237 (2024) 112603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2023.112603>.
- [67] B. Schembera, F. Wübbeling, H. Kleikamp, C. Biedinger, J. Fiedler, M. Reidelbach, A. Shehu, B. Schmidt, T. Koprucki, D. Iglezakis, D. Göddeke, Ontologies for Models and Algorithms in Applied Mathematics and Related Disciplines, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2310.20443>.
- [68] M. Grönewald, P. Mund, M. Bodenbenner, M. Fuhrmans, B. Heinrichs, M.S. Müller, P.F. Pelz, M. Politze, N. Preuß, R.H. Schmitt, T. Stäcker, Mit AIMS zu einem Metadatenmanagement 4.0: FAIRe Forschungsdaten benötigen interoperable Metadaten, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.11588/HEIBOOKS.979.C13721>.
- [69] V. Hartmann, B. Heinrichs, Specification of Turntable API for Metadata Repositories, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10408707>.
- [70*] Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Darmstadt, NFDI4Ing ing.est, (2024). <https://ingest.nfdi4ing.de/> (accessed August 1, 2024).
- [71*] I. Lang, M. Nellesen, L.C. Bossert, M. Politze, Carrots and Sticks: Motivating with Storage for Good RDM – Science Led Allocation of Research Data Storage Resources within an Integrated RDM System, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.11588/HEIBOOKS.1288.C18071>.
- [72] M. Politze, Y. Shakeel, S. Hunke, P. Ost, R. Aversa, B. Heinrichs, I. Lang, Long Term Interoperability of Distributed Research Data Infrastructures, Proc. Conf. Res. Data Infrastruct. 1 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.348>.
- [73] M.A. Cyra, M. Politze, H. Timm, A push for better RDM: Erfahrungsbericht aus dem Einsatz von git für Forschungsdaten, Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement (2022). <https://doi.org/10.17192/bfdm.2022.2.8435>.
- [74*] M. Politze, H. Timm, M. Cyra, Einstieg ins Forschungsdatenmanagement mit git und GitLab, (2020). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8385731>.

- [75] B. Flemisch, D. Gläser, M. Politze, Metadaten und wo sie zu finden sind & Automatisierung, Qualitätssicherung, Zeitpläne: Praxiseinsatz für den GitLab Runner, (2020). <https://tu-darmstadt.cloud.panopto.eu/Panopto/Pages/Viewer.aspx?id=b7dacf4b-0af3-496e-91fb-acb800ec5a9d> (accessed July 31, 2024).
- [76*] V. Seibert, A. Rausch, S. Wittek, Betty's (Re)Search Engine: A client-based search engine for research software stored in repositories., (2024). <https://doi.org/10.48694/INGGRID.3953>.
- [77*] P. Ost, Y. Shakeel, P. Tögel, Data Collections Explorer, Proc. Conf. Res. Data Infrastruct. 1 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.405>.
- [78] K. Diederichs, C. Krause, M. Lemaire, M. Reidelbach, J. Windeck, A Vision for Data Management Plans in the NFDI, Zenodo, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10570654>.
- [79*] A. Seeland, NFDI4Ing JupyterHub, (2022). <https://jupyter.nfdi4ing.de/> (accessed August 14, 2023).
- [80*] T. Hamann, J. Werheid, M.N. Moser, M. Robrecht, S. Hillemacher, P. Kehl, S. Ben-Hassine, Joint Assistant for Research in Versatile Engineering Sciences, Jt. Assist. Res. Versatile Eng. Sci. (2023). <https://jarves.nfdi4ing.de/> (accessed September 23, 2023).
- [81*] Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Darmstadt, TUstorage, (2022). <https://tustorage.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/home> (accessed July 26, 2024).
- [82*] M. Moser, J. Werheid, T. Hamann, A. Abdelrazeq, R.H. Schmitt, Which FAIR Are You? A Detailed Comparison of Existing FAIR Metrics in the Context of Research Data Management - Presentation, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8346694>.
- [83*] H. Dierend, Data Quality Metrics, (2022). <https://quality.nfdi4ing.de/en/> (accessed August 14, 2023).
- [84] J. Nogueras-Iso, J. Lacasta, M.A. Ureña-Cámara, F.J. Ariza-López, Quality of Metadata in Open Data Portals, IEEE Access 9 (2021) 60364–60382. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3073455>.
- [85] F. Löffler, V. Wesp, B. König-Ries, F. Klan, Dataset search in biodiversity research: Do metadata in data repositories reflect scholarly information needs?, PLOS ONE 16 (2021) e0246099. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0246099>.
- [86] A. Quarati, J.E. Raffaghelli, Do researchers use open research data? Exploring the relationships between usage trends and metadata quality across scientific disciplines from the Figshare case, J. Inf. Sci. 48 (2022) 423–448. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551520961048>.

- [87] T. Miksa, J. Chodacki, M. Suchánek, M. Praetzellis, E. Papadopoulou, M.-C. Jacquemot, A. Kevin, Salzburg Manifesto on machine actionable Data Management Plans, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10658522>, <https://activedmps.org/> (accessed June 19, 2024).
- [88] L.J. Castro, L. Geist, E. Gonzalez, M. Gonzalez-Ocanto, Y.V. Grossmann, T. Pronk, D. Solanki, C. Utrilla Guerrero, D. Wallace, J. Windeck, Five Minutes to Write a Software Management Plan – A Machine-actionable Approach to Simplify the Creation of SMPs, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10374839>.
- [89] FAIR for Machine Learning (FAIR4ML) IG, (n.d.). <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rationale/fair-machine-learning-fair4ml-ig/> (accessed July 26, 2024).
- [90] J. Savelka, A. Agarwal, C. Bogart, Y. Song, M. Sakr, Can Generative Pre-trained Transformers (GPT) Pass Assessments in Higher Education Programming Courses?, in: Proc. 2023 Conf. Innov. Technol. Comput. Sci. Educ. V 1, 2023: pp. 117–123. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3587102.3588792>.
- [91] A. Moradi Dakhel, V. Majdinasab, A. Nikanjam, F. Khomh, M.C. Desmarais, Z.M. (Jack) Jiang, GitHub Copilot AI pair programmer: Asset or Liability?, J. Syst. Softw. 203 (2023) 111734. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2023.111734>.
- [92] M. Wermelinger, Using GitHub Copilot to Solve Simple Programming Problems, in: 2023: pp. 172–178. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3545945.3569830>.
- [93] C.E. Jimenez, J. Yang, A. Wettig, S. Yao, K. Pei, O. Press, K. Narasimhan, SWE-bench: Can Language Models Resolve Real-World GitHub Issues?, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2310.06770>.
- [94] D. Chen, S. Lin, M. Zeng, D. Zan, J.-G. Wang, A. Cheshkov, J. Sun, H. Yu, G. Dong, A. Aliev, J. Wang, X. Cheng, G. Liang, Y. Ma, P. Bian, T. Xie, Q. Wang, CodeR: Issue Resolving with Multi-Agent and Task Graphs, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2406.01304>.
- [95] T. Eisenreich, S. Speth, S. Wagner, From Requirements to Architecture: An AI-Based Journey to Semi-Automatically Generate Software Architectures, in: Proc. 1st Int. Workshop Des. Softw., Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2024: pp. 52–55. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3643660.3643942>.
- [96] S. Geisler, S.-Y. Kim, Unlocking the Potential: LLMs Transforming Research Data Management, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.18154/RWTH-2023-10498> (accessed June 19, 2024).

- [97] P. Lewis, E. Perez, A. Piktus, F. Petroni, V. Karpukhin, N. Goyal, H. Küttler, M. Lewis, W. Yih, T. Rocktäschel, S. Riedel, D. Kiela, Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Knowledge-Intensive NLP Tasks, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2005.11401>.
- [98*] M.L. Wawer, Reifegradmodelle für das Forschungsdatenmanagement in Forschungsprojekten, (2021). <https://maturitymodelsnfdi4ing.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> (accessed July 26, 2024).
- [99] A. Devaraju, R. Huber, An automated solution for measuring the progress toward FAIR research data, Patterns 2 (2021) 100370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100370>.
- [100] LISA - a Hugging Face Space by Kadi-IAM, (n.d.). <https://huggingface.co/spaces/Kadi-IAM/LISA> (accessed July 26, 2024).
- [101] DA-FDM Home - DA-FDM - BSZ-WIKI, (n.d.). <https://wiki.bsz-bw.de/display/DAFDM/DA-FDM+Home> (accessed July 26, 2024).
- [102] A.Q. Jiang, A. Sablayrolles, A. Roux, A. Mensch, B. Savary, C. Bamford, D.S. Chaplot, D. de las Casas, E.B. Hanna, F. Bressand, G. Lengyel, G. Bour, G. Lample, L.R. Lavaud, L. Saulnier, M.-A. Lachaux, P. Stock, S. Subramanian, S. Yang, S. Antoniak, T.L. Scao, T. Gervet, T. Lavril, T. Wang, T. Lacroix, W.E. Sayed, Mixtral of Experts, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.04088>.
- [103] AI4EOSC, Build AI models in the EOSC – AI4EOSC, (2022). <https://ai4eosc.eu/platform/> (accessed July 26, 2024).
- [104] M.T. Horsch, XAIR: Explainable-AI and Metadata – Knowledge Graph Alliance, (n.d.). <https://www.kg-alliance.org/kg-wg-xai-24-4/> (accessed August 1, 2024).
- [105] M.T. Horsch, B. Schembera, H.A. Preisig, European standardization efforts from FAIR toward explainable-AI-ready data documentation in materials modelling, in: 2023 3rd Int. Conf. Appl. Artif. Intell. ICAPAI, IEEE, Halden, Norway, 2023: pp. 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAPAI58366.2023.10193944>.
- [106] RDMO, (n.d.). <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/en/Community/> (accessed July 26, 2024).
- [107] Janeway, Janeway - Home, (n.d.). <https://janeway.systems/index> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [108*] NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Ing Community Meeting CC-41 2022, NFDI4Ing (n.d.). https://nfdi4ing.de/events/communitymeeting_cc-41_2022/ (accessed July 28, 2024).

- [109*] NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Ing Community Meeting CC-42 2022, NFDI4Ing (n.d.). https://nfdi4ing.de/events/communitymeeting_cc-42_2022/ (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [110*] NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Ing Community Meeting CC-44 2023, NFDI4Ing (n.d.). https://nfdi4ing.de/events/communitymeeting_cc-44_2023/ (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [111*] NFDI4Ing Konferenz 2021, NFDI4Ing (n.d.). <https://nfdi4ing.de/deprecated-conference-2021/> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [112*] NFDI4Ing conference 2022, NFDI4Ing (n.d.). <https://nfdi4ing.de/conference-2022/> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [113*] NFDI4Ing conference 2023, NFDI4Ing (n.d.). <https://nfdi4ing.de/conference-2023/> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [114] NFDI InfraTalk: ing.grid - FAIR Data Management in Engineering Sciences (6 November 2023), 2023. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DxqTMn0tvOo> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [115*] K.T. Logan, I.S. Pimenta, M. Leštáková, P.F. Pelz, A FAIR Future for Engineering Sciences - Linking an RDM Community through a Scientific Journal, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8387301>.
- [116*] Research data management maturity models in engineering, IG RDMInEng Data Quality and FAIR metrics in Engineering - Virtual Plenary 19, online, 2021. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pzTDhdfxRn0>.
- [117*] I. Silva Pimenta, K. Logan, M. Leštáková, P.F. Pelz, A.-C. Günther, M. Kerekes, S. Kraußold, Open Peer Review for a Transparent and Engaging Scientific Environment: Towards a FAIR Journal, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.26083/TUPRINTS-00024577>.
- [118] I. Silva Pimenta, K. Logan, M. Leštáková, P. Pelz, Research outcomes and scholarly publishing: FAIR principles as quality assessment, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10047550>.
- [119] Perspektive offene Wissenschaft @ RMU 2022 | UB Mainz, (n.d.). <https://www.ub.uni-mainz.de/de/rmu/perspektive-offene-wissenschaft> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [120] A Vision for a FAIR Publisher - ing.grid presentation at University:Future Festival 2021, 2022. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bPa4pa7GOxk> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [121] Research Data Alliance, RDA Deutschland Tagung 2022, DESY-Konf. Indico (n.d.). <https://indico.desy.de/event/31380/contributions/115815/> (accessed July 28, 2024).

- [122] Automation of LIMS for Data Analysis and Reuse, 2023.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6R7q1UzCO7w> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [123] D. Wolfram, P. Wang, A. Hembree, H. Park, Open peer review: promoting transparency in open science, *Scientometrics* 125 (2020) 1033–1051. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03488-4>.
- [124] J. Bosman, J.E. Frantsvåg, B. Kramer, P.-C. Langlais, V. Proudman, OA Diamond Journals Study. Part 1: Findings, Zenodo, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4558703>.
- [125] N.C. Hong, In which journals should I publish my software?, *Softw. Sustainability Inst.* (n.d.). <https://www.software.ac.uk/top-tip/which-journals-should-i-publish-my-software>.
- [126] JOSS, Journal of Open Source Software, (n.d.). <https://joss.theoj.org> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [127] W.H. Walters, Data journals: incentivizing data access and documentation within the scholarly communication system, *Insights* 33 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.510>.
- [128] Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Darmstadt, Reviewer Guidelines, Ingrid (n.d.). <https://www.ingrid.org/site/reviewerguidelines/>.
- [129] Bausteine - FDM, Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement, (n.d.). <https://bausteine-fdm.de/index> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [130*] C. Bless, I. Baimuratov, O. Karras, SciKGT_eX - A LaTeX Package to Semantically Annotate Contributions in Scientific Publications, (2023).
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2304.05327>.
- [131] M. Leštáková, Y. Wu, L. George, ing.grid LaTeX Template, GitLab (2024).
<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/inggrid/template> (accessed July 31, 2024).
- [132] S. Mehrnia, P.F. Pelz, Tribological Design by Molecular Dynamics Simulation: Influence of the Molecular Structure on Wall Slip and Bulk Shear, *Chem. Eng. Technol.* 46 (2023) 95–101. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceat.202200448>.
- [133] G. Hatzissawidis, G.J. Ludwig, P.F. Pelz, Modal Decomposition of Large- and Small-Scale Cloud Cavitation, *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.* 774 (2021) 012097.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/774/1/012097>.
- [134] T.M. Müller, Supplementary Material: Algorithmisch gestützte Planung dezentraler Fluidsysteme, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.48328/TUDATALIB-834>.

- [135*] M. Rexer, N. Preuß, S. Neumeier, P.F. Pelz, How to Make Bespoke Experiments FAIR: Modular Dynamic Semantic Digital Twin and Open Source Information Infrastructure, (2024). <https://preprints.inggrid.org/repository/view/40/> (accessed July 25, 2024).
- [136*] S. Arndt, B. Farnbacher, M. Fuhrmans, S. Hachinger, J. Hickmann, N. Hoppe, M.T. Horsch, D. Iglezakis, A. Karmacharya, G. Lanza, S. Leimer, J. Munke, D. Terzijska, J. Theissen-Lipp, C. Wiljes, J. Windeck, Metadata4Ing: An ontology for describing the generation of research data within a scientific activity., (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.5957104>.
- [137] Research Object Crate (RO-Crate), (n.d.). <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/> (accessed July 25, 2024).
- [138*] M. Hock, H. Mayr, M. Richter, J. Lemmer, P. Pelz, plotID - a toolkit for connecting research data and visualization, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.48694/INGGRID.3632>.
- [139] Catena-X, (n.d.). <https://catena-x.net/en/> (accessed July 25, 2024).
- [140] N. Kockmann, ENPRO: REUNION, TU Dortmund. (n.d.). <https://ad.bci.tu-dortmund.de/research/projects/current-projects/enpro-reunion/> (accessed July 25, 2024).
- [141] HeFDI Code School: Sustainable Research Software (EN), Philipps-Univ. Marburg (n.d.). <https://www.uni-marburg.de/en/hefdi/hefdi-data-event/code-school> (accessed July 25, 2024).
- [142] C. Schnur, S. Klein, A. Blum, Checklist – Measurement and data planning for machine learning in assembly, (2022). <https://zenodo.org/records/7556876#.Y8-mGHbMJD8>.
- [143*] C. Schnur, T. Dorst, K.S. Deshmukh, S. Zimmer, P. Litzenburger, T. Schneider, L. Margies, R. Müller, A. Schütze, PIA - A Concept for a Personal Information Assistant for Data Analysis and Machine Learning of Time-Continuous Data in Industrial Applications, Ing.Grid 1 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.48694/inggrid.3827>.
- [144*] D. Inturri, K. Logan, M. Leštáková, Software Packaging (Python) - NFDI4Ing Alex's Action Items, (2021). https://ta_alex.pages.rwth-aachen.de/action-items/action-items/55_software_packaging_python/ (accessed July 25, 2024).
- [145*] D. Inturri, Introduction to Poetry - NFDI4Ing Alex's Action Items, (2021). https://ta_alex.pages.rwth-aachen.de/action-items/action-items/introduction-to-poetry/ (accessed July 25, 2024).
- [146*] M. Leštáková, M. Richter, Python Styleguide for Researchers, (2022). https://ta_alex.pages.rwth-aachen.de/action-items/action-items/37_styleguide_py/ (accessed August 13, 2023).

[147*] I. Afkir, B. Calabakan, K. Repp, S.A. Sauter, B. Tiggers, Z. Zhichao, pyKraken-Bibliothek zur Strukturierung von Daten mit Metadaten unter Python und dem Export in HDF5 und JSON, (2022). <https://git.rwth-aachen.de/fst-tuda/public/pykkn> (accessed August 12, 2023).

[148] K.T. Logan, M.M. Meck, N. Preuß, P. Wetterich, P.F. Pelz, Data Management as an Enabler of Sustainability – Discussion Using the Example of a Digital Data Sheet; 2nd revised edition, Fluid Power Digit. reliable (2023) pages 813-827. <https://doi.org/10.18154/RWTH-2023-04624>.

[149] D. Inturri, SOFIRpy / SOFIRpy · GitLab, GitLab (2024). <https://git.rwth-aachen.de/sofirpy/sofirpy> (accessed July 25, 2024).

[150] P. Leise, Supplementary Material: Algorithmic Design of Technical Systems under Uncertainty, (2022). <https://tudatalib.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/handle/tudatalib/3550> (accessed July 25, 2024).

[151] M.J. Mich, pyDuCo, (2024). <https://git.rwth-aachen.de/pyduco/pyduco> (accessed July 15, 2024).

[152] TU-DA Fluidsystemtechnik / Projects / Research Data Management / Metadata Serializer · GitLab, GitLab (n.d.). <https://git.rwth-aachen.de/fst-tuda/projects/rdm/metadata-serializer> (accessed July 25, 2024).

[153] API Reference — Plot Serializer documentation, (n.d.). <https://plot-serializer.readthedocs.io/en/latest/autoapi/index.html> (accessed July 25, 2024).

[154] K. Logan, N. Xia, Datenkompetenz von Anfang an – Grundlagen der Digitalisierung, (n.d.). https://4ing.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/presentation_240415_4Ing_Workshop_Grundlagen_der_Digitalisierung_Logan_Xia_Pelz.pdf.

[155] P. Pelz, D.M. Kuhr, D.C. Hastik, J. Breuer, K. Henn, B. Hermann, T. Meck, P. Moor, N. Puff, Z. Tabaie, P. Wetterich, N. Xia, Datenkompetenz von Anfang an, (n.d.). https://4ing.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/presentation_231009_Datenkompetenz_von_Anfang_an_4Ing_hastik_kuhr_pelz_final.pdf.

[156] P. Groche, E. Abele, N. Al-Baradoni, S. Bartsch, C. Bölling, N. Brötz, C.M. Gehb, F. Geßner, B. Götz, J. Hartig, P. Hedrich, D. Hesse, M. Heßler, F. Hoppe, L. Joggerst, S. Kersting, H. Klobberdanz, M. Knoll, M. Kohler, M. Krech, J. Lenz, M. Leštáková, K.T. Logan, D. Martin, T. Melz, T.M. Müller, T. Öztürk, P.F. Pelz, R. Platz, A. Rapp, M. Rexer, M. Schaeffner, F. Schulte, J. Sinz, J. Stegmeier, M. Weigold, J. Wendt, Methods and Technologies for Mastering

Uncertainty, in: P.F. Pelz, P. Groche, M.E. Pfetsch, M. Schaeffner (Eds.), Mastering Uncertain. Mech. Eng., Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2021: pp. 209–364.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-78354-9_5.

[157] Text+, Home - Text+, (n.d.). <https://text-plus.org/> (accessed August 1, 2024).

[158] N. Preuß, P.F. Pelz, Integrated management of experimental research- and meta- data for fan test rigs, (n.d.). <https://www.fan2025.org/archives/fan2018/papers/paper-87.html> (accessed August 1, 2024).

[159] N. Preuß, G. Staudter, M. Weber, Methods and Technologies for Research- and Metadata Management in Collaborative Experimental Research, (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.885.170>.

[160] Fluidsystemtechnik, Institut für Fluidsystemtechnik, Fluidsystemtechnik – TU Darmstadt (n.d.). <https://www.fst.tu-darmstadt.de/fachgebiet/index.de.jsp> (accessed July 25, 2024).

[161] Technische Universität Darmstadt, Reaktive Strömungen und Messtechnik, Reakt. Strömungen Messtech. – TU Darmstadt (n.d.). https://www.rsm.tu-darmstadt.de/home_rsm/index.de.jsp (accessed November 24, 2023).

[162] Technische Universität Darmstadt, Simulation of reactive Thermo-Fluid Systems, (n.d.). <https://www.maschinenbau.tu-darmstadt.de/stfs/stfs/welcome.en.jsp> (accessed September 29, 2019).

[163] Technische Universität Darmstadt, CRC 1194 - Interaction between Transport and Wetting Processes, (n.d.). https://www.sfb1194.tudarmstadt.de/sfb_1194/index.en.jsp. (accessed September 29, 2019).

[164] Technische Universität Darmstadt, SFB/TRR150: Turbulente, chemisch reagierende Mehrphasenströmungen in Wandnähe, (n.d.). https://www.trr150.tudarmstadt.de/der_sonderforschungsbereich/CRC.en.jsp (accessed September 29, 2019).

[165] RWTH Aachen University, CRC/TRR 129 Oxyflame, (n.d.). <https://www.oxyflame.de/> (accessed November 24, 2023).

[166] Technische Universität Darmstadt, SFB 805, (n.d.). <https://www.sfb805.tudarmstadt.de/sfb805/Index.de.jsp> (accessed September 29, 2019).

[167] Technische Universität Darmstadt, Home - Clean Circles, (n.d.). https://www.tu-darmstadt.de/clean-circles/about_cc/index.de.jsp (accessed August 1, 2024).

- [168] M. Barker, N.P. Chue Hong, D.S. Katz, A.-L. Lamprecht, C. Martinez-Ortiz, F. Psomopoulos, J. Harrow, L.J. Castro, M. Gruenpeter, P.A. Martinez, T. Honeyman, Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software, *Sci. Data* 9 (2022) 622. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>.
- [169] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice. Code of Conduct, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3923601>.
- [170] L.J. Castro, S. Ferenz, M. Fuhrmans, J. Göpfert, D. Iglezakis, O. Karras, A. Struck, “Research Software Metadata” - Working Group Charter (NFDI section-metadata), Zenodo, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10808325>.
- [171] A. Hocquet, F. Wieber, G. Gramelsberger, K. Hinsen, M. Diesmann, F. Pasquini Santos, C. Landström, B. Peters, D. Kasprowicz, A. Borrelli, P. Roth, C.A.L. Lee, A. Olteanu, S. Böschen, Software in science is ubiquitous yet overlooked, *Nat. Comput. Sci.* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-024-00651-2>.
- [172*] D. Gläser, T. Koch, S. Peters, S. Marcus, B. Flemisch, FieldCompare: A Python package for regression testingsimulation results, *J. Open Source Softw.* 8 (2023) 4905. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.04905>.
- [173*] D. Gläser, T. Koch, B. Flemisch, GridFormat: Header-Only C++-Library for Grid File I/O, *J. Open Source Softw.* 8 (2023) 5778. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.05778>.
- [174*] T. Koch, D. Gläser, A. Seeland, S. Roy, K. Schulze, K. Weishaupt, D. Boehring, S. Hermann, B. Flemisch, A sustainable infrastructure concept for improved accessibility, reusability, and archival of research software, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2301.12830>.
- [175*] P. Diercks, D. Gläser, O. Lünsdorf, M. Selzer, B. Flemisch, J.F. Unger, Evaluation of tools for describing, reproducing and reusing scientific workflows, *Ing.Grid* 1 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.48694/inggrid.3726>.
- [176] S. Druskat, J.H. Spaaks, N. Chue Hong, R. Haines, J. Baker, S. Bliven, E. Willighagen, D. Pérez-Suárez, A. Konovalov, Citation File Format, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.1003149>.
- [177] CodeMeta, The CodeMeta Project, (n.d.). <https://codemeta.github.io/>.
- [178] W.L. Oberkamp, C.J. Roy, Verification and Validation in Scientific Computing, 1st ed., Cambridge University Press, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511760396>.
- [179] OpenML, OpenML, (n.d.). <https://www.openml.org/> (accessed July 23, 2024).

- [180] Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB), Open Research Knowledge Graph, (n.d.). <https://orkg.org/> (accessed November 29, 2023).
- [181] Jens Bröder, Gabriel Preuß, Fiona D’Mello, Said Fathalla, Volker Hofmann, Stefan Sandfeld, The Helmholtz Knowledge Graph: driving the transition towards a FAIR data ecosystem in the Helmholtz Association, in: Mater. Data Sci. Inform., 2024. https://2024.eswc-conferences.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/ESWC_2024_paper_303.pdf.
- [182] S. Soiland-Reyes, P. Sefton, M. Crosas, L.J. Castro, F. Coppens, J.M. Fernández, D. Garijo, B. Grüning, M. La Rosa, S. Leo, E.Ó. Carragáin, M. Portier, A. Trisovic, R.-C. Community, P. Groth, C. Goble, Packaging research artefacts with RO-Crate, (2021). <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2108.06503>.
- [183*] A. Kraft, F. Engel, A. Klinger, Terminologies in RDM for Engineering – a Service Approach: NFDI4Ing Terminology Service, Proc. Conf. Res. Data Infrastruct. 1 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.207>.
- [184] G. Pizzi, A. Cepellotti, R. Sabatini, N. Marzari, B. Kozinsky, AiiDA: automated interactive infrastructure and database for computational science, Comput. Mater. Sci. 111 (2016) 218–230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.commatsci.2015.09.013>.
- [185] H. Van de Sompel, M. Klein, S. Jones, M.L. Nelson, S. Warner, A. Devaraju, R. Huber, W. Steinhoff, V. Tykhonov, L. Boruta, E. Meijers, S. Soiland-Reyes, M. Wilkinson, FAIR Signposting Profile, (2023). <https://signposting.org/FAIR/>.
- [186] T. Delva, J. Arenas-Guerrero, A. Iglesias-Molina, O. Corcho, D. Chaves-Fraga, A. Dimou, RML-star: A declarative mapping language for RDF-star generation., in: CEUR, 2021.
- [187] J. Benet, IPFS - Content Addressed, Versioned, P2P File System, (2014). <http://arxiv.org/abs/1407.3561> (accessed July 5, 2024).
- [188] Protocol Labs, IPLD – The data model of the content-addressable web, (2024). <https://ipld.io/> (accessed July 5, 2024).
- [189] Protocol Labs, Advanced Data Layout Specifications, (2024). <https://ipld.io/specs/advanced-data-layouts/> (accessed July 5, 2024).
- [190] JupyterHub, (n.d.). <https://jupyter.org> (accessed December 8, 2023).
- [191] T. Bronger, JuliaBase, the samples database, (n.d.). <https://juliabase.org/> (accessed November 24, 2023).

- [192] N. Carpi, A. Mingos, M. Piel, eLabFTW: An open source laboratory notebook for research labs, *J. Open Source Softw.* 2 (2017) 146. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00146>.
- [193] O. Kramer, Scikit-Learn, in: *Mach. Learn. Evol. Strateg.*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2016: pp. 45–53. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-33383-0_5.
- [194] M. Feurer, K. Eggensperger, S. Falkner, M. Lindauer, F. Hutter, Auto-Sklearn 2.0: Hands-free AutoML via Meta-Learning, (2022). <http://arxiv.org/abs/2007.04074> (accessed July 5, 2024).
- [195] A. Kelley, D. Garijo, A framework for creating knowledge graphs of scientific software metadata, *Quant. Sci. Stud.* 2 (2021) 1423–1446. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00167.
- [196] S. Druskat, O. Bertuch, G. Juckeland, O. Knodel, T. Schlauch, Software publications with rich metadata: state of the art, automated workflows and HERMES concept, (2022). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2201.09015>.
- [197] M.D. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, I.J. Aalbersberg, G. Appleton, M. Axton, A. Baak, N. Blomberg, J.-W. Boiten, L.B. Da Silva Santos, P.E. Bourne, J. Bouwman, A.J. Brookes, T. Clark, M. Crosas, I. Dillo, O. Dumon, S. Edmunds, C.T. Evelo, R. Finkers, A. Gonzalez-Beltran, A.J.G. Gray, P. Groth, C. Goble, J.S. Grethe, J. Heringa, P.A.C. 'T Hoen, R. Hooft, T. Kuhn, R. Kok, J. Kok, S.J. Lusher, M.E. Martone, A. Mons, A.L. Packer, B. Persson, P. Rocca-Serra, M. Roos, R. Van Schaik, S.-A. Sansone, E. Schultes, T. Sengstag, T. Slater, G. Strawn, M.A. Swertz, M. Thompson, J. Van Der Lei, E. Van Mulligen, J. Velterop, A. Waagmeester, P. Wittenburg, K. Wolstencroft, J. Zhao, B. Mons, The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, *Sci. Data* 3 (2016) 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.
- [198] D.S. Katz, M. Gruenpeter, T. Honeyman, Taking a fresh look at FAIR for research software, *Patterns* 2 (2021) 100222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100222>.
- [199] W. Hasselbring, L. Carr, S. Hettrick, H. Packer, T. Tiropanis, From FAIR research data toward FAIR and open research software, *It - Inf. Technol.* 62 (2020) 39–47. <https://doi.org/10.1515/itit-2019-0040>.
- [200*] P. Kuckertz, J. Göpfert, D. Neuroth, J. Schönau, R. Pueblos, S. Ferenz, F. Engel, N. Pflugradt, J.M. Weinand, L. Kotzur, A. Nieße, S. Auer, D. Stolten, DataDesc - A framework for machine-actionable software metadata, (2024). <https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-VSA/DataDesc>.
- [201] Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB), ORKG Ask, (n.d.). <http://ask.orkg.org> (accessed July 22, 2024).

- [202] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), Schwerpunktprogramm „Hundert plus – Verlängerung der Lebensdauer komplexer Baustrukturen durch intelligente Digitalisierung“ (SPP 2388), (n.d.). <https://www.dfg.de/de/aktuelles/neuigkeiten-themen/info-wissenschaft/2021/info-wissenschaft-21-56> (accessed July 22, 2024).
- [203] SFB TRR 339, Straße der Zukunft, (n.d.). <https://www.sfbtrr339.de/de/> (accessed July 22, 2024).
- [204] Technische Universität Berlin | Civil Systems Engineering, Computing in Civil Engineering, (n.d.). <https://gacce.de/> (accessed July 22, 2024).
- [205] F. Petzold, Arbeitskreis Architekturinformatik, (n.d.). <https://www.architekturinformatik.org/> (accessed July 22, 2024).
- [206] Projektträger Jülich, Forschungsnetzwerk Systemanalyse, (n.d.). <https://www.forschungsnetzwerke-energie.de/systemanalyse> (accessed November 24, 2023).
- [207] Gesellschaft für Energiewissenschaft und Energiepolitik e. V., GEE, gee.de (n.d.). <https://gee.de/> (accessed November 24, 2023).
- [208] Open Energy Modelling Initiative, Openmod, (n.d.). <https://openmod-initiative.org> (accessed July 22, 2024).
- [209] Hydrogen TCP, Hydrogen TCP - Research and Innovation in Hydrogen Technology by IEA, Iea Hydrog. (n.d.). <https://www.ieahydrogen.org/> (accessed November 29, 2023).
- [210] Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, FZJ-IEK3-VSA, GitHub (n.d.). <https://github.com/FZJ-IEK3-VSA> (accessed November 29, 2023).
- [211] Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, IEK-3 Dataverse, (n.d.). <https://data.fz-juelich.de/dataverse/iek-3> (accessed July 22, 2024).
- [212] Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, EnArgus, (n.d.). <https://www.enargus.de/pub/bscw.cgi/?op=enargus.eps2&q=lodgeoss&v=10&id=1213112> (accessed November 29, 2023).
- [213] Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, H2Atlas Africa, (n.d.). <https://www.h2atlas.de/en/> (accessed July 22, 2024).
- [214] OEP Community, Open Energy Ontology, (n.d.). <https://openenergyplatform.org/ontology/> (accessed July 22, 2024).
- [215] Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB), TIB AV-Portal, (n.d.). <https://av.tib.eu/> (accessed November 29, 2023).

- [216] Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB), TIB Leibniz Data Manager, (n.d.). <https://projects.tib.eu/datamanager/> (accessed November 29, 2023).
- [217] Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB), Slide Wiki, (n.d.). <https://slidewiki.org/>.
- [218*] T. Hamann, A.I. Metzmacher, P. Mund, Engineering RDM Survey - Dataset, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7645547>.
- [219*] T. Hamann, A. Metzmacher, P. Mund, M. Galdino, A. Abdelrazeq, R.H. Schmitt, A survey on the dissemination and usage of research data management and related tools in German engineering sciences, (2024). <https://preprints.inggrid.org/repository/view/26/> (accessed May 20, 2024).
- [220*] T. Hamann, M. Robrecht, M.L. Wawer, J.M. Werheid, M. Moser, M.A. Galdino, A. Abdelrazeq, R. Lachmayer, R. Schmitt, Matching Data Life Cycle and Research Processes in Engineering Sciences, (2024). <https://preprints.inggrid.org/repository/view/42/>.
- [221*] T. Hamann, P. Mund, Dataset: Problem-centered interviews results for Matching Data Life Cycle and Research Processes in Engineering Sciences, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11198841>.
- [222*] Leibniz Universität Hannover, Golo's Field Database Platform, (2024). <https://fielddatabaseplatform.nfdi4ing.de/> (accessed August 2, 2024).
- [223] M.W. Grieves, Digital Twins: Past, Present, and Future, in: N. Crespi, A.T. Drobot, R. Minerva (Eds.), Digit. Twin, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2023: pp. 97–121. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21343-4_4.
- [224] R. Stark, C. Fresemann, K. Lindow, Development and operation of Digital Twins for technical systems and services, CIRP Ann. 68 (2019) 129–132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirp.2019.04.024>.
- [225] M. Pantelidakis, K. Mykoniatis, J. Liu, G. Harris, A digital twin ecosystem for additive manufacturing using a real-time development platform, Int. J. Adv. Manuf. Technol. 120 (2022) 6547–6563. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-022-09164-6>.
- [226*] H. Dierend, O. Altun, I. Mozgova, R. Lachmayer, Management of Research Field Data Within the Concept of Digital Twin, in: M. Valle, D. Lehmhus, C. Gianoglio, E. Ragusa, L. Seminara, S. Bosse, A. Ibrahim, K.-D. Thoben (Eds.), Adv. Syst.-Integr. Intell., Springer, Cham, 2023: pp. 205–214. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-16281-7_20.

- [227*] I. Mozgova, G. Jagusch, J. Freund, A. Kraft, T. Glück, K. Herrmann, M. Knöchelmann, R. Lachmayer, Product Life Cycle Oriented Data Management Planning with RDMO at the Example of Research Field Data, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.11588/heibooks.979.c13722>.
- [228*] A. Gooran Orimi, R. Hamlaoui, C. Backe, H. Görner, T. Glück, M.C. Sundermeier, Z. Dai, V. Briken, R. Lachmayer, A Digital Twin Framework for Field Data and Distributed Systems, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8403959>.
- [229] B. Schleich, M.-A. Dittrich, T. Clausmeyer, R. Damgrave, J.A. Erkoyuncu, B. Haefner, J. De Lange, D. Plakhotnik, W. Scheidel, T. Wuest, Shifting value stream patterns along the product lifecycle with digital twins, *Procedia CIRP* 86 (2019) 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2020.01.049>.
- [230] W. Scheidel, I. Mozgova, R. Lachmayer, Product data management in the context of Industry 4.0, *Eng. Chang. World Proc. 59th IWK Ilmenau Sci. Colloq. Tech. Univ. Ilmenau Sept. 11-15 2017* 59, 2017 (2017). https://www.db-thueringen.de/receive/dbt_mods_00033233 (accessed July 18, 2024).
- [231] M. Jafari, A. Kavousi-Fard, T. Chen, M. Karimi, A Review on Digital Twin Technology in Smart Grid, Transportation System and Smart City: Challenges and Future, *IEEE Access* 11 (2023) 17471–17484. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3241588>.
- [232] Z. Wang, R. Gupta, K. Han, H. Wang, A. Ganlath, N. Ammar, P. Tiwari, Mobility Digital Twin: Concept, Architecture, Case Study, and Future Challenges, *IEEE Internet Things J.* 9 (2022) 17452–17467. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JIOT.2022.3156028>.
- [233] M.M. Rathore, S.A. Shah, D. Shukla, E. Bentafat, S. Bakiras, The Role of AI, Machine Learning, and Big Data in Digital Twinning: A Systematic Literature Review, Challenges, and Opportunities, *IEEE Access* 9 (2021) 32030–32052. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3060863>.
- [234] M. Liu, S. Fang, H. Dong, C. Xu, Review of digital twin about concepts, technologies, and industrial applications, *J. Manuf. Syst.* 58 (2021) 346–361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmsy.2020.06.017>.
- [235] F. Tao, H. Zhang, A. Liu, A.Y.C. Nee, Digital Twin in Industry: State-of-the-Art, *IEEE Trans. Ind. Inform.* 15 (2019) 2405–2415. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2018.2873186>.
- [236] Z. Dehghani, Data Mesh Principles and Logical Architecture, *Martinfowler* (2020). <https://martinfowler.com/articles/data-mesh-principles.html>.

- [237] Z. Dehghani, How to Move Beyond a Monolithic Data Lake to a Distributed Data Mesh, Martin Fowler (2019). <https://martinfowler.com/articles/data-monolith-to-mesh.html>.
- [238] Z. Dehghani, Data Mesh, (n.d.). <https://www.oreilly.com/library/view/data-mesh/9781492092384/> (accessed July 28, 2024).
- [239*] C. Backe, A. Gooran Orimi, V. Briken, R. Hamlaoui, H. Görner, Creating Rich Metadata for Collaborative Research: Case Studies and Challenges, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8430752>.
- [240*] B. Wehbe, N. Shah, M. Bande, C. Backe, Sonar-to-RGB Image Translation for Diver Monitoring in Poor Visibility Environments, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7728088>.
- [241] TOTAL E-QUALITY Deutschland e.V., Prädikatsvergabe 2023, (n.d.). https://www.total-e-quality.de/media/modelfield_files/dokumente/dokument/datei/Liste_der_Pr%C3%A4dikatsstr%C3%A4ger_innen_2023_8GtYFLU.pdf.
- [242] TOTAL E-QUALITY Deutschland e.V., Prädikatsvergabe, TOTAL E-Qual. Dtschl. EV (n.d.). <https://www.total-e-quality.de/de/das-praedikat/praedikatsvergabe/> (accessed August 2, 2024).
- [243] Bundesministerium für Familie, Senioren, Frauen und Jugend, Anteil von Frauen und Männern an den erfolgreich abgelegten Abschlussprüfungen der Fächergruppe Ingenieurwissenschaften, Open Data Portal (n.d.). <https://www.daten.bmfsfj.de/daten/daten/anteil-von-frauen-und-maennern-an-den-erfolgreich-abgelegten-abschlusspruefungen-der-faechergruppe-ingenieurwissenschaften-131766> (accessed September 27, 2023).
- [244] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, Chancengleichheits-Monitoring 2024, (n.d.). <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/176148/d38e443f43c5bbd4118d01b48f0d7160/chancengleichheits-monitoring-data.pdf>.
- [245] NFDI4ING, Progress Report NFDI4Ing, (2023). <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/323794/7484ba3d8c944318586bf7620fe98487/nfdi4ing-data.pdf> (accessed August 5, 2024)
- [246] iRight.Labs, Projekt Enter – Der Open-Access-Award, Shortlist (2024). <https://enter-award.irights-lab.de/shortlist/> (accessed August 5, 2024)

- [247] Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, Members of the Review Boards (last updated June 28, 2024). <https://www.dfg.de/en/about-us/statutory-bodies/review-boards/members-of-the-review-boards#EngineeringSciences> (accessed August 5, 2024)
- [248] Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf e.V., HELIPOINT Helmholtz Scientific Project Workflow Platform (n.d.). <https://heliport.hzdr.de/> (accessed August 5, 2024)
- [249] O. Knodel, S. Müller and D. Pape, “Facilitating Research Data Management with HELIPOINT”, (Apr. 11, 2024). doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10993243.
- [250] T. Haase, R. Dr. Glück, P. Kaufmann and M. Willmeroth, “shepard - storage for heterogeneous product and research data”. Zenodo, Jul. 01, 2021. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5091604.
- [251] P. Diercks, D. Gläser, O. Lünsdorf, M. Selzer, B. Flemisch and J. Unger (2023) 'Evaluation of tools for describing, reproducing and reusing scientific workflows', ing.grid. 1(1) doi: 10.48694/inggrid.3726
- [252] P. Houlahan 'Prototyping Python Dashboards for Scientists and Engineers: Build and Deploy a Complete Dashboard with Python' (2024). Apress, Berkeley, CA
- [253] S. Few. 'Information dashboard design: the effective visual communication of data'. O'Reilly, Beijing ; Cambridge [MA], 1st ed edition, 2006. OCLC: ocm63676286.
- [254] H. Luu, A. Aleyasen, M. Winslett, Y. Mostofi, and K. Peng. The Dashboard: HPC I / O Analysis Made Easy. 2015.
- [255] V. Arora, N. Gurrola, A. Maji, and G. Jin. 'A Fast and Responsive Web-based Framework for Visualizing HPC Application Usage'. In: Proceedings of the SC '23 Workshops of The International Conference on High Performance Computing, Network, Storage, and Analysis, pages 708–711, Denver CO USA, November 2023. ACM.
- [256] K. Pauwels, T. Ambler, B. H. Clark, P. LaPointe, D. Reibstein, B. Skiera, B. Wierenga, and T. Wiesel. 'Dashboards as a Service: Why, What, How, and What Research Is Needed?' In: Journal of Service Research, 12(2):175–189, November 2009.
- [257] M. Alhamadi 'Challenges, Strategies and Adaptations on Interactive Dashboards'. In: Proceedings of the 28th ACM Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization, pages 368–371, Genoa Italy, July 2020. ACM.
- [258] K. D. Noubary, M. Kellner, J. Hötzer, M. Seiz, H. J. Seifert, B. Nestler. “Data workflow to incorporate thermodynamic energies from Calphad databases into grand-potential-based phasefield models”. In: Journal of Materials Science 56.20

- [259] Y. C. Yabansu, P. Altschuh, J. Hötzer, M. Selzer, B. Nestler, S. R. Kalidindi. “A digital workflow for learning the reduced-order structure-property linkages for permeability of porous membranes”. In: *Acta Materialia* 195 (2020), S. 668–680. ISSN: 13596454. DOI: 10.1016/j.actamat.2020.06.003.
- [260] R. Darabi, E. Azinpour, A. Reis, J.-C. de Sa ‘Multi-scale Multi-physics Phase-field coupled Thermo-mechanical approach for modeling of powder bed fusion process’. In: *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, Volume 122, 2023, Pages 572-597, ISSN 0307-904X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2023.06.021>.
- [261] J. Hötzer, A. Reiter, H. Hierl, P. Steinmetz, M. Selzer, B. Nestler. “The parallel multi-physics phase-field framework PACE3D”. In: *Journal of Computational Science* 26 (2018), S. 1–12. ISSN: 18777503. DOI: 10.1016/j.jocs.2018.02.011.
- [262] A. Dubey, A. Almgren, J. Bell, M. Berzins, S. Brandt, G. Bryan, P. Colella, D. Graves, M. Lijewski, F. Löffler, B. O’Shea, E. Schnetter, B. Van Straalen and K. Weide ‘A survey of high level frameworks in block-structured adaptive mesh refinement packages’. In: *Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing*, Volume 74, Issue 12, 2014, Pages 3217-3227, ISSN 0743-7315, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpdc.2014.07.001>.
- [263] W. Zhang, A. Myers, K. Gott, A. Almgren, J. Bell. ‘AMReX: Block-structured adaptive mesh refinement for multiphysics applications. In: *The International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications*. 2021;35(6):508-526. doi:10.1177/10943420211022811
- [264] L. Lambers, M. Suditsch, A. Wagner and T. Ricken (2021) ‘A Multiscale and Multiphase Model of Function-Perfusion Growth Processes in the Human Liver’. In: *Proc. Appl. Math. Mech.*, 20: e202000290. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pamm.202000290>
- [265] N. Kohl, J. Hötzer, F. Schornbaum, M. Bauer, C. Godenschwager, H. Köstler, B. Nestler, U. Rude. “A Scalable and Extensible Checkpointing Scheme for Massively Parallel Simulation Software”. In: *International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications* 33.4 (2019), S. 571–589. ISSN: 10943420. DOI: 10.1177/1094342018767736.
- [266] A. Abdelfattah, et al. ‘GPU algorithms for Efficient Exascale Discretizations’. In: *Parallel Computing*, Volume 108, 2021, 102841, ISSN 0167-8191, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parco.2021.102841>.
- [267] J. Ejarque, et al. ‘Enabling dynamic and intelligent workflows for HPC, data analytics, and AI convergence’. In: *Future Generation Computer Systems*, Volume 134, 2022, Pages 414-429, ISSN 0167-739X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2022.04.014>.

[268] A. Francis, et al. (2020) 'Exascale applications: skin in the game' In: Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A.37820190056, <http://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2019.0056>

[269] P. Grete, JC Dolence, JM Miller, et al. 'Parthenon—a performance portable block-structured adaptive mesh refinement framework'. In: The International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications. 2023;37(5):465-486. doi:10.1177/10943420221143775

[270] A. Vondrous, M. Selzer, J. Hötzer, B. Nestler. "Parallel computing for phase-field models". In: International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications 28.1 (2014), S. 61–72. ISSN: 10943420. DOI: 10.1177/1094342013490972.

[271] C. Alappat, G. Hager, O. Schenk and G. Wellein, "Level-Based Blocking for Sparse Matrices: Sparse Matrix-Power-Vector Multiplication" in IEEE Transactions on Parallel & Distributed Systems, vol. 34, no. 02, pp. 581-597, 2023. doi: 10.1109/TPDS.2022.3223512

[272] N. Baumgarten, C. Wieners 'The parallel finite element system M++ with integrated multilevel preconditioning and multilevel Monte Carlo methods'. In: Computers & Mathematics with Applications, Volume 81, 2021, Pages 391-406, ISSN 0898-1221, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2020.03.004>.

[273] M. Bauer, J. Hötzer, D. Ernst, J. Hammer, M. Seiz, H. Hierl, J. Hönig, H. Köstler, G. Wellein, B. Nestler, et al. "Code generation for massively parallel phase-field simulations". In: Proceedings of the International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis. 2019, S. 59.

[274] J. Hötzer, M. Jainta, M. Bauer, P. Steinmetz, M. Kellner, H. Köstler, U. Råde, B. Nestler. "Study of complex microstructure evolution in ternary eutectic alloys with massive parallel large-scale phase-field simulations". In: High Performance Computing in Science and Engineering. Ed. by S. Wagner, A. Bode, H. Brüche, M. Brehm. Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften, Garching/Munich, 2016, S. 194–195. ISBN: 978-3-9816675-1-6.

[275] M. Bauer, J. Hötzer, M. Jainta, P. Steinmetz, M. Berghoff, F. Schornbaum, C. Godenschwager, H. Köster, B. Nestler, U. Råde. "Massively parallel phase-field simulations for ternary eutectic directional solidification". In: International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis, 2015, Austin, United States, 15 November 2015 - 20 November 2015. 2015, S. a8. ISBN: 978-145033723-6. DOI: 10.1145/2807591.2807662.

[276] K. W. Schulz et al. 'Cluster Computing with OpenHPC' (2016), DOI: 10.1145/1235, <https://openhpc.community/>

[277] B. Dröge 'EESSI: A cross-platform ready-to-use optimised scientific software stack'. In: *Software: Practice and Experience* 53 (1), 176-210, 2023. <https://www.eessi-hpc.com/>

[278] D. Hudak et al. 'Open OnDemand: A web-based client portal for HPC centers'. In: *Journal of Open Source Software* 3 (25), 622, 2018. <https://openondemand.org/>

